

**GENE EXPRESSION ANALYSIS OF OESTROGEN
RECEPTORS AND ATYPICAL CHEMOKINE
RECEPTORS IN RESPONSE TO 17- β OESTRADIOL
IN MCF-7**

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Thesis is dedicated to 'My Family

My Homeland Kashmir'

AUTHOR DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this thesis work entitled, 'Gene expression analysis of Estrogen receptors and Atypical chemokine receptors in response to 17 β -Estradiol in MCF-7' is a record of original research work done by me under guidance of Prof Fiona Henriquez and Dr Fiona Menzies, the research staff of School of Science and Sport at the University of West of the Scotland, Paisley Campus.

I declare that the present work was carried out in accordance with the guidelines and regulation of the University of the West of Scotland. This work is original except where indicated by special reference in context. I also declare that I have not submitted this work presented herein to any other University.

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– Shruti Talashi, **April 2024**.

ABSTRACT

17 β -Estradiol (E2) is the most potent form of oestrogen, that binds efficiently to oestrogen receptors type i.e. Oestrogen receptor-alpha (ER α) and oestrogen receptor-beta (ER β) to regulate the cell growth in the tissues. E2 is crucial for the breast development, yet a high level of E2 has been associated with cancer. Inflammation as a cancer hallmark, involve chemokine's which are signalling molecules that attract immune cells to promote cancer spread or metastasis. Interestingly, in cancer biology research, E2 has shown ability to inhibit chemokine production in tumour microenvironment (TME), although the mechanism remains unclear. There are chemokine receptors as atypical chemokine receptors (ACKRs) which are referred to as anti-inflammatory G-protein independent transmembrane proteins that act like "scavengers," removing chemokine's and dampening inflammation. Atypical chemokine receptor type 2 (ACKR2) potentially lowers inflammation & is established as essential gene for the mammary gland development. ACKR 2 is a gene essential for development and it also act as a tumour suppressors. Unlike ACKR 2, ACKR 3 & ACKR 4 are associated with cancer progression. A higher E2 level is found around breast cancer tissues and E2 has the ability to lower chemokine production in cancer environment. E2 can be considered as preventive to cancer from spreading and since ACKRs being expressed in breast cancer. This research delves into this paradox by conduct experiment to investigate the higher E2 effect on ACKRs gene modulation using a hormone responsive breast cancer model.

In-vitro *MCF-7* cell line used as experimental model since it is hormone responsive and most studied breast cancer cell line. For gene expression analysis, *RT-qPCR* technique been optimised to study gene modulation of target gene of interest as ER α/β and *ACKRs* when exposed to higher *E2* levels. Use of published primers for ER β gene isoforms led to multiple (non-specific binding) PCR products. Experiment has been designed to make selection of normalization gene for use in RT-qPCR from few housekeeping gene (HKGs) that had been used in gene expression study before *18S rRNA*, *HPRT1*, *TBP* while introducing *TOP1* gene,

for which primers were designed in-house. Using 'Multialign' and 'Oligocalci' online bioinformatics tool, a new primer was designed for *ERβ* gene and called as *ERβ_iso* primer. *TOP1* as HKG had been chosen as best normalization gene for *RT-qPCR* assay. *E2* (1nM, 100nM, 1μM) & their vehicle control (DMSO ≤ 0.1% v/v) were used to prepare *E2* stimulated samples for gene expression study at two points 6 hours(H) & 18H. Relative gene expression were calculated applying Livak's $\Delta\Delta Cq$ comparative method and for statistical analysis non-parametric Mann-Whitney's U-test had been used. Experimental analysis shown one-fold down regulation of mRNA gene expression of *ER α/β* & two-fold down regulation of mRNA gene expression *ACKR 2*, *ACKR 3* & *ACKR 4* at transcriptional (m-RNA) level. Statistical analysis support this fact as there lies a significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between *E2* treated and vehicle control groups at 18H with a confidence interval 95%, hence *E2* modulate the mRNA gene expression of ACKRs anti-inflammatory mediator.

These findings highlight the seemingly contradictory roles of *E2*. Since it has been considered to fuel tumour growth, it might also have anti-inflammatory properties through a pathway that involve ACKRs gene. Hence it is deemed to further research into the interplay of ERs & ACKRs that could be valuable in finding early biomarkers in breast cancer screening or in developing novel cancer therapies.

Keywords: *E2*-17β-Estradiol; *ERα*- Oestrogen receptor alpha gene; *ERβ* – Oestrogen receptor beta gene; TME – Tumour microenvironment; ACKRs – Atypical Chemokine receptors (*ACKR2* gene, *ACKR3* gene & *ACKR4* gene); *RT-qPCR* – Real time quantitative polymerase chain reaction; HKGs- Housekeeping genes; 18S rRNA – 18S ribosomal ribonucleic acid gene; *HPRT1*- Hypoxanthine Phosphoribosyltransferase 1 gene; *TBP*- Tata Box binding gene ; *TOP1*- Topoisomerase 1; *DMSO* – Dimethyl Sulfoxide; mRNA – messenger ribonucleic acid.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATION

AB	Alamar blue
ABR	Alamar blue reduction
ACKR	Atypical chemokine receptor
ACKR1 or DARC	Atypical chemokine receptor 1 or Duffy Antigen receptor for chemokine
ACKR2 or D6	Atypical chemokine receptor 2 or Decoy Receptor 6
ACKR3	Atypical chemokine receptor 3
ACKR4	Atypical chemokine receptor 4 (CCRL1/CCX-CKR/CCBP2)
ACKR5	Atypical chemokine receptor 5
ACKR6	Atypical chemokine receptor 6 or Nir1 OR PPITP3 (Phosphatidylinositol transfer protein membrane associated 3)
AD	Androstenedione
AGT	Angiotensinogen
AF-1	Activation transcriptional factor 1
AF-2	Activation transcriptional factor 2
AKT	Protein Kinase B
AP-1	Activator protein 1
AR	Aromatase
bp	Base Pair
C3	Complement C3 protein
CCL2 or MCP-1	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 2 or Monocyte Chemoattractant protein-1
CCL3 or MIP-1a	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 3 or Macrophage Inflammatory protein 1 alpha
CCL4 or MIP-1b	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 4 or Macrophage

	Inflammatory protein 1 beta
CCL5 or RANTES	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 5 or Regulated on Activation, normal T cell expressed and secreted
CCL7	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 7
CCL8	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 8
CCL11	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 11
CCL12	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 12
CCL13	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 13
CCL14	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 14
CCL17	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 17
CCL19	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 19
CCL22	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 22
CCR2	C-C chemokine receptor type 2
cDNA	Complementary Deoxyribonucleic acid
CDS	Conserved domain sequence
cFos/Jun	Proto-oncogene Fos family transcriptional factor or Jun family transcriptional factor
CNS	Central nervous system
CoA	Co-activators
CoR	Co-repressors
Cq	Threshold cycle value
CRH	Corticotrophin releasing hormone
C-terminal	Carboxylic acid end terminal of protein
CTSD	Cathepsin D

CXCL1	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 1
CXCL2	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 2
CXCL3	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 3
CXCL8	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 8
CXCL12 or SDF-1	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 12 or Stromal derived factor 1
CXCR2	C-X-C motif chemokine receptor type 2
CXCR3	C-X-C motif chemokine receptor type 3
CXCR4	C-X-C motif Chemokine receptor type 4
CXCR7 or RDC-1	C-X-C motif Chemokine receptor type 7 or orphan receptor
CYP19/P450	Aromatase P450 gene
Cyt c	Cytochrome c oxidase
DAPI	4, 6-diamino-2-phenylindole
DBD	DNA binding domain
DF	Dilution Factor
DHEA	Dehydroepiandrosterone
DHEAS	Dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate
DMEM: F12	Dulbecco's modified eagle medium: nutrient mixture F12
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
DPBS	Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline
DNA	Deoxy-ribonucleic acid
E1	Oestrone
E2	17 β -oestradiol

E3	Oestriol
E4	Oestetrol
ECM	Extracellular matrix
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
EGFR	Epidermal growth receptor factor
ELISA	Enzyme linked immunosorbent assay
EMT	Epithelium mesenchymal transition
Erk1/2	Extracellular signal-regulated kinase 1/2
ER+	Oestrogen receptor positive
ER α	Oestrogen receptor alpha (mRNA) gene
ER β	Oestrogen receptor beta (mRNA) gene
ER β <i>iso</i>	Primer name for oestrogen receptor beta (all mRNA variant) gene
ER β 1	Oestrogen receptor beta 1 (mRNA variant) gene
ER β 2/cx	Oestrogen receptor beta 2/cx (mRNA variant) gene
ERE	Oestrogen receptor element
EROK	Oestrogen receptor knockout gene
ERU	Oestrogen receptor unit
ERRs	Oestrogen related receptors
ER β 1	Oestrogen receptor beta 1 (mRNA variant)
ESR1	Oestrogen receptor gene 1
ESR2	Oestrogen receptor gene 2
EtBr	Ethidium bromide
EtOH	Ethanol

FACLS	Fluorometric assay based on cell lysis and staining
FasL	Cluster of differentiation D95 ligand
FBS	Foetal bovine serum
FWD	Forward
G ₀ /G ₁	Cell resting phase/ Gap 1 phase
GF	Growth factor
GFAP	Glial fibrillary acid protein
GFR	Growth factor receptor
GOI	Gene of interest
GSK3 β	Glycogen synthase kinase 3 beta
H	Hours
HAT	Histone acetyltransferase
HER2	Human epidermal growth factor receptor 2
HKGs	Housekeeping genes
HLF	Human lactoferrin
HPRT1	Hypoxanthine Phosphoribosyl transferase 1
HSP	Heat shock protein
HSP27	Heat shock protein 27
IARC	International association for cancer
IHC	Immunohistochemistry
IL-1a	Interleukin 1 alpha/ hematopoietin 1
Kbp	Kilo base pair
Ki-67	Cell proliferative protein marker

LBA	Ligand binding assay
LBD	Ligand binding domain
LTED	Long term oestrogen deprived
LTEE	Long term oestrogen exposed
M	Molarity
MAPK	Mitogen activated protein kinase
MCF-7	Michigan cancer cell foundation 7
MCR	Metabolic clearance rate
MEK1/2	Mitogen activated protein kinase1/2
MIQE	Minimum information for publication of Quantitative Real-time PCR experiments
mRNA	Messenger ribonucleic acid
mTOR	mammalian target of rampamycin
MTT	3(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide
NCBI	National centre for biotechnology information
NO	Nitric Oxide
NR	Nuclear receptor
NSC	Normal serum concentration
NTC	No-reverse transcriptase template control
N-terminal	Amino acid end terminal of a protein
OXT	Oxytocin
PAFR2	Platelet activating receptor transcript 2
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction

PgR/PGR	Progesterone receptor
PI3K	Phosphoinositide 3-kinase
PI3K-AKT-NF- κ B	Phosphatidyl inositol- 3 kinase-protein kinase B- Necrotic factor kappa β
PS2	Trefoil factor 1
PTMA	Prothymosin α
PYK2	Protein tyrosine kinase 2
REV	Reverse
RNA	Ribonucleic acid
RT-qPCR	Real time- quantitative polymerase chain reaction
RXRA	Retinoic acid receptor a1
SD	Standard deviation
SF-1	Steroidogenic factor 1
SP-1	Specificity protein 1
Snail	Protein family of zinc-finger transcription factor
SR	Secretion rate
STS	Steroid sulfatase
T	Testosterone
TAMs	Tumour associated macrophages
TBP	TATA-binding protein gene
TBE	TRIS-borate-EDTA buffer
TGF- β 1	Transforming growth factor beta 1
TGFA	Transforming growth factor
TOP1	Topoisomerase 1 gene

TRIS	Tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane
UK	United Kingdom
UV	Ultraviolet
VEGF	Vascular endothelial growth factor
2D	Two-Dimension
17 β -HSD1	17 beta hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 1
17 β -HSD2	17 beta hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 2
17 β -HSD3	17 beta hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 3
18S rRNA	18 subunit ribosomal ribonucleic acid
28S rRNA	28 Subunit ribosomal ribonucleic acid
CH ₃ Cl	Chloroform
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
ddH ₂ O	Double distilled water
-OH	Hydroxyl
°C	Degree Celsius
%	Percentage
α	Alpha
β	Beta
+	Positive
-	Negative
x g	Relative centrifugal force
Cells/mL	Cells per millilitre
L/day	Litre per day

mg/day	milligram per day
mL	Millilitre
ng/g	Nanogram per gram
ng/ μ L	Nanogram per microliter
nm	Nanometre
nM(mol/L)	Nanomolar
nmol/L(M)	Nanomole per litre
pg/mL	Picogram per millilitre
pmol/L	Picomole per litre
units/mL	Units per millilitre
v/v	Volume by volume
μ L	Microliter
μ g	Microgram
μ g/mL	Microgram per millilitre
$\Delta\Delta$ Ct	delta delta threshold cycle value
$2^{\Delta\Delta$ Ct	Fold change

Chapter 1

Literature

Review

1.0 Literature Review

1.1 Oestrogen in the human body

Oestrogen are steroid hormones that are biologically active molecules playing a key role in the development, function, and maintenance of the reproductive system in the human body. It is also known to play similar role for the cardiovascular, musculoskeletal, central nervous system (CNS) and immune system of the human body. Oestrogen is a common term used for four of its physiological forms. These are named as oestrone (E1), oestradiol (E2), oestriol (E3) and oestetrol (E4) and are shown in *figure 1.1*. Of the four oestrogen types, the oestetrol (E4) been the latest, discovered by Dr Egon Diczfalusy at the Karolinska Institute in Stockholm in the year 1965 (*Hagen et al, 1965*). Structurally E4 is an oestrogenic steroid with four hydroxyl groups and produced by developing foetal liver during pregnancy (*Holinka et al, 2008*).

Figure 1.1 Chemical structure of the different forms of oestrogen A. Oestrone (E1); B. Oestradiol (E2); C. Oestriol (E3) & D. Oestetrol (E4) with different positioning of the hydroxyl (-OH) structural groups shown in red. (Figure generated using chemdraw)

E2 is the most potent and ubiquitous form of the oestrogen with higher in efficiency to bind to its oestrogen receptors (ERs) types i.e. oestrogen receptor alpha ($ER\alpha$) and oestrogen receptor beta ($ER\beta$).The complex of E2-ERs, initiates also regulates cell development & growth via various cell signalling pathways. (Klinge, 2001)

The *figure 1.2* shows the pathway involved in initiation of ERs gene expression inside the cell by hormone.

Figure 1.2 Regulation of gene expression by steroid hormones in human cell. (Figure is adapted from online source: <https://schoolworkhelper.net/the-endocrine-system-function-and-structure/>)

1.1.1 Quantities of oestrogen in human males and females

The serum concentration of oestrogen in human body is higher in female as compared to male (*Table 1.1*). In females, the estrogenic level varies throughout

life time as from the onset of menstrual cycle (follicular and luteal phase), time of pregnancy (luteal phase only) and until menopause (Reed & Carr, 2000).

Table 1.1 Representation of Metabolic clearance rate (MCR), Production Rate (PR), Secretion Rate (SR) & Normal serum concentrations (NSC) of major steroid hormones in human male and female. (Table is adapted from Yen & Jaffe's Reproductive Endocrinology, 2004)

Steroid hormones	Reproductive phase	MCR (L/day) Litre per day	PR (mg/day) Milligram per day	SR (mg/day)	NSC
Male		Testis			
Androstenedione (AD)	-	2200	2.8	1.6	2.8-7.3 nmol/L (Nano mole per litre)
Oestrone (E1)	-	2050	0.15	0.11	37-250 nmol/L
Oestradiol (E2)	-	1600	0.06	0.05	<37-210 pmol/ (Pico mole per litre)
Female		Ovary			
Androstenedione (AD)		2000	3.2	2.8	3.1-12.2 nmol/L
Oestrone (E1)	Follicular	2200	0.11	0.08	110-400 nmol/L
	Luteal	2200	0.26	0.15	310-660 pmol/L
	Postmenopausal	1610	0.04	Insignificant	22-230 pmol/L
Oestradiol (E2)	Follicular	1200	0.09	0.08	<37-360 pmol/L
	Luteal	1200	0.25	0.24	699-1250 pmol/L
	Postmenopausal	910	0.006	Insignificant	<37-140 pmol/L

1.1.2 Role of Oestrogen in reproductive health

The main function of oestrogen is in the development of female reproductive and secondary sexual characteristics. It helps decelerate the height increase in females during puberty, it accelerates burning of body fat and reduces muscle bulk. It also stimulates growth of the inner lining of the uterus (endometrium) during the menstrual cycle, increases uterine growth, improves lubrication of the vagina, and thickens the vaginal wall while increasing blood vessels to the *skin* (Mandal, 2016 reviewed by April Cashin-Garbutt).

In premenopausal women, oestrogen are produced primarily in the ovaries, corpus luteum, and placenta, although a small but significant amount of oestrogen can also be produced by non-gonad organs, such as the liver, heart, skin, and brain (Cui *et al*, 2013). Oestradiol mains to stromal development and ductal growth in the breast or mammary gland via inducing gene expression for other mitogens such as Amphiregulin (Forster *et al*, 2002; LaMarca & Rosen, 2008; Brisken & O'Malley, 2010; Kariagina *et al*, 2010). It has also known to causes adipose tissues in women to accumulate around the hips and breast and is also involved in the development of the endometrial lining (Hebbar *et al*, 2014).

During the menstrual cycle, E2 reaches its highest level immediately before ovulation; levels of circulating E2 during the follicular phase, pre-ovulatory phase, and luteal phase are 19–140 pg/ml, 110–410 pg/ml, and 19–160 pg/ml, respectively, whereas in postmenopausal women they are below 35 pg/ml (Cui *J et al*, 2013). During the menopause transition, serum E2 levels decrease by 85–90% and serum E1 levels decrease by 65–75% from mean pre-menopausal levels (Khosla *et al*, 1997). In males, E2 is known to play important physiological roles for maintenance of a healthy libido, erectile functions and in spermatogenesis (reviewed by Schulster *et al*, 2016).

1.1.3 Other physiological roles of oestrogen

Oestrogen exerts various biological effects via oestrogen receptors types in different systems of human body such as the central nervous system, the musculoskeletal & cardiovascular system and is known to influence the immune

system development and function (reviewed by Paterni et al, 2014). Oestrogen regulate cell proliferation by increasing production of steroid binding protein such as albumin in the hepatic cells (reviewed by Hammond, 2016).

In women, oestrogen have been reported to have various other physiological functions such as taking part in regulating synthesis of lipoprotein, affecting response to insulin, preventing urogenital atrophy (reviewed by Cagnacci, 1992). The human brain is an additional extra gonadal site of oestrogen synthesis, and it can synthesize oestrogen from cholesterol (Do Rego et al, 2009). Oestrogen are important for an early development, not only for primary and secondary sexual characteristics but also for embryonal and foetal development of the brain networks (reviewed by McCarthy, 2008).

Oestrogen is responsible for the maintenance of the normal structure of the skin and blood vessels and take part in decreasing the rate of resorption of calcium in bone (reviewed by Green et al, 1993). Oestrogen has profound role in bone formation, in post-menopausal women oestrogen is used as pharmacological agent to prevent bone loss. While understanding the oestrogen deficiency to bone loss the mechanism is multifaced and complex in post-menopausal women occurrence of osteoporosis is linked to integration of a multitude of redundant pathways and cytokines while oestrogen are known to directly affect bone cells and regulate level of adaptive immune response (Weitzmann & Pacifici, 2006). Looking at oestrogen functional importance in developing brain an aromatase-knockout mouse has shown impaired in various behaviours, such as sexual, aggressive, and locomotive behaviours (Honda et al, 2011), whereas aromatase depletion in an animal model for alzheimer's disease (AD) led to earlier and more severe neuropathology than observed in ovariectomized control mice (Cui et al, 2013). Cell-specific E2 can be formed from circulating testosterone or cholesterol by neurons and astrocytes (Yague et al, 2006), but not by microglia or oligodendrocytes (Gottfried-Blackmore et al, 2008). Under normal physiological conditions, neurons are the major site for E2 synthesis in the brain, but elevated aromatase expression in astrocytes has been found following brain injury,

suggesting that neuronal impairment can induce E2 production in astrocytes (Yague et al, 2006). The brain produces its own E2, in addition to utilizing circulating E2 and C19 steroid precursors (a substrate for oestrogen synthesis) to provide essential substrates for oestrogen synthesis in the brain (Kancheva et al, 2011). It has been reported that E2 levels in the brain are 0.08–0.19 ng/g wet weight (Rosario et al, 2011). In the brain, oestrogen action affects both the activity and the connectivity of certain neuronal populations and thereby modulates physiological parameters important for regulating animal reproduction including mood and behaviour, gonadotropin production and release from the pituitary and locomotor activity also suggests that oestrogen may also mediate non-reproductive events including learning and memory (reviewed by Joel, 1997; Wickelgren, 1997).

Oestrogen can promote the accumulation of sub-cutaneous fat (reviewed by Krotkiewski et al, 1983) and loss of oestrogen in body during menopause is associated with an increase in body fat (reviewed by Lee et al, 2009; Poehlman et al, 1995). Accumulation of adipose tissue or fat, in the intra-abdominal adipose depot is associated with an increased risk of developing cardiovascular problems, type-2 diabetes mellitus, obesity, certain cancers and other disorders like the metabolic syndrome (reviewed by Brown & Clegg, 2010).

The frequencies of migraine have close relation with hormonal changes throughout life in women as 60% of women migraineurs showed an association between migraine and menstruation and evidence suggested that oestrogen withdrawal may be a trigger for menstrual migraine in susceptible women (Zacur & Howard, 2006). E2 supplementation before the onset of menses delayed the onset of migraine without delay in menses but not a similar outcome was reported in case of progesterone administration. This finding provided evidence that oestrogen withdrawal is related to trigger menstrual migraine (Somerville, 1971; Somerville, 1972).

Oestrogen affects gene expression in the central nervous system (CNS) through interaction with intracellular oestrogen receptors, ER α and ER β . These receptors are widely distributed throughout the CNS, and, when activated by Estrogen binding, the E2-ER complex serve as transcription factors and initiate transcription. Oestrogen can elicits more rapid effects in the CNS through interactions with membrane-bound oestrogen receptors that, in turn, activate second-messenger in signal pathway system. It can also alter the activity of ion channels and modulates the rates of neuronal firing (*reviewed by Martin & Behbehani, 2006*). Studies using EROK- mice for ER α and ER β have revealed that each subtype plays unique role in oestrogen biology in a wide variety of target tissues as the lack of ER types not only affect the reproductive phenotype but can also induces abnormalities in brain (*reviewed by Couse & Korach, 1999*).

1.2 Biosynthesis of Oestrogen

Biosynthesis of oestrogen starts from the cholesterol followed by a cascade of enzymatic reactions within functional tissues such as ovary, liver, heart, muscle, bone and brain in the human body. The three most important enzymes responsible for tissue-specific biosynthesis of oestrogen are cytochrome P450 aromatase (P450arom), oestrogen/steroid sulfatase (ES /STS) and 17 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type-1 (17 β HSD1) (*Figure 1.3*). This three-enzyme system is primarily responsible for biosynthesis of the female hormone in breast, ovary, placenta, endometrium and other tissues (*Purohit et al, 1997*).

Figure 1.3 Three enzyme systems of oestrogen bio-synthesis in breast, ovary, placenta, endometrium and other tissues. (Enzyme related genes - P450 Aromatase enzyme, 17βHSD 17β-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type-1, ES/STS Oestrogen/steroid sulfatase). Source Purohit et al, 1997 & figure is created using chemdraw.

ES is bound to the membrane of the endoplasmic reticulum, presumably through multiple transmembrane and other membrane anchoring segments. The highly hydrophobic nature of the enzyme has so far prevented its purification to homogeneity in quantities that is sufficient for crystallization while its purification, biochemical characterization and crystallization of the full-length, active form from the membrane bound fraction of human placenta was first structural study of a membrane bound human sulfatase and subsequent rational design of inhibitors for use as anti-tumour agents. (Ghosh et al, 2010)

Oestrogen sulphate has a relatively long half-life in the peripheral blood, and the level is 5–10 times higher than that of unconjugated oestrogen such as E1, E2 and E3 in postmenopausal women. (*Pasqualini, 2004*)

Tissue concentration of E2 in the breast carcinoma was 5-fold higher than in plasma in premenopausal women, and 23-fold higher in postmenopausal women (*Pasqualini, 2004*). E2 concentration was also 2-fold higher in breast carcinoma tissues than in the areas considered as morphologically normal. (*Chetrite et al, 2000*) E1S or STS catalyses the hydrolysis of E1/steroid sulphate releasing unconjugated E1 or steroids. ES is a component of the three-enzyme system that has been implicated in intracrine biosynthesis of E2 responsible towards proliferation of hormone dependent breast tumour. (*Hernandez-Guzman et al, 2001*)

Enzymes necessary for oestrogen synthesis involves aromatase (P450/CYP19A/AR), 17 β -HSD-1, 2 & 3 and oestrone sulfatase (ES) which are present within normal functional breast tissues (*Santner et al, 1984*) while activities of these enzymes in tumour tissues are found to be elevated than normal tissues (*James et al, 1987*). E1 can be converted to E1 sulfate by oestrone sulfotransferase (E1ST) enzyme and E1 sulfate can be catalysed back to E1 by E1S enzyme. Furthermore, E1 and E2 have been found to be inter-convertible by action of 17 β -HSD1 & 17 β -HSD2; hence, the conversion of E1 to E2 leads to the increased levels of E2 which has been proposed to play an important role in the proliferation of breast cancer (*Siitri & MacDonald, 1966*). This reaction involving enzymes that mentioned are in *Figure 1.4*.

Figure 1.4 Oestrogen synthesis involving enzymes AR-Aromatase, 17-β HSD-1, 2 & 3 - 17-β dehydrogenase type 1, 2 & 3 E1S- Estrone sulfatase & E1ST- Oestronesulfotransferase (Figure is adapted from Siitri & MacDonald, 1966 & drawn using Chemdraw).

Although oestrogen production in all tissues contributes to cellular health, the two most well studied and influential target sites of E2 productions are the ovaries and brain. Synthesis of oestrogen in ovaries occurs during the process of follicle formation both thecal and granulosa cells are involved in cell-specific oestrogen synthesis. Thecal cells cannot produce oestrogen, but do produce androgens; conversely, granulosa cells cannot produce androgen from progesterone, but can convert androgen into E2. Therefore, in growing follicles androgen is released from thecal cells and transported into granulosa cells where it is metabolized into oestrogen by AR enzyme. These ovary-derived oestrogen are released into general circulation and target the distal oestrogen-responsive tissues in the body including reproductive and non-reproductive organs (Hillier et al, 1994).

1.3 Cellular signalling pathways of oestrogen

Oestrogen receptors belong to the nuclear receptors (NRs) form of a large superfamily of transcriptional factors which is present in all metazoan phyla that share a common evolutionary origin. NRs superfamily evolved following two waves of gene duplication, the first one occurred during metazoan evolution that resulted in its diversification into six subfamilies. The second of this event occurred in the vertebrates that produced different paralogues within each of the subfamily. The ligand binding function of NRs acquired during metazoan evolution where DNA binding and dimerization function co-evolved with NRs (*reviewed by Escriva et al, 2004*).

Oestrogen is known to influence the expression of wide range of genes via ER. ERs are members of NRs superfamily and has a broad range of biological role to play in living body one of which most discussed being the growth, differentiation and physiology of the reproductive system (*reviewed by Pearce ST et al, 2004*). These receptors also play vital role in non-reproductive tissues such as bone, cardiovascular system, brain and liver (*reviewed by Heldring et al, 2007*).

Oestrogen bind to ER and activated ER dimer then bind to specific sequence on the DNA that is responsible for regulation region of target gene, called oestrogen response elements (EREs). EREs involves proteins with consensus sequence variations in 5'-GGTCA nnn TGACC-3' (*Table 1.2*). Such ER action is seen to be involving ligand directly which is called to be the genomic pathway or indirectly which means not dependent on hormonal ligand for gene activation which is termed as non-genomic pathway. These types of interaction with specific sequence of DNA known as EREs or even can be with ERE like sequences which is seen in the regulatory region of oestrogen target gene making to a concept of oestrogen response unit (ERU). Moreover, ER can interact with half palindromic or in combination with half palindromic elements that can mediate oestrogen inducibility (*Kushner et al, 2000*).

Table 1.2: List of proteins involved in gene regulation with differences in ERE (Table adapted from Kushner et.al, 2000).

Protein	Gene symbol	Difference	Sequence & details
Oxytocin	OXT	No. of nucleotides differing from the consensus : 1	GGTGA nnn TGACC
pS2	PS2	No. of nucleotides differing from the consensus : 1	GGTCA nnn TGACC
Angiotensinogen	AGT	No. of nucleotides differing from the consensus : 1	GGGCA nnn TGACC
Cathepsin D	CTSD	No. of nucleotides differing from the consensus : 2	GGCCG nnn TGACC
Glial fibrillary acid protein	GFAP	No. of nucleotides differing from the consensus : 2	GGGTA nnn TGACC
Complement C3	C3	No. of nucleotides differing from the consensus : 2	GGTGG nnn TGACC
Vascular endothelial growth factor	VEGF	No. of nucleotides differing from the consensus : 3	AATCA nnn TGACT
Corticotropin releasing hormone	CRH	Four half-palindromes	Four half-ERE sites occur in promoter gene
Platelet activating receptor transcript 2	PAFR2	Two half palindromes	Two different promoters yield two transcripts of receptor; transcript 2 is ERU with two half ERE sites separated by 153 bp
Prothymosin α	PTMA	Two half-palindromes	5 kbp promoter region has two half palindromic EREs at position -750 and -1050
Lactoferrin	HLF	Retinoic acid response element overlaps with ERE can get activated by retinoic receptor and ER	AGGTCA n AGGTCA
Heat shock protein 27	HSP27	ERE half element synergistic with Sp1 site 10 bp away	GGGCGGG(Sp1)n(10)GGTC A
c-fos	CFOS	Overlapping with two sequences homologous to the core sequence of AP-1 transcription binding site	CGGCA gcg TGACC
Transforming growth factor α	TGFA	Two imperfect palindromes separated by 20 bp	GGTCA nnnn TGCCC n(20) GGTGA nnn TAGCC
Retinoic acid receptor α 1	RXRA	ERE/Sp1 separated by 10 bp	GGTGA and GGC GGG
Progesterone receptor	PGR	Half ERE two Sp1 binding site	TGACC nnnn CCGCCC nnnn CCGCCC

Few other activations of pathways of oestrogen involves the ER related receptors (ERRs), nuclear orphan's receptors with significant homology to ERs, which do not bind to oestrogen and have unknown physiological ligand. One of such receptors is known to bind to steroidogenic factor 1 (SF-1) response element

which is an ERE half site preceded by thymine-cytosine-adenine trinucleotide (Wilson et al, 1993)

ERs are DNA binding proteins belonging to nuclear receptor family of transcriptional factors that are mediated the effect of E2 in ligand dependent or independent signalling pathways as discussed before. The genomic pathway (ligand dependent) is mainly regulated by the ERs in the nucleus of the cell (Kraus et al, 1995) whereas the non-genomic pathways in mainly mediated by the receptor in the cell membrane or within the cytosol of cell and does not require to enter the nucleus to regulate the target gene (Wang et al,2007).

In the genomic pathway, hormone binding to ER causes the migration of these receptors from cytosol to nucleus, dimerization of the receptors and activation of transcription upon binding to ERE such as Cathepsin D while in non-genomic pathway E2 activate ER then (Fig.1.5, below).

(A)

(B)

Figure 1.5 Molecular mechanism of ERs action (A) showing the ligand dependent (genomic and non-genomic pathways) while (B) showing ligand independent pathway/rapid signalling pathway. (Figure is adapted from Thomas C et. al., 2011).

The non-genomic pathway (ligand dependent/independent) may involve ERs bound to the cell membrane, some of which are also found to be attached to caveolin-1 and complexed with receptor and non-receptor tyrosine kinase or G-couple receptor proteins (Zivadinovic et al, 2005). Upon activation by oestrogen, signal is sent to the nucleus through mitogen activated protein kinase (MAPK/ERK) and phospho-inositol 3 kinase (PI3K/AKT) pathways which phosphorylates glycogen synthase kinase (GSK-3 β) removing its inhibitory effect on nuclear ER α (Kato et al,1995). Level of Ca²⁺ and nitric oxide (NO) might also

increase in the cytoplasm through signalling cascade involving secondary messenger (*Devikar et al, 2011; Lu et al, 2004*).

In non-genomic ligand independent pathway on the other hand involves growth factor induced activation of kinases that lead to the phosphorylation of ER, thus activating it. The well-studied transcriptional regulation by E2 can also induce rapid effects via membrane ER which includes kinases and phosphatase activation and increased membrane ion fluxes (*Thomas & Gustafsson, 2011*).

1.3.1 Oestrogen receptor types

Until 1996, only one human ER was known which was renamed ER α as a novel ER was cloned from rat prostate and it was named as ER β (*Kupier et al, 1996*). The complete human ER β cDNA was published in 1998 (*Ogawa et al, 1998*).

ER α and ER β share high degree of homology in their gene structure. The most conserved domain in ERs is DNA binding domain (DBD), the region in gene which is responsible for binding to specific DNA sequence i.e. oestrogen responsive elements (EREs) in target gene promoter region. A/B region located N-terminal of the protein domain is least conserved part among the two ERs with only 16% homology and in fictional only in ER α subtype shown in *Figure 1.6* (*Sotoca et al, 2012*).

The C-terminal of the protein contains the ligand dependent transactivation domain AF-2, the ligand binding domain (LBD) and homo/hetero dimerization site. Homology of between E/F regions of both proteins is only 53% explaining difference in ligand binding affinity between two receptors. Hinge region located in the D domain contain the nuclear localized in the D domain contain the nuclear localization signal of the ERs as well as post translational modification site (*Sentis et al, 2005*). Information on structural and functional relationship of this region is very limited and it appear to be a variable and not well conserved part of ER (30% homology).

The A/B region located in the N-terminus of the protein encompasses the AF-1 domain responsible for ligand independent transactivation while this region is least conserved part among the two ERs with only 30% homology and it is known functional only in ER α subtype (Hall & McDonnel, 1999).

Figure 1.6 Showing the domains and homology in sequence of ER α and ER β . (A/B refers to N-terminal domain, C refers to DNA binding domain, D refers to hinge region, E refers to ligand binding domain and F refers to C terminal domain) Figure is adapted from Sotocia et al, 2012

When E2 binds to the ERs it induces the ligand binding domain (LBD) to undergo a conformational change upon which the receptor forms dimer and finally the dimer complex binds to oestrogen response element (ERE) of DNA inside the nucleus to initiate the gene transcription (Cowley et al, 1997; Katzenellenbogen & Katzenellenbogen, 2000).

1.3.2 Oestrogen receptors structure and functional domain

The later discovered ER β receptor was thought to be substituting the function of ER α in ER α knockout mice but a double ER $\alpha\beta$ knockout mice model revealed that life is possible without either or both the receptor, but this model has shown a

severely impaired or complete loss of reproductive function (*Krege et al, 1998; reviewed by Couse & Korach, 1999*).

ER α and ER β are composed of three independent and interacting functional domains: the NH₂-terminal or A/B domain, the C or DNA-binding domain, and the D/E/F or ligand-binding domain (*Fig.1.6*). Binding of a ligand to ERs triggers conformational changes in the receptor, translocate it to the ERE for the initiation of transcription of various genes that are mostly oestrogen-regulated. These events, and the order in which they occur in the overall process, are not completely understood, but they include receptor dimerization, receptor-DNA interaction, recruitment of and interaction with co-activators (CA) and other transcription factors, and formation of a pre-initiation complex (*Shibata et al, 1997; Rachez et al, 1998; McKenna et al, 1999; Karus et al, 1995; Karus & Kadonaga, 1998; Beato, 1989; Beekman, 1993*).

E2 is the most potent steroid hormone among oestrogen which acts via binding to two known nuclear receptor family oestrogen receptor (ER) subtypes: ER α and ER β encoded as ESR1 (ER α) and ESR2 (ER β) located on human chromosomes number 6 and 14, respectively also that ER(s) exist in variants forms and exert distinct cellular functions following activation in response to ligand-binding or a ligand-independent manner (*Stefan et.al, 2001*). Hormone activated ER form dimers with each other: ER α ($\alpha\alpha$), ER β ($\beta\beta$) homodimers or ER $\alpha\beta$ ($\alpha\beta$) heterodimers. Both ERs sub-types have high homology in DNA and ligand binding domains of 97% and 60% respectively (*Tremblay et al, 1997*).

The two forms of oestrogen receptor α and β of human ER are functionally distinct, ER β does not has AF-2 region rather contain a repressor domain that when removed increase the overall transcriptional activity of the receptor. ER β function as a trans dominant inhibitor of ER α transcriptional activity at sub-saturating E2 concentration underlying two mains as 1) ER α and ER β can form heterodimers with in target cells and 2) ER β interact with the target gene promote in a ligand-independent manner. Earlier data indicated that one role of ER β is to modulate the ER α transcriptional activity and thus the relative expression level of these two

isoforms will be a key determinant of cellular response to agonist and antagonist (Hall & McDonnell, 1999).

E2 activates ER leading to its dimerization after which this protein complex is transported to nucleus via carrier proteins and later it binds to the ERE situated on specific DNA sequence sites. This then leads to different effects on the cell, such as change in cell morphology, motility and proliferation (Lazennec et al, 2001). Several isoforms of ER are known to exist due to exons deletions, insertions or C-terminal mRNA splicing with at least 3 ER α (66, 46 and 36kDa) and 5 ER β (full length 60kDa) having been identified. ER α variants mostly differ in the 5'-UTR and not in the coding sequence with short isoforms, ER α -36 and ER α -46, lacking exon-1 and AF-1 been identified. ER β 2 or ER β cx has its C-terminal truncated (exon 8) with a unique 26 amino acid inserted in the ligand binding domain and shares identical sequence from exon 1-7 with ER β 1 (Li et al., 2015).

Studies have shown that ER β can antagonize ER α dependent transcription, with an example of alteration in AP-1 dependent transcriptional regulation of ER β by altering recruitment of *c-Fos* to AP-1 regulated promoters (Matthews & Gustafsson, 2003; Matthews et al, 2006). Furthermore, ER α proteolytic degradation is increased by the expression of ER β and its variant ER β 2/cx suggesting that ER β mediated inhibition is accomplished by the combination of key transcription factors recruitment and ER α degradation (Matthews et al, 2006). Above listed studies suggest that a balancing act between ER α and ER β signalling dictates the overall response of proliferation induced by E2.

1.3.3 Variant & Isoforms of ER β

There are 20 alternative splice variants for ER α known in breast cancer and other tumours out of which three are proven to be functionally different in breast cancer progression i.e. ER α 66, ER α 46 & ER α 36 (Phoola et al, 2000) while ER β variant (Figure 1.7) have been reported from various human tissues and cancer cell lines (Lewandowski et al, 2002).

The ER α 46 isoform has been identified in the MCF-7 breast cancer cell line in which it is co-expressed with the full length ER α 66. Unlike ER α 66, the truncated isoform ER α 44 does not mediate E2 dependent cell proliferation and high level of this isoform is seen with E2 stimulated growth being & has been associated with cell cycle arrest in the G0/G1 phase (Penot *et al*, 2005). The presence of ER β isoforms has been confirmed in various human cell lines as well as in a broad range of human tissues at different levels which provides another possible mechanism of tissue dependent modulation of the ER response. Isoforms of ERs types should be considered in human cell line or tissue response to oestrogen as previous studies have shown differential and antagonistic properties of ERs types with their differential distribution in human tissues that might significantly influence biological response to hormone action (Leung *et al*, 2006; Moore *et al*, 1998).

Figure 1.7 Protein structures of ER β isoforms full length isoforms showing functional domain regions. (Figure is adapted from Leung *et al*, 2006)

At present functionality of ER β isoforms are not well understood. The ER β 1 which is the full-length protein with LBD and active AF-2 domain. ER β 2, 4 and 5 have shortened Helix 11 and a full-length Helix 12 is present only in ER β 1 and ER β 2. ER β 2 has a different orientation than ER β 1 due to short helix 11 which limits its ligand access to binding pocket (*Leung et al,2006*). Because of their altered structure ER β 2, 4 and 5 cannot form homo-dimer and have no transcriptional activity on their own, although they have shown to hetero dimerize with ER β 1 upon treatment with E2 and enhance its AF-2 mediated transcriptional activity (*Leung et al,2006*). Studies showing interactions between different ER β isoforms with ER α are very limited. However, ER β 2 (also named as ER β cx) was shown to limit DNA binding of ER α 66 that inhibit its transcriptional activity in similar manner to ER β 1 (*Ogawa et al, 1998*). The most important point is that ER α expression induces significant cell proliferation in the absence of ER β but not the other way around. Cell proliferation is triggered by classical genomic and non-genomic pathways while only the wild type ER α can induce hormone dependent proliferation and it has been shown that most of the ER variants do not mediate ligand dependent proliferation. The overall biological effects of E2 and other oestrogenic compounds in breast cancer cells are the result of complex interplay between various mechanism involving ER subtypes, co-activators and co-repressors, sequences of target EREs but also the cross talk with growth factors pathways, immune cells and activity of certain kinase and phosphatases. All these factors taken together enable response to oestrogen or anti-oestrogens (*Sotoca et al, 2012*).

1.4 Cancer

1.4.1 Introduction to cancer

Cancer disease is the second leading cause of death in the world, characterised by its ability to alter any normal cells of the body to grow out of cellular growth control mechanism to lead to a neoplastic state (*Sudhakar, 2009*). Cancer continues to be the cause of mortality and morbidity among humans despite rapid advances in the field of science and medicines. Cancer or neoplasia is

characterized by abnormal and uncontrolled proliferation of cells due to defects in regulatory circuits that governs normal growth, signalling and homeostasis (*Hahn & Weinberg, 2002*). Cancer is primarily an environmental disease with 90-95% of cases attributed to environment factors and 5-10% due to genetics. Environmental means any because which is not genetic. Common environmental factors that contribute to cancer death include tobacco (25-30%), diet and obesity (30-35%), infections (15-20%), radiation (both ionizing and non-ionizing, up to 10%), stress, lack of physical activity and environmental pollutant (*Anand et al, 2008*). Apart from alteration in oncogenes and tumour suppressor genes, mutation in stability genes (involved in repair, growth and invasion) is known to be associated with malignancy (*Hanahan & Weinberg, 2000*). These genetic alterations are known to occur by point mutation, deletion, gene amplification, chromosomal translocation or other mechanism such as methylation of cytosine bases in DNA or modification of chromatin structure (by acetylation or phosphorylation) can lead to modification of the expression of genes. Estimates predict that during the process of tumorigenesis, cell must acquire a minimum of six mutations to become malignant. These mutations include those that render malignant cell-sufficient in growth signals, insensitive to growth-inhibitory signals, to replicate extensively, avoid apoptosis or programmed cell death, have sustained angiogenesis and competent to invade and produce distant tumours (*Knudson, 1995*).

A tumour growth is classified as “benign” if the cells remain confined or localized at a specific site which makes them treatable by surgery. However, tumour may acquire properties by which they invade the surrounding tissues and spread to near and distinct sites and are termed “malignant”. Malignant cancer cells invade into adjacent tissues and travel to distant sites where they may succeed in forming new colonies by the process called metastasis (*Liotta & Stetler-Stevenson, 1993*).

1.4.2 Cancer in world

In 2008 GLOBOCAN a project which is complete cancer investigation data base managed by the international association of cancer registries (IARC), estimated

12.7 million new cancer cases and 7.6 million cancer deaths in 2008 with 56% of new cases and 63% of the cancer deaths occurring in the less developed regions of the world. The most commonly diagnosed cancer worldwide is lung (1.61 million, 12.7% of the total). Breast (1.38 million, 10.9%) and the colorectal cancer (1.23 million, 9.7%) and liver cancer (696,000 deaths, 9.2%) (Ferlay et al, 2010). GLOBOCAN projects survey has described 14.1 million new cases and 8.2 million deaths in year 2012. The most commonly diagnosed were lung (1.82 million), breast (1.67 million) and colorectal (1.36 million) while the most common cause of cancer death was due to lung cancer (1.6 million deaths), Liver cancer (745,000 deaths and stomach cancer (723,000 deaths). Breast cancer is the second most common cancer in the world and by far the most frequent cancer among women with an estimated 1.67 million new cancer cases diagnosed in 2012 (25% of all cancers. Breast cancer rank as the fifth cause of death from cancer overall (522,000 deaths) and while it is the most frequent cause of cancer death in women in less developed regions (324,000 deaths, 14.3%of total), it is now the second cause of cancer death in more developed regions (198,000 deaths, 15.4%) after lung cancer. Prostate cancer is the fourth most common cancer and second most common cancer in men. An estimated 1.1 million cases were diagnosed worldwide with prostate cancer in 2012, accounting for 15% of the cancer diagnosed in men with almost 70% for them (759,000) occurring in more developed regions. Cancer has been reported as prime threat to human health as its existence in more than 200 types so far been reported by the international agency for research on cancer (IARC) who has estimated 14.1 million new cancer cases in the year 2012 and by now approximately 8.2 million deaths been reported due to cancer across world while major types of cancer incidence and mortality cases across UK is listed in (Table 1.3) (Ferlay et al, 2013).

Table 1.3: Estimated age-standardised (ASR) per 100,000 in population of cancer incidence and mortality across UK. It is adapted from Ferlay et al., 2008.

Name	ICD-10 code	ASR cancer incidence by sex		Cancer mortality by sex ASR	
		Female	Male	Female	Male
Oesophagus	C15	2.7	8.1	2.4	7.1
Stomach	C16	4.2	8.6	2.8	5.7
Colon rectum	C18-21	24.6	36	9.7	14.5
Liver	C22	1.6	3.8	1.7	3.7
Lung	C33-34	21.9	39.3	18.8	32.2
Breast	C50	84.0	-	17.8	-
Cervix	C53	8.3	-	2.4	-
Prostate	C61	-	86.4	-	15.7
All sites	C00-97/C44	249.4	303.5	99.7	134.6

1.5 Breast cancer

Breast cancer is the second most common cancer in the world, and it is rated as the most frequent cancer among women with 1.67 million new cancer cases diagnosed in 2012 making 25% of all cancer cases (*GLOBOCAN 2012, IARC*).

1.5.1 Role of oestrogen in breast Cancer

Most of the reported breast cancer cases have been classified as hormone-dependent; therefore, the tumour cells have been shown to be dependent upon the presence of oestrogen for their growth/proliferation (*Santen et al, 1978*). Indeed, *Beatson (1896)* demonstrated the relationship between the ovaries and breast cancer when he treated a locally recurrent breast cancer patient using bilateral oophorectomy. Thus, he could clearly establish a link between oestrogen and

breast cancer development. To date, exposure to exogenous and endogenous oestrogen is considered a well-established cause of breast cancer (reviewed by Hankinson et al, 2004). Epidemiological, clinical and animal studies implicate major role by level of oestrogen in the etiology and onset of breast, prostate, ovarian, lung and endometrial cancer (Henderson & Feigelson, 2000). The concentrations of E1 and E2 have also been found to be at least ten times higher than usual in breast cancer cases (Bonney et al, 1983; Van Landeghem et al, 1985). Recent studies have demonstrated that oestrogen are locally produced from circulating inactive steroids in the breast carcinomas by STS and AR. It has been shown that oestrogen are locally produced from circulating inactive steroids in the breast carcinomas by STS and AR (Suzuki et al, 2002; Suzuki et al, 2005).

Figure 1.8: Scheme representing in-situ production of oestrogen in the breast carcinoma tissue STS; steroid sulfatase, EST; oestrogen sulfotransferase, 17HSD1; 17-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 1, and ER; oestrogen receptor (Figure is adapted from Suzuki et al, 2002).

STS mainly catalyses oestrone sulphate to E1 in breast carcinoma (Fig. 1.8), which immensely contributes to the intra-tumoral oestrogen production. Gene quantification data has shown that the 'sulfatase pathway', which transforms oestrogen sulphates into the bioactive unconjugated E2, is 100-500 times higher

than the 'aromatase pathway' in which androgen is converted into oestrogen by enzyme AR (*Pasqualini, 2004*) which is supported by yet another finding that tissue concentration of oestrone sulphate is higher in tumour tissue than in normal breast tissues (*Chetrite et al, 2000*).

1.5.2 Role of oestrogen receptors in breast cancer

Oestrogen and its targeted receptors play a very crucial role in the development, progression and prognosis of breast cancer (*Leygue et al, 1999*). ER α overexpression is found in 70% of the breast cancer. Consequently, this leads to increased proliferation of mammary cells with increased cell division and replication, in turn leading to mutation (*Henderson et al, 1988*).

ER α expression and breast cancer biology is shown to have a high level of correlation, with the breast carcinomas lacking ER α expression often showing more aggressive phenotypes seen during endocrine treatment as ER α expression acts good prognostic marker in tumour tissues with initial overexpression marked as an indicative event in breast cancer genesis (*Hayashi et al, 2003*).

ER β is prone to be expressed in ER α positive breast cancers and immunohistochemically staining studies have shown the presence of co-expressing human breast cancer cells (*Leygue et al, 1999*). ER β expression is usually higher than that of ER α in the breast cancer cells, but much lower when compared to healthy tissue. ER β subtypes can only trans activates transcription if formed dimer within ER β 1, but when it forms dimer with ER β 2/cx receptors, ligand binding significantly reduces also that receptor-ligand complex's ability to bind ERE on DNA is decreased hence ER β 1 when forms a dimer with ER β 2 it inhibits to bind to ERE (*Iwase et al, 2003*). ER β 1 and ER β 2/cx specifically suppress the function of ER α , particularly proliferation, through various pathways and thus changes in the ER α : ER β ratio may lead to the progression and development of tumour in the process of tumorigenesis (*Leygue et al, 1999*). ER β has also been shown to be expressed in various cancers including breast cancer (*Omoto et al, 2002*). Transfected hormone dependent breast cancer MCF7 cell lines

constitutively expressing ER β and ER β 2 showed reduced colony formation, cell cycle and growth in anchorage-independent situation with diminished ERE activity and weak response of ER α target genes (e.g. cathepsin D) (*Augereau et al, 1994; Hayashi et al, 2003*).

1.5.3 Breast Cancer and inflammation

Inflammation is seen in breast cancer which includes involvement of inflammatory mediators. Among these, chemokine belong to superfamily of small (17 kDa-30 kDa), cytokine chemo-attractant signalling proteins that induce leukocyte trafficking, through interaction with their cognate G-protein coupled receptors making contribution to a diverse range of physiological and pathological processes including cytoskeletal rearrangement, firm adhesion to endothelial cells and in its directional migration, inflammation, embryogenesis, immune system development, tumorigenesis and cancer metastasis (*Morales et al, 1999; Rossi & Zlotnik,2000; Gerard & Rollins,2001; Gale & McColl,1999*). Chemokines are secretory proteins which have highly conserved secondary structure conferred by their characteristic tetra cysteine motif, the configuration of which forms the basis for their systemic nomenclature while these are subdivided into four group's bases on the arrangement of conserved cysteine shown in *Figure 1.9 (Martins-Green et al, 2013)*. To date 50 human chemokines have been described, many of which binds to several of the 24 described human chemokines receptors (*Kiefer & Siekmann, 2011*).

Figure 1.9 Diagram showing the main four Chemokine superfamily the C family (A), in which one of the first two cysteine is missing, the CC family (B), in which the first two cysteine are adjacent, the CXC family (C), in which the first two cysteine are separated by any single amino acid, and the CX3C family (D), in which the first two cysteine are separated by three amino acids. (Figure is adapted from Martins-Green et al, 2013).

1.5.4 Role of Chemokines in breast cancer

Neoplastic cells are known to either produce chemotactic factors or induce expression in nearby host cells. In a review it has been mentioned that there is a major role of chemokines during malignancy proved in an experimental animals' knockout mice models for natural killer cells which had shown immune response (Mantovani et al, 2010).

Melanoma cancer (skin cancer), in which chemokines (for example, CXCL1, CXCL2, CXCL3 and CXCL8) have been shown exert autocrine controlled cell proliferation while blocking CXCR2 receptor has attenuated melanoma cell proliferation in-vitro (Richmond & Thomas, 1986; Norgauer et al, 1996).

CXCR2 ligands have been identified as having autocrine role in the growth of pancreatic, head and neck and non-small cell lung carcinoma (*Vicari & Farrow, 2002*) while in animal model CXCR5 variably affects tumour vascularity and apoptosis (*Aregberg et al, 1998*).

There is involvement of chemokines receptors in breast cancer metastasis to lymph nodes, bone marrow, lung and liver as studies using mouse model by Muller and colleagues suggested in year 2001 that pattern of breast cancer metastasis is in part governed by specific interaction between CXCR4 and its ligand SDF-1/CXCL12. CXCR4 and CCR7 are highly expressed in human breast cancer cell lines, malignant breast tumours and metastatic foci while ligand for these receptors in organs to which tumour metastasize (*Muller, 2001*). CXCL12 triggers chemotaxis of malignant mammary carcinoma cells in vitro and the chemotactic activity of extracts organs target by breast cancer cells can be neutralized by anti-CXCR4 antibody (*Moore, 2001*).

Human mammary tumour cell line MCF-7 cells are known to produce a large quantity of CCL2 (MCP-1) in response to interleukin-1a (IL-1a) while addition of E2 to MCF-7 cells inhibited CCL2 production in a dose-dependent manner (*Inadera et al, 2000*). TGF- β 1 upregulates CXCR4 expression on dendritic cells, eosinophils, T cells, macrophages and melanoma cells (*Zoetewei et al, 1998; Sato et al, 2000; Nagase et al, 2000; Javelaud et al, 2007*). Previously a study was done to investigate the effect of TGF- β 1 on breast cancer cells, the human breast cancer cell line MCF-7 was treated with rh-TGF- β 1 at concentrations of 0 (control), 1, 10, 100 ng/mL for 48 h then total RNA was isolated for real-time PCR analysis of CXCR4 mRNA expression. TGF- β 1 treatment, as showed in a significant increase in CXCR4 mRNA expression in MCF-7 cells (*Zhao et al, 2010*). The breast carcinoma cells can respond to chemokines, and suggests a potential role for these molecules in the process of tumour cell migration, invasion and metastasis as shown in for MCF-7 breast cancer cell line that CCL3 (MIP-1a), CCL4 (MIP-1b) and CCL5 (RANTES) were the most potent inducers of cell migration, while

CCL2 (MCP-1) and many of the chemokines elicited a significant but lower chemotactic response (*Youngs et al, 1997*).

1.5.5 Oestrogen action on ERs and Inflammatory receptors

ER α expression is found in two-thirds of breast cancer while breast cancer is closely regulated by oestrogen. ER β is expressed at a lower level than ER α but it is found to have a negative role in breast cancer progression (*Huang et al, 2014*). Interestingly many chemokines (e.g. CCL2, CCL3, CXCL8, and CXCL12) and chemokine receptors (CCR2 or CXCR3) have shown expression dependent of oestrogen receptors. Such as CXCL12 is regulated by oestrogen in breast cancer cells while CXCL12 antibody can abrogate E2-induced proliferation of breast cancer while mechanism behind this action remains unclear (*Ali & Lazennec, 2007*).

The chemokine signalling system consists of chemokine ligands and transmembrane receptors that coordinate leukocyte trafficking in human immune system. Chemokine receptors are differentially expressed by all leukocytes and many non-hematopoietic cells including cancer cells. It is broadly divided into two types: G protein-coupled chemokine receptors activating G protein and atypical chemokine receptors (AKCRs). AKCRs are transmembrane proteins which dampen inflammation by scavenging chemokines but in a G protein independent & β -arrestin-dependent manner (*Bachelier et al, 2014*). AKCRs are a subfamily of apparently non- (or atypically-) signalling chemokine receptors scavenging chemokines and known to mediate cell migration while much work remains to be done to find specific function of AKCR. DARC (ACKR1) and D6 (ACKR2) are two sub-types of AKCRs that play a role in regulation of anti-inflammation at the site of infection by scavenging, transportation or buffering secreted inflammatory chemokines.

1.5.6 Relation between oestrogen and inflammatory mediators

ACKR2 (D6) is massively expressed by placental trophoblast cells which are known to synthesise oestrogen during foetal development (*Toeh et al, 2014*). Like ER β , higher ACKR2 expression in human breast cancer is correlated to disease

free survival rate in cancer patient (*Wu et al, 2008*). Also, ACKR1 (DARC) is silent chemokine receptor like ACKR2 that has shown as negative regulator of growth in breast cancer mainly by sequestering angiogenic chemokines and inhibiting tumour neo-vascularity (*Wang et al, 2006*). ACKR3 has been identified as potential modulator of endocrine resistance in ER α positive breast cancer studies (*Ribas et al, 2014*).

1.5.7 The emerging role of AKCR(s) in cancer

ACKR plays essential roles in the context of resolving inflammatory responses that has been proved using various animal models for study. Also, it is now established fact that ACKR2 and ACKR3 play a role in cancer disease. The role of ACKR1 is studied in models of acute or chronic inflammation in wild type and ACKR1 KO mice while the lack of the receptor has resulted in reduced neutrophil recruitment to the lung after intra-tracheal administration of CXCL8 (*Lee et al., 2003*). Hence these studies have established that endothelial ACKR1 promotes acute and chronic inflammation by reducing chemokine concentrations in the inflamed tissues and creating a gradient that increases neutrophil and monocyte extravasation. A key role for ACKR2 in regulating the promotion of inflammation-dependent cancers has now been shown using mouse models of cutaneous and colorectal cancer (*Nibbs et al, 2007; Vetrano et al, 2007*). Also, in-vitro studies on cell lines have shown expression of ACKR 2 in breast cancer while ACKR2 functions essentially act as tumour suppressor gene by limiting tumour-promoting tissue inflammatory responses (*Wu et al, 2009*). A study using zebrafish embryos have demonstrated important and evolutionary conserved roles for ACKR3 in the regulation of key cellular populations during embryogenesis that have shed important light on the importance of ACKR3 for the generation of tissue gradients during cellular migration within the embryo (*Streichan et al., 2011*). ACKR3 KO mice has been seen with defects in brain, heart, and kidney development also that ACKR3 is also prominently expressed in a wide range of tumours both within the tumour cells and by cells of the tumour vasculature (*Maksym et al., 2009*). It has therefore been highlighted as a potential therapeutic target in oncology. ACKR4 is

expressed by keratinocytes and a subset of lymphatic endothelial cells in mouse skin and that it can mediate chemokine scavenging by these cells ACKR4 in KO mice, has been demonstrated as homeostatic chemokine clearance is necessary to control excessive Th17 responses that can lead to immune-pathologies (Comeford et al, 2018).

1.6 Study models for cancer MCF-7 line: Hormone dependent Breast cancer cell line

MCF-7 is commonly used breast cancer cell line, that has been promoted for more than 40 years by multiple research groups hence it has been highly characterized in terms of molecular profile, proliferation, migration, invasion, spheroid formation, its involvement in angiogenesis and lymph angiogenesis and its interaction with the mesenchymal stem cells (Comsa et al,2015).

MCF-7 cell line has been considered as excellent in-vitro study model for mechanism of tumour response to endocrine therapy as well as for understanding the complex relationship between binding and biological action triggered via hormones (Levenson & Jordan, 1994). MCF-7 breast cancer cell line had been developed about 45 years ago at Michigan cancer foundation centre, Karmanos Cancer Institute Wayne State University, by late Dr Herbert Soule. He had derived these cells from pleural effusion with 7 years to mastectomy to benign tumour in right breast of 69 years old female patient with metastatic breast cancer, hence MCF-7 cell line has been named on the institute where it was developed i.e. Michigan cancer foundation and duration of derive metastatic cells from pleural effusion after seven years to benign mastectomy. MCF-7 is suitable model cell line for breast cancer investigations worldwide including screening anticancer drugs and molecular understanding of signalling pathways involved in onset of disease physiology (Sweeney et al, 2013). It is oestrogen receptor ER (+) positive and progesterone receptor PR (+) positive while interestingly the ER (-), PR (-) and HER2 (-) negative (triple negative) sub lines seems to have the origin in the ER (+) positive MCF-7 cell line (Shirazi, 2011; Leung et al, 2014). MCF-7 belongs to the luminal A molecular subtype of breast cancer cell line with higher level of ER

while it is poorly-aggressive and non-invasive cell line with low metastatic potential (Done,2011; Gest et al, 2013). With respect to inflammatory mediator gene expression there are work that has shown presence of ACKR in MCF-7 cell line in various studies (Wang et al, 2006; Wu et al,2008; Ribas et al, 2014).

1.7 Basis of investigation of this study

1.7.1 Introduction to study plan

Several experimental studies have established that culturing MCF-7 cells with E2 induces mitogenic effects & morphological changes via a change in gene expression of ER despite the receptor localization in the cell (reviewed by Zidavinovic et al, 2005). Also, stromal factors i.e. the growth factors released from the stromal cells around the mammary epithelial cells have been implicated in the regulation of cell behaviour but its influence on human breast cancer needs to be explored well (Horgan et al,1987). Many inflammatory mediators, importantly the chemokine receptors are a factor in stromal surrounding breast tumour and these are considered to drive the cancer progression. As evident from studies that the breast cancer cells have gene expression for various inflammatory receptors hence it gets essential to look E2 could change gene expression level in these inflammatory mediators along with the ER which has been consistently addressed with the prognosis of breast cancer in research. Previous studies have looked at gene expression of ER types on MCF-7 with changing E2 levels. In most of these studies, it has been concluded that ER α gene expression changes when exposed to E2 in MCF-7 cells in-vitro or in-vivo (Frasor & Gibori, 2003). So far studies have been achieved to find modulation of chemokine receptor with E2 and chemokines as potential modulator in ER+ breast cancer but not much work is being performed to examine the role of E2 in gene expression modulation of anti-inflammatory mediators such as ACKR2 that are known to play negative role in cancer progression (Ali & Lazennec, 2007).

Chapter 2

Research

Methodology

2.0 Research Methodology

2.1 Aim & Objectives

Aim

Investigating the effect of higher oestradiol (E2) levels on oestrogen receptors (ERs) & atypical chemokine receptor (ACKRs) gene expression in MCF-7 breast cancer cells

Background

Oestradiol (E2) is a critical hormone known to influence gene expression in breast cancer cells. This study aims to explore how elevated E2 levels affect the mRNA expression of ACKRs and oestrogen receptors (ERs) in MCF-7 breast cancer cells grown in vitro (laboratory setting).

Hypothesis

Based on prior research, it is hypothesized that higher E2 concentrations will modulate the gene expression of ACKRs in MCF-7 cells.

Research Questions

1. **Model and technical approach:** To investigate this hypothesis, MCF-7 cell line will be utilised and employ quantitative real-time PCR (RT-qPCR) to measure mRNA expression levels.

2. **Endogenous Control Selection:** Before analyzing ACKR expression, it is to determine the most reliable reference gene (endogenous control) for accurate data normalisation in MCF-7 cells.
3. **E2 Concentration Effects:** To assess how varying E2 concentrations impact MCF-7 cell viability in culture.
4. **E2 and ERs Expression:** To investigate whether E2 exposure alters the expression of both ER subtypes (ER α and ER β) in MCF-7 cells.
5. **E2 and ACKRs Expression:** The core question: Does E2 treatment modulate the expression of specific ACKRs in MCF-7 cells?

2.2 Materials

- **Cell Line:** MCF-7 cells were purchased from ATCC-LGC Standards (UK).
- **Cell Culture Reagents:**
 - Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium: Nutrient Mixture F12 (DMEM:F12) without
 - Dulbecco's Phosphate-Buffered Saline (DPBS) without calcium and magnesium
 - Standard Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS)
 - TrypLE Express Enzyme (1X)
 - Gibco's Antibiotic-Antimycotic (100X) solution were obtained from Life Technologies (Paisley, UK).
- **Cell Culture Plastics:**
 - 6-well plates
 - T-75 cm² tissue culture flasks
 - 96-well qPCR plates

- Filtered tips
- 1.5 mL centrifuge tubes

These were obtained from a combination of Fischer Scientific (UK) and Star Labs (UK).

- **Molecular Grade Chemicals:**

- Ethanol
- Chloroform
- Isopropanol

These chemicals were obtained from Fischer Scientific (UK).

- **RNA Isolation and cDNA Synthesis:**

- Ribozol (AMERESCO, US)
- Agarose powder
- Ethidium bromide
- DNase-free kit
- High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kits.
- RNA inhibitor (Applied Biosystems)

These were purchased from VRW Life Science (UK).

- **PCR and Real-Time PCR:**

- VWR Red Taq Polymerase Master Mix

- qScript™ One-Step SYBR® Green qRT-PCR Kit with ROX (Applied Biosystems)
These were purchased from VRW Life Science (UK).

- **Cell Culture Environment:**

- Biosafety cabinet (Class II)
- New Brunswick Galaxy 170R CO₂ incubator (5% CO₂, 37°C) for culturing MCF-7 cells
- Bright-light microscope for cell observation
- MSE Mistral 1000 centrifuge for cell pelleting

- **Analysis Equipment:**

- NanoDrop ND-100 spectrophotometer with ND100 software for RNA quantification
- Bio-Rad PCR thermocycler for conventional PCR
- Agilent Stratagene Mx3005P qPCR system for real-time PCR with associated software
- Bio-Rad gel electrophoresis unit and imaging system for PCR product analysis
- Applied Biosystems StepOne Plus real-time PCR instrument with software for gene expression analysis

- **Primers:**

- Primers were obtained from Invitrogen as desalted dry-oligos (25 nM conc.).

- **Other Reagents:**

- Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and E2 (Sigma-Aldrich, Dorset, UK)

- **ELISA Plate Reader:**

- BioTek Synergy HT Microplate Reader for measuring sample optical densities

Chapter 3

RT-qPCR

Assay development

3. Relative gene expression using RT-qPCR

3.1 Introduction

Several decades of research on breast cancer disease has shown that exposure to oestrogen is a strong factor in the etiology behind breast cancer progression. Numerous evidence-based research, including epidemiological and clinical investigations, have demonstrated a link between extended exposure to oestrogen and the risk of breast cancer (*Pike et al, 1993; Kelsey et al, 1993; Berstein & Ross, 1993; Henderson et al, 1988*). A form of oestrogen, as E₂, plays a crucial role in the advancement of breast cancer because it mediates its effect binding to one of the physically and functionally different ERs i.e. ER α and ER β . Up to 80% of breast tumours express ER α , the classical ER, which serves as a marker for the use of anti-hormonal therapy in the treatment of breast cancer (*Osborne, 1998*). Since it has been used for more than 40 years in breast cancer research, the MCF-7 cell line has been characterized for the presence of disease-prognostic receptors such as oestrogen receptor positive (ER+), progesterone receptor positive (PgR+), overexpression of the cell-proliferative Ki-67 protein, and negative for HER2. These results are the result of clinical and molecular investigations and MCF-7 is nearly 'Luminal A' subtype of breast cancer (*Subik et al, 2010*).

The first method used to measure ER in breast cancer tissue biopsies was ligand binding assays (LBA), which could be used to gauge the amount of ER (*Osborne, 1998*). However, one drawback of this experimental strategy is that it is unable to show the relative concentrations of the two distinct ER forms, ER α and ER β . In

breast cancer, there are several splice variants of ER α and ER β . The MCF-7 cell line exhibits both ER α and ER β , together with any potential splice variations for each (Huang B et al, 2014). Although the precise roles that each of these variations plays in the development of breast cancer are still unknown.

The ER types in breast cancer tissue samples have been characterized using the Immunohistochemistry Assay (IHC). This staining methodology demonstrated variability in the sensitivity and specificity for the use of ER β antibodies, which added to the uncertainty around its molecular action and tissue expression. However, it was still possible to detect ER α with high specificity when evaluating for ER β (Choi et al, 2001, Hartman et al, 2012, Skliris et. al., 2002, Weitsman et al, 2006; Wu et al, 2012).

It has been determined that using IHC to characterize ER β is challenging, and not everyone agrees that its expression in widely used cell line models is normal (Al-Bader et al, 2011; Gruvberger-Saal et al., 2007; Guo et al., 2014(a); Guo et al., 2014(b); Hieken et al., 2015; Omoto et al., 2002; Shaaban et al., 2003; Skliris et al., 2002, Umekita et al., 2006).

Compared to IHC, RT-qPCR has demonstrated a wider dynamic range and greater sensitivity. RT-qPCR is becoming a more potent method due to its high-throughput, sensitivity, and reproducibility for assessing variations in gene

expression and quantifying transcript abundance (*Sinn et al., 2017; Ginzinger, 2002*).

In this chapter RT-qPCR technique based assay is developed to to determine the relative gene expression for the target gene ERs in MCF-7. The measurement of gene expression in research is done at the mRNA (transcriptional level) with RT-qPCR, as highly sensitive and flexible methodology. Its high throughput, low cost, and less time to process the samples makes it a valuable tool for determining the target gene expression level for basic research use(*Gracia-Vallejo et al., 2003*).

The preferred technique for quantifying mRNA—often referred to as the "gold" standard—is RT-qPCR, but it necessitates a high level of test step uniformity. Despite being the most used approach for quantifying mRNA, it is not regarded as a standard assay (*Nolan et al., 2006*).

RT-qPCR can be roughly split into three stages:

- 1) The conversion of RNA to cDNA, is dependent on reverse transcriptase (RT).
- 2) PCR amplification of cDNA
- 3) Amplification product detection and quantification (*Gibson et al., 1996*)

Figure 3.1 Flowchart showing steps in RT-qPCR experimental workflow. Triangular shapes in blue are control steps that will keep check on samples quality.

Quantitative data that is more dependable and repeatable may be produced if quality control is upheld throughout the protocol by using a standard operating procedure (Nolan et al., 2006). Following the Minimum Information for Publication of Quantitative Real-Time PCR Experiments (MIQE) guidelines has helped researchers increase experimental transparency and has promoted consistency between laboratories. The MIQE guidelines are a standard that is followed to target the reliability of results to ensure the integrity of the scientific literature (Bustin et al., 2009). Thus, for the RT-qPCR experiments conducted in this chapter, the MIQE requirements have been adhered to.

This experimental chapter's goal is to identify ER isoforms by relative gene expression in order to accomplish a number of goals that were established as follows:

- RNA optimization for MCF-7 cell gene expression analysis
- Characterizing oestrogen receptors gene in MCF-7 using PCR
- Selection of normalization gene for RT-qPCR
- Relative gene expression of ERs types over time in culture

Using the primers for ER β 1 and ER β 2/cx, it has been examined as how these genes' gene expression is affected by E2, following the guidelines provided by the literature study and the foundation of this investigation. To recap, not much progress has been made in determining the significance of various ER β gene variations in breast cancer, thus this chapter focusses to develop a method to

measure the target gene's gene expression levels. Taking into account the available primers for ER β 1 and ER β 2/cx based on similar study, as well as splice variants of the ER β gene (Green et al., 2009), later in the chapter these primers led to produced non-specific gene amplification but certainly not suitable for RT-qPCR study. So a novel primer design strategy has been used to get the overall ER β gene expression despite looking at a specific variant form.

3.2 Method

3.2.1 MCF-7 Cell Culture

a) Media Preparation:

Complete growth medium for MCF-7 cells consisted of Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium: Nutrient Mixture F12 (DMEM:F12) without phenol red, 10% (v/v) heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS), 1% (v/v) antibiotic-antimycotic solution containing 10,000 units/mL penicillin, 10,000 μ g/mL streptomycin, and 25 μ g/mL Amphotericin B. Fetal bovine serum (FBS) was heat-inactivated by incubating in a water bath at 55°C for 30 minutes. The complete medium was stored at 4°C in the refrigerator.

b) Cell Thawing and Seeding:

MCF-7 cells were obtained cryopreserved in a cryo-vial from ATCC-LGC Standards (UK). Upon arrival, the cryo-vial was thawed at 37°C in a water bath. 5 mL of fresh complete medium was added to the thawed cells and transferred to 15

mL centrifuge tube using a sterile pipette. The cell suspension was centrifuged at 1200 x g for 5 minutes using the MSE Mistral 1000 centrifuge to pellet the cells. After centrifugation, the supernatant was discarded, and the cell pellet was re-suspended in 5 mL of fresh complete medium. The re-suspended cells were transferred to a sterile T-75 cm² tissue culture flask containing an additional 15 mL of freshly prepared complete medium.

c) Cell Maintenance:

The flask was incubated at 37°C in a humidified incubator with 5% CO₂. Fresh complete medium was replaced every two days. Cells were monitored daily for confluence and signs of contamination under a bright-light microscope. A cell confluence of over 70% was typically achieved in the initial flask in a weeks' time since thawing the cells.

3.2.2 Sub-culturing and Cryopreservation of MCF-7 Cells

a) Sub-culturing:

i) Cell Detachment and Harvest: When the MCF-7 cells in the T-75 cm² flask reached 70% confluence, the medium was aspirated. The cells were washed with 3 mL of Dulbecco's Phosphate-Buffered Saline (DPBS) without calcium and magnesium. DPBS used or wash was aspirated, and 3 mL of TrypLE Express (1X) was added to detach the cells from the flask surface. Detachment was monitored under a light microscope.

ii) Cell Collection and Seeding: Once detached, 5 mL of fresh complete medium was added to the flask, and the cell suspension was gently mixed. This suspension was centrifuged at 1200 x g for 5 minutes in a 15 mL centrifuge tube. After centrifugation, the supernatant was discarded, and the cell pellet was re-suspended in 3 mL of fresh complete DMEM: F12 medium.

iii) Cell Splitting: 1:3 split ratio was used from the re-suspended cells, 1 mL aliquots were added to three new T-75 cm² flasks, each containing 19 mL of fresh complete medium.

iv) Incubation and Maintenance: The three flasks were incubated at 37°C in a humidified incubator with 5% CO₂. The medium was replaced every two days, and cell growth and confluence were monitored daily under a light microscope. Typically, cells reached over 70% confluence on the fifth day of sub-culturing.

b) Cryopreservation:

i) Cell Counting and Viability Assessment: One flask out of the three used for sub-culturing was used for cryopreservation. After harvesting the cells, a hemocytometer was used to determine cell concentration and viability. Briefly, 10 µL of a 1:1 mixture of cell suspension (100 µL) and trypan blue dye (100 µL) was loaded onto the hemocytometer and counted under a light microscope. Trypan blue stains dead cells but not live cells.

ii) Viability Calculation: The percentage of viable cells was calculated using the following equation:

% Viability = (Number of unstained cells / Total number of cells counted) x 100
.....(Equation 1)

c) Cryo-suspension Preparation: The cell pellet was gently re-suspended in the required volume of cryopreservation medium to achieve a final concentration of 1×10^6 cells/mL.

d) Cryo-vial Storage: The cell suspension was aliquot into 2mL cry vials, labeled with the passage number and date, and stored in liquid nitrogen for long-term preservation. Other two sub-culture flask was used for preparing the sample for use in the experimental design.

3.2.3 RT-qPCR assay development

3.2.3.1 Cell densities & time points in culture

Two flasks from the 1:3 sub-cultured MCF-7 cells were used for this experiment. Cells were counted using a hemocytometer. Different cell density e.g. 2.5×10^5 , 5×10^5 , 7.5×10^5 , 1×10^6 , and 2.5×10^6 cells/mL were seeded into each 6-well plate separately in triplicate set (n=3) for four time points 6 hours (H), 12H, 24H & 48H. Each well received 1 mL of complete medium for a final volume of 2 mL.

Rationale being that this experiment will set the stage to determine the optimal cell number and incubation time for isolating sufficient RNA ($\geq 1 \mu\text{g}$) for gene expression analysis using RT-qPCR. Seeding various cell densities allows us to

identify the minimum number of cells required to yield enough RNA for planning experimental design for qPCR assay.

The four 6-well plates, each containing cells at different densities, were incubated at 37°C, 5% CO₂, and humidified conditions for four time points: 6 hours (h), 12 h, 24 h, and 48 h. Triplicate biological repeats as Run 1 (R1), Run 2 (R2), and Run 3 (R3) were set as well. For observational purposes, only bright-light microscope images of MCF-7 cells from wells at different densities and time points in replicate R1 were captured using an Olympus manual camera. Studying different time points allows us to monitor MCF-7 cell adherence to the culture plates, cellular health in the media selection, and use of these sample in qPCR assay development & investigate potential changes in ER gene expression over time in culture.

3.2.3.2 Total RNA Extraction using Ribozol

This section describes the isolation of total RNA from above cell densities & time point experimental design including biological repeat using the Ribozol method.

a) Cell Lysis: At designated time points, the culture medium was aspirated from each well of the 6-well plates containing different cell numbers. The wells were washed once with 1 mL of DPBS (without Mg⁺²/Cl⁻) to remove residual media components. 1 mL of Ribozol reagent was added directly to each well and mixed vigorously by pipetting to lyse the cells. The lysates were transferred to labeled 1.5 mL micro-centrifuge tubes according to cell number and time point.

b) Phase Separation: The tubes were incubated at room temperature (25°C) for 10 minutes to allow complete cell lysis. 200 µL of chloroform was added to each tube, followed by vigorous shaking for 60 seconds. After shaking, the tubes were incubated for an additional 2 minutes at room temperature. Centrifugation was performed at 14,000 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C to separate the mixture into three phases: An organic lower phase containing cellular debris; A middle interphase; & A colorless upper aqueous phase containing RNA.

c) RNA Precipitation: The upper aqueous phase (~500 µL) was carefully transferred to a fresh 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tube. An equal volume (~500 µL) of isopropanol was added to each tube, and the mixture was incubated for 10 minutes at room temperature to precipitate the RNA. The tubes were centrifuged again at 12,000 x g for 10 minutes at 4°C. The supernatant was carefully discarded, and the RNA pellet was visualized at the bottom of each tube as a white pellet.

d) RNA Wash and Re-suspension: Each RNA pellet was washed with 1 mL of 75% ethanol (v/v) by pipetting to remove residual contaminants. The tubes were centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 10 minutes at 4°C. The supernatant was carefully discarded, and the RNA pellets were allowed to air-dry for 10 minutes with the lids open to remove residual ethanol.

e) RNA Elution and Storage: 21 µL of nuclease-free water was added to each tube to re-suspend the RNA pellets. The tubes were capped and incubated in a water bath at 55°C for 10 minutes to dissolve the RNA. The extracted total RNA samples were stored at -80°C for future use.

3.2.3.3 RNA Quantification and Integrity Assessment

a) RNA Quantification: The NanoDrop ND-100 spectrophotometer was used to quantify the total RNA concentration in each sample. One microliter (μL) of RNA sample was loaded onto the instrument's detector to measure absorbance at 260 nm. The absorbance value at 260 nm is used to estimate RNA quantity.

b) RNA Integrity Check: To assess RNA integrity, 1 μg of total RNA from each sample was electrophoresed on a 1.2% agarose gel stained with ethidium bromide (EtBr).

c) Gel Preparation:

i) TBE Buffer:

A 5X TBE stock solution was prepared by dissolving 54 g of TRIS base, 27.5 g of boric acid, and 3.725 g of EDTA disodium salt (EDTA) in 800 mL of deionized water (ddH_2O). The final volume was adjusted to 1 L with ddH_2O . A 1X working TBE buffer was prepared by diluting 200 mL of 5X TBE stock solution with 800 mL of ddH_2O to obtain a final volume of 1 L.

ii) Agarose Gel:

2.25 g of ultrapure agarose was weighed and added to a 250 mL conical flask. 150 mL of 1X TBE buffer was added to the flask, and the mixture was heated in a

microwave for 3 minutes to dissolve the agarose completely. The flask was allowed to cool down to approximately 45°C. One microliter (µL) of EtBr solution was added to the cooled agarose solution, and the flask was gently swirled to ensure even mixing. The molten agarose solution was poured into a gel casting tray and allowed to solidify for 30 minutes.

d) Electrophoresis:

After gel solidification, 1 µg of RNA sample mixed with loading buffer was loaded into each well of the gel, along with a 1 kb DNA ladder as a size marker. The gel was run in an electrophoresis unit to separate the RNA molecules based on their size.

e) Visualization:

The RNA integrity was evaluated by visualizing the gel under a gel imaging system. Ideally, intact RNA should show two distinct bands corresponding to 28S and 18S ribosomal RNA (rRNA).

3.2.3.4 DNase Treatment and Confirmation

a) DNase Treatment:

To eliminate contaminating DNA before cDNA synthesis, RNA samples were treated with DNase I using the DNase-free kit (details provided by the manufacturer). Five microliters (µL) of total RNA from each sample was used for DNase I treatment following the kit instructions given in table 3.1.

Table 3.1 DNA-free kit reagents and amount for one reaction

DNA-free kit reagents	Amount (μL) per reaction
RNA (5 μg) samples	Variable
DNase/RNase free water	Variable
10X DNase Buffer	2.5 μL
DNase I enzyme	1.0 μL
Total volume	25 μL

Briefly, the reaction mixture containing RNA, DNase I enzyme, and reaction buffer was incubated at 37°C for 30 minutes in a Bio-Rad PCR thermocycler. After incubation, DNase I was inactivated by adding DNase I inactivation slurry and incubating the mixture at room temperature for 2 minutes followed by centrifugation at 300 x g for 2 minutes. Twenty-five microliters (μL) of the supernatant from each sample was transferred to a fresh PCR tube labeled appropriately and stored at -80°C.

b) Confirmation of DNA Removal

To confirm the removal of DNA contamination, a PCR amplification targeting the 18S rRNA gene was performed on the DNase-treated RNA samples. Since 18S rRNA is an RNA molecule, amplification in these samples would indicate the presence of contaminating DNA. Positive and negative controls were included in

the PCR reaction: Positive control: BeWo cDNA (a source of 18S rRNA cDNA);
Negative control: Nuclease-free water.

c) PCR Amplification

PCR reactions were prepared using the VWR Red Taq Polymerase Master Mix according to the manufacturer's instructions for a single reaction volume given in table 3.2.

Table 3.2 PCR reagent amount per reaction

Reagents for PCR	Amount (μL) per reaction
Red Taq. polymerase mix (1.5 mM MgCl)	12.5
RNase free water	10.5
18S rRNA Forward Primer	0.5
18S rRNA Reverse Primer	0.5
Template/control	1
Total volume	25

Each reaction contained the following: DNase-treated RNA sample (5 μ L), 18S rRNA primers (forward and reverse), reaction buffer with nucleotides, Taq DNA polymerase enzyme & nuclease-free water (to adjust final volume). All PCR tubes were mixed briefly by centrifugation at 300 x g and then subjected to PCR

amplification in a Bio-Rad thermocycler using a 35-cycle program given in table 3.3.

Table 3.3 Thermocycler PCR cycles programme

Cycles	Duration of cycle	Temperature
1	30 seconds ^a	95°C
35	30 seconds ^b	95 °C
	30 seconds ^{c*}	61 °C
	1 minute ^d	72 °C
1	10 minutes ^e	72 °C
Storage	Infinite	10 °C

Note: a, b, c, d & e stands for hot start, denaturation, annealing, elongation and final elongation respectively. c annealing temperature used for 18S rRNA primers was given in paper from which it has been adopted and same defined temperature was used.*

d) Gel Electrophoresis and Visualization:

One microliter (μL) of each PCR product (including positive and negative controls) was loaded onto a 1.2% agarose gel alongside a 100 bp DNA ladder. The gel was run in an electrophoresis unit to separate DNA fragments based on size. After electrophoresis, the gel was visualized using a gel imaging system. Note: This procedure was performed for all three independent biological replicates (R1, R2, and R3).

3.2.3.5 cDNA Synthesis and PCR Amplification

a) cDNA Synthesis: RNA samples confirmed to be free of DNA contamination were used for cDNA synthesis using a High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription kit. Since the kit lacked an RNA inhibitor, it was purchased separately for this experiment. cDNA synthesis reactions were prepared following the kit's instructions. Briefly, the reaction mixture contained: DNase-treated RNA (0.2 µg); Random hexamer primers; Deoxynucleotide triphosphates (dNTPs); Reaction buffer; Multiscribe reverse transcriptase enzyme; Nuclease-free water (to adjust final volume). In addition to sample reactions, a no-reverse transcriptase control (NTC) was included for each run. The NTC reaction mixture contained all components except for the reverse transcriptase enzyme. This control helps assess the functionality of the cDNA synthesis kit and serves as a negative control in subsequent qPCR experiments. A no-template control (water only) was also considered for each batch of cDNA synthesis reactions.

Table 3.4 Program for cDNA thermal cycling condition

Settings	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4
Temperature	25°C	37°C	85°C	4°C
Time (minute)	10	120	5	∞

All reaction mixtures were pipetted into the Aligent Stratagene SureCycler 8800 machine, and cDNA synthesis was carried out using the thermal cycling program specified in table 3.4.

b) cDNA check with PCR Amplification

To confirm successful cDNA synthesis, a PCR amplification targeting the 18S rRNA gene was performed on the cDNA samples. The PCR reactions were prepared using the same primers used for the DNA contamination check (18S rRNA forward and reverse primers). Positive and negative controls were included: Positive control: BeWo cDNA & Negative control: Nuclease-free water PCR reactions were prepared following the same protocol used for the DNA contamination check (refer to Section 3.2.3.4 for details). Briefly, the reactions contained: cDNA sample; 18S rRNA primers; PCR master mix (including Taq DNA polymerase); Nuclease-free water (to adjust final volume). The PCR reactions were run in a thermocycler using the same cycling program as described in section 3.2.3.4 (refer to table 3.3).

c) Gel Electrophoresis and Visualization:

One microliter (μL) of each PCR product (including controls) was loaded onto a 1.2% agarose gel with a 100 bp DNA ladder. The gel was run in an electrophoresis unit to separate DNA fragments by size. After electrophoresis, the gel was visualized using a gel imaging system.

3.2.3.6 Selection of Reference Gene for qPCR

a) Importance & characterization of housekeeping genes (HKGs)

In real-time PCR (qPCR), selecting a reliable reference gene is crucial to normalize target gene expression data. Housekeeping genes are stably expressed genes essential for cellular functions and are often used for normalization. Common housekeeping genes include ribosomal RNAs (rRNA) and genes like HPRT1, TBP, and HKG. This study aimed to identify the most suitable reference gene for qPCR analysis in MCF-7 cells, including a novel candidate, TOP1 details given in table 3.5.

Gradient PCR (gPCR) was performed to optimise the annealing temperature for each primer set specific to the chosen reference genes (HKGs) on a test sample. The SureCycler instrument was programmed to run the gPCR across a temperature range of 55-65°C. After gPCR, the samples were loaded onto a 1.2% agarose gel, and the amplified products were visualized using a gel imaging system to determine the optimal annealing temperature for each primer pair.

b) qPCR Procedure Details

qScript™ One-Step SYBR® Green q-PCR Kit with ROX was used for all qPCR reactions. The kit includes reagents for both cDNA synthesis and qPCR amplification. Each qPCR run included: cDNA samples from various cell densities and time points in culture (unstimulated samples); Negative controls: nuclease-free water and no-reverse transcriptase control (NTC).

Table 3.5 Details of HKG primers along with references.

Gene	Forward Primers	Reverse Primers	Nucleotide Sequence No.	Product size (bp)	References
18S rRNA	5'-CAA CTT TCG ATG GTA GTC G-3'	5'-CTT TCC TTG GAT-GTG GTA-3'	K03432	110	Green et al,2009
HPRT1	5'-TGA CAC TGG CAA AAC AATGCA-3'	5'-GGT CCT TTT CAC-CAG CAA GCT-3'	NM_000194	94	Aithal & Rajeswari, 2015
TOP1	5'-GAC GAA TCA TGC CCG AGG AT-3'	5'-CAG TGT CCG CTG-TTT CTC CT-3'	NM_003286.2	381	Design in-house for study
TBP	5'-TTC GGA GAG TTC TGG GAT TGT A-3'	5'-TGG ACT GTT CTT-CACTCT TGG C-3'	NM_00117208 5.1	227	Maltseva et al, 2013

Each sample from the three experimental replicates (R1, R2, and R3) was run in duplicate (n=2) on a 96-well qPCR plate. An adhesive cover was used to seal the plate before running it on the StepOne system instrument of 'Applied Bio-systems'. qPCR data was collected and analyzed using the instrument's Quant Studio software software.

c) Selection process of the most stable HKG

Following qPCR optimization, all reference genes were used in separate qPCR runs with the test samples. The mean Cq (cycle threshold) value, as recommended by MIQE guidelines, was calculated for each reference gene across all samples. Cq values for HPRT1, TOP1, and TBP ranged between cycles 16-22, while 18S rRNA Cq values fell within the earlier cycle range of 2-8.

Note: 18S rRNA Cq Value Adjustment - Due to the significantly lower Cq values observed for 18S rRNA, 1/100th dilution of the sample was used for subsequent qPCR runs. This aimed to bring the 18S rRNA Cq value into a range comparable to the other reference genes across all samples. Amplification plots and melting curves were carefully analyzed to ensure the cycle range of detection of the diluted samples (refer to **supplementary Fig.1**).

d) Ranking HKGs

The mean Cq value and standard deviation (SD) were calculated for each reference gene across all test samples (n=64) with different cell numbers and time

points. The reference genes were ranked based on the combination of the lowest mean Cq value and the least SD. The gene with this combined characteristic was considered the most stable and least variable reference gene for normalization across the test samples.

e) Selection of the Best Performing Reference Gene for ER α Expression analysis

Stimulated samples (from Chapter 4) were used in a qPCR experiment to compare the performance of 18S rRNA and TOP1 as reference genes for target gene expression analysis. The selection criteria focused on the reference gene that yielded the lowest standard deviation (SD) with $2^{\Delta\Delta Cq}$ or fold change values when analyzing the gene of interest (GOI) as ER α . The qPCR procedure was performed as described in section 3.2.3.6(b). The qPCR plate was run in StepOne system instrument, and data was collected for analysis using the instrument's Quant Studio software.

3.2.3.7 Characterization of ER Types

a) Selection and Initial Testing of Primers

The study aimed to analyze the expression of specific transcript variants for the Estrogen Receptor (ER) alpha (ER α), ER beta 1 (ER β 1), and ER beta 2/cx (ER β 2/cx) genes in MCF-7 cells. Primers targeting these specific variants were chosen from a published paper by Green et al. (2009) and given in table 3.6. These

primers were designed to amplify regions spanning exons (coding regions) with a common forward primer for ER β variants.

Table 3.6 Details of primers for ER α , ER β 1 and ER β 2/cx been from published paper Green et al 2009.

Gene	Forward Primers	Reverse Primers	Nucleotide Sequence No.	Product size (bp)
ER α	5'-TGG GCT TAC TGA CCA ACC TG -3'	5'-CCT GAT CAT GGA GGG TCA AA-3'	NM_000125	99
ER β 1	5'-GTT TGG GTG ATT GCC AAG AG-3'	5'-CAC TGG GAC CAC ATT TTT GC-3'	NM_001437	150
ER β 2/cx	5'-GTT TGG GTG ATT GCC AAG AG-3'	5'-CCT TTT CTG CCC TCG CAT-3'	AB006589	105

Gradient PCR (gPCR) was performed to optimize the annealing temperature for each primer set. Analysis of the gPCR products on an agarose gel revealed multiple bands for both ER β 1 and ER β /cx primers.

b) Resolving Multiple Bands for ER β 1 and ER β /cx

Since multiple bands indicate non-specific primer binding, further investigation was required for ER β 1 and ER β 2/cx primers. Literature review confirmed the existence of six natural isoforms of ER β , with ER β 1, ER β 2, and ER β 5 known to be expressed in MCF-7 cells. Further, from literature review mRNA (variants) and protein (isoforms) for human ER β gene ESR2 were listed in table 3.7.

Table 3.7 Information listed mRNA (variants) and protein (isoforms) for human ER β gene ESR2.

Nucleotide (mRNA)	Nucleotide Accession Number	Coding sequence (CDS)	Protein	Protein Accession Number	Total Amino Acid	Tissue Distribution ESR2 gene	Reference
Transcript variant a	NM_001437.2 AF051427.1	1592 bp 2011 bp	Oestrogen receptor beta isoform 1	NP_001428.1 AAC05985.1	530 a.a	High expression: Testis and ovary Medium expression: Spleen and uterus Low expression: Adipocytes, Thymus, mammary gland , placenta, brain	Moore et al, 1998
Transcript variant b Oestrogen Receptor 2 splice Variant Transcript variant k Transcript variant l Oestrogen receptor beta 2 cx	NM_001040275.1 AF051428.1 NM_001291712.1 NM_001291723.1 AB006589.1	1487 bp	Oestrogen receptor beta isoform 2	NP_001035365.1 AAC05751.1 NP_001278641.1 NP_001278652.1 BAA31966.1	495 a.a	High expression: Testis, ovary & Thymus Medium expression: Spleen and uterus Low expression: Adipocytes, mammary gland, placenta, brain	Moore JT et al, 1998 Ogawa S et al, 1998
Oestrogen receptor beta isoform 3 mRNA	AF060555.1	1541 bp	Oestrogen receptor beta isoform 3	AAC15234.1	513 a.a	Testis and ovary	Ogawa S et al, 1998
Transcript variant d	NM_001214902.1 DQ838582.1	1445 bp	Oestrogen receptor beta isoform 3 Oestrogen receptor beta isoform 4	NP_001201831.1 ABH09189.1	481 a.a	High expression: Testis, Low expression: Spleen, thymus, ovary, mammary gland and uterus	Leung YK et al, 2006 Poola I et al, 2005
Transcript variant f	NM_001271876.1 DQ777076.1	1424 bp	Oestrogen receptor beta isoform 5	NP_001258805.1 ABG88022.1	474 a.a	Ovary cDNA	Poola I et al., 2005
Oestrogen receptor beta isoform 5	DQ838583.1	1419 bp	Oestrogen receptor beta isoform 5	ABH09190.1	472 a.a	Breast cancer cell lines	Leung YK et al., 2006
Transcript variant g	NM_001271877.1	1518 bp	Oestrogen receptor beta isoform 6	NP_001258806.1	439 a.a	Testis	Ogawa S et al, 1998

To address the multiple bands, two approaches were taken:

i) *In-silico* analysis:

The primers were aligned with all known ER β transcript reference sequences (as per table 3.7) using online tools like MULTIALIGN. ER β primers from Green et al. 2009 that led to multiple bands were verified for alignment specificity to exon regions (exon 7/8 for ER β 1 and exon 7/cx for ER β 2/cx) (data presumably shown in **supplementary Fig.2**).

ii) Primer redesign:

Due to the high sequence similarity, designing new primers from the initially targeted region (exon-exon junctions) was deemed unsuitable for specific amplification using SYBR Green chemistry. New primers were designed to target the N-terminal region (beginning) of the ER β gene, a region with higher homology among isoforms and lower chance of mismatches, details of new exon-exon spanning location given in table 3.8.

Table 3.8 Detail of the new primer ER β _iso from ESR2 gene

Gene	Forward Primers	Reverse Primers	Nucleotide Sequence No.	Product size (bp)
ESR2	5'-TCA CAT CTG TAT GCG GAA CC- 3'	5'-TGA ACC TGG ACC AGT AAC AG-3'	Specific to various nucleotide variants listed table 3.7	140

Online tools like *Multialign* and *OligoCalci* were used to design new primers for the ESR2 gene and compare it with the primer that led to non-specific bands, aiming for commonality among ER β isoforms (presumably shown in the table 3.9). *In-silico* 'Multialign' was performed using new primers for ER β gene against ER β variants the expected primer product region & size (data is shown in **supplementary Fig. 3**).

Table 3.9 Showing ER β _iso primers location on mRNA and CDS region for ESR2 gene

Transcript variants (Isoforms)	ER β primers led to multiple bands location on mRNA	New ER β _iso primer location mRNA
ER β 1 isoform/ mRNA Transcript variant a	754-773 (FWD) 894-875(REV)	286-305(FWD) 426-407(REV)
ER β 2 isoform/ mRNA Transcript variant b, l, k		
ER β 3 isoform/ mRNA Transcript variant d	376-395(FWD) 516-479(REV)	
ER β 5 isoform/ mRNA Transcript variant f		
ER β 6 isoform/ mRNA Transcript variant g		

c) Testing Newly Designed Primers

gPCR was performed using the newly designed primers for the ER β isoforms & compared with the old ones. The same gPCR protocol as described in section 3.2.3.6 (a) was followed. After qPCR, the samples were loaded onto a 1.2% agarose gel, and the amplified products were visualized using a gel imaging system to determine the optimal annealing temperature for each primer pair.

3.2.3.8 qPCR for Relative Gene Expression of ER α and ER β _iso time culture

Endogenous Control Selection:

TOP1 was chosen as the endogenous control for qPCR based on the outcome from section 3.2.3.6, C_q values across the experimental test samples had less variability.

Experimental Design Untreated samples with a fixed cell density of 2.5×10^5 cells/mL and RNA yield exceeding 1 μ g were used. Samples were collected at four time points: 6 hours (6H), 12 hours (12H), 24 hours (24H), and 48 hours (48H) in culture. Negative controls included water and a no-template control (NTC). Each reaction was run in duplicate for each of the three biological replicates (n=3).

PCR efficiency for ER β _iso was determined using a 10-fold serial dilution of their respective cDNAs. Efficiency values (E) and correlation coefficients (R²) for each primer pair will be presented in the results section.

3.3 Result

3.3.1 Cell density and incubation time for E2 treatment:

To optimize conditions for E2 treatment experiments (in Chapter 4), we evaluated different cell densities and incubation times. Based on this analysis, a cell density of 5×10^5 cells/mL and an incubation time of 48 hours were chosen for subsequent experiments. E2 is known to be a mitogen, promoting rapid cell proliferation (Cooper SC et al, 1989). Therefore, a lower cell density was chosen to minimize the impact of reaching confluence (maximum cell growth) during the experiment. The 48-hour incubation time was selected because microscopic observation confirmed good cell adherence at this point, with no significant detachment or floating cells observed in the DMEM: F12 culture media.

Figure 3.2: Assessment of adherence and confluence in 6-well plate: images from Zeiss bright light microscope (40X) showing adherence and confluence at respective cell-densities (2.5×10^5 , 5×10^5 , 7.5×10^5 , 1×10^6 & 2.5×10^6) cells/mL and time point (6, 12, 24 & 48 hours) of MCF-7 in DMEM:F12 complete media culture.

3.3.2 Total RNA Quantification and Quality Assessment

a) RNA Concentration Total RNA isolated from the experiment described in section 3.2.3.2 was quantified using a NanoDrop 1000 spectrophotometer. The results showed that MCF-7 cells grown at a density of 2.5×10^5 cells/mL in DMEM: F12 media for 48 hours yielded approximately 1 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$ of total RNA (refer to table 3.10). This concentration falls within the ideal range for gene expression studies using real-time PCR (qPCR).

Table 3.10: Representation of average data to total RNA quantification using nanodrop from all the three biological repeat (n=3).

Sample ID Cells/mL in culture for time in hours	RNA quantification values		Average RNA concentration ng/ μL
	A_{260}/A_{280}	A_{260}/A_{230}	
2.5×10^5 (6H)	1.62	0.35	921.21
5×10^5 (6H)	1.62	0.3	586.6
7.5×10^5 (6H)	1.73	0.3	1272.16
1×10^6 (6H)	1.71	0.52	1321.12
2.5×10^6 (6H)	1.83	0.57	2180.01
2.5×10^5 (12H)	1.63	0.49	1306.82
5×10^5 (12H)	1.58	0.42	1383.86
7.5×10^5 (12H)	1.66	0.47	1024.57
1×10^6 (12H)	1.7	0.65	1054.12
2.5×10^6 (12H)	1.68	0.62	2021.08
2.5×10^5 (24H)	1.61	0.44	1112.48
5×10^5 (24H)	1.56	0.5	1083.69
7.5×10^5 (24H)	1.64	0.58	1649.15
1×10^6 (24H)	1.61	0.42	992.98
2.5×10^6 (24H)	1.61	0.38	967.64
2.5×10^5 (48H)	1.6	0.47	1097.27
5×10^5 (48H)	1.58	0.3	716.7
7.5×10^5 (48H)	1.63	0.43	1170.96
1×10^6 (48H)	1.63	0.4	967.2
2.5×10^6 (48H)	1.64	0.47	1197.23

b) RNA Purity: The NanoDrop analysis also provided two absorbance ratios to assess RNA purity: A260/A280 ratio: This ratio reflects RNA purity, with a value around 2.0 indicating pure RNA. Lower values suggest contamination with proteins, phenol, or other substances. A260/A230 ratio: This secondary measure of nucleic acid purity ideally ranges from 1.8 to 2.2. Lower values may indicate co-purified contaminants. While the samples displayed a good RNA yield with a peak absorbance at 260 nm, the A260/A280 ratios suggested some level of contamination, possibly from phenol or ethanol solvents used during RNA extraction.

c) RNA Integrity: RNA integrity was further evaluated using a 2% agarose gel electrophoresis. The gel image (Fig 3.3) represents for few of the total RNA extracted from cell densities & time-point experiment. 1 µg of RNA was loaded per well. All samples exhibited an intensity ratio of 28S/18S rRNA bands close to 2, indicating intact ribosomal RNA. The absence of a smear below the 18S rRNA band suggests minimal RNA degradation. Additionally, the tRNA/5S rRNA band was clearly visible on the gel. However, the gel also revealed leftover material in the wells for samples derived from high cell density cultures. This might represent genomic DNA carryover during RNA isolation using the Ribozol method.

Figure 3.3 Above gel picture is of RNA samples for various cell densities over time in culture using MCF-7 cell line for testing the RNA integrity of the samples. Gel image (A) & (B) is showing two bands upper being 28S rRNA band and lower being 18S rRNA adjacent to 5kilo base pair (Kbp) and 2Kbp on the 1Kb resolved DNA ladder. A, B, C, D & E wells represent 2.5×10^5 , 5×10^5 , 7.5×10^5 , 1×10^6 & 2.5×10^6 cells per mL respectively at four different time point in culture i.e. 6 H, 12 H, 24 H & 48H. This image is representative of gels prepared for one out of three technical repeats ($n=3$).

3.3.3 DNA Contamination Check

Following RNA integrity confirmation, the samples were assessed for DNA contamination. A standard PCR reaction targeting the 18S rRNA gene was performed on DNase-treated RNA samples (presumably the experiment described in section 3.2.3.5). This served as a check for any residual DNA contamination after DNase I treatment. The results showed faint 18S rRNA bands in some samples (Fig 3.4), particularly those derived from higher cell densities. This suggests the presence of trace amounts of DNA contamination even after the initial DNase I treatment. To address this, all samples were subjected to a second round of DNase I treatment.

Figure 3.4: Above gel image is a representation of PCR using 18S rRNA primer (Table 3.5) using RNA samples from technical repeats undergone DNase I treatment. DNA contamination (white circles) seen with sample E at 24H & 48H with amplified 110 bp 18S rRNA band when compared to cDNA BeWo cell line used as positive control adjacent to 100bp band on 1Kbp DNA ladder.

3.3.4 cDNA Integrity Assessment

The integrity of the cDNA samples was verified using PCR amplification of the 18S rRNA gene (experiment described in section 3.2.3.5). The gel image (Fig 3.5) revealed uniform intensity bands for the expected 110 bp 18S rRNA PCR product in all cDNA samples. As expected, no bands were amplified for the negative controls (water and no-reverse transcriptase control, NTC). This successful amplification of 18S rRNA from the cDNA samples confirms the absence of significant primer degradation or PCR inhibition, indicating acceptable quality for further real-time PCR gene expression studies.

Figure 3.5 PCR gel image showing consistency in band size 110 bp 18S rRNA product against 100bp DNA ladder for some of cDNA synthesised samples and also for positive control i.e. cDNA BeWo cell line while it appears no band for negative control and No Reverse Transcriptase control (NTC) sample. This image is a representative of gels prepared for three technical repeats (n=3).

3.3.5 Optimization of Annealing Temperatures for HKG Primers

Gradient PCR (gPCR) was performed to determine the optimal annealing temperature for each primer set targeting the housekeeping genes (HKGs) 18S rRNA, TOP1, HPRT1, and TBP (listed in Table 3.5). Similar to PCR, gPCR amplifies DNA but uses a temperature gradient across the reaction wells to identify the temperature that yields the most specific and intense band for a given primer pair. The gPCR results showed that primer sets for 18S rRNA, TOP1, and HPRT1 all produced bands with the strongest intensity at an annealing temperature of 61°C. The TBP primer set exhibited faint bands consistently across the entire temperature range tested (refer to Fig 3.6).

Figure 3.6 Gradient PCR gel image for (A) 18S rRNA gene (B) HPRT1 gene (C) TOP1 gene and (D) TBP gene HKGs were run on 1.2% agarose gel using a cDNA test sample.

3.3.6 Selection of the Most Stable HKG Using Cq Values

A total of 64 cDNA samples, representing three experimental repeats (n=3) prepared as described in section 3.2.3.1, were used for this analysis. qPCR was performed in duplicate (n=2) on each sample for all four HKGs at best annealing temperature for primers (18S rRNA, TOP1, HPRT1, and TBP). The goal was to identify the HKG with the most stable expression across all samples (n=64) based on the following criteria: Standard deviation (SD) of mean Cq values: A lower SD indicates less variation in Cq values across samples, reflecting more stable gene expression.

a) Challenges with 18S rRNA:

Initial analysis revealed that 18S rRNA amplification occurred in earlier cycles (16-22) compared to the other HKGs. This suggested a higher starting concentration of 18S rRNA transcripts in the samples. To address this and achieve a cycle range comparable to the other HKGs, cDNA samples were diluted (1/10, 1/100, and 1/1000). A 1/100 dilution was found to yield a similar cycle range for 18S rRNA as observed for the other HKGs. Consequently, all cDNA samples were diluted 1/100, and qPCR was repeated for 18S rRNA in duplicate to obtain reliable Cq values.

b) Selection of the Most Stable HKG:

The mean Cq value and standard deviation (SD) were calculated for each HKG across all diluted cDNA samples (n=64), refer to annexure i.A. The results are likely presented in Figure 3.7 and Table 3.11.

Figure 3.7 Comparative graph of mean \pm SD Cq value for HKG's on samples. This data is collective of result of sample run (n=64).

Table 3.11 Stability ranking for HKGs analysed on SD of average Cq value (sample size, n=64, refer to annexure I A).

HKGs	MeanCq SD value
18S rRNA	2.29
TOP1	2.49
HPRT1	3.15
TBP	3.78

Based on these calculations, 18S rRNA emerged as the HKG with the lowest SD and, consequently, the most stable expression across the unstimulated samples from cell densities & time-point experiment.

c) Unexpected Finding and Revised Selection:

However, when using 18S rRNA and TOP1 as endogenous controls (for normalization) in separate qPCR runs targeting the gene of interest (GOI), ER α , an unexpected observation arose. The diluted E2 treatment sample (refer to section 4.2.2 , page no. 127) used for 18S rRNA normalisation resulted in higher standard deviation compared to samples (without dilution) normalised using TOP1. This was determined by calculating ΔCq (delta Cq) values for target genes using stimulated samples. ΔCq is a commonly used method in qPCR for relative gene expression analysis. It considers the difference in Cq values between the GOI and the reference gene (HKG) to account for variations in starting template amounts. Therefore, despite having the lower SD ranking with the mean Cq value analysis for cell densities & time-point samples, 18S rRNA was not considered optimal choice for normalisation due to the large variability seen in with mean ΔCq value for stimulated samples (refer to section 4.2.2). Based on the final analysis, TOP1 was chosen as the most suitable HKG for normalisation in subsequent experiments target gene expression. This decision is justified as TOP1 yielded ΔCq values with less variability (refer to Annexure I. B), leading to a more reliable measure of gene expression change hence TOP1 was considered as endogenous control for qPCR run.

Table 3.12. Stability ranking for HKGs with target gene combined data

Housekeeping genes	SD of mean ΔCq Target genes
18S rRNA	0.3
TOP1	0.2

3.3.7 Validation of Annealing Temperature for ER Primers

gPCR was performed to validate the annealing temperatures chosen for the primer sets targeting the estrogen receptor (ER) genes ER α , ER β 1, and ER β 2/cx (originally described in Green et al., 2009). This step aimed to confirm specific amplification under the chosen temperature conditions using the experimental samples.

a) ER α : The ER α primers successfully amplified a single band of the expected size (99 bp) as shown in Figure 3.8. This confirmed the specificity of the primers and the suitability of the chosen annealing temperature (61°C) for further qPCR analysis of ER α gene expression.

b) ER β 1 and ER β 2/cx: The gPCR results for ER β 1 and ER β 2/cx primers revealed the presence of multiple bands on the gel image (Fig.3.8). This indicates non-specific primer binding, potentially amplifying unintended targets besides the desired ER β gene sequences.

c) Addressing Non-Specific Amplification for ER β 1 and ER β 2/cx:

The issue of multiple bands for ER β 1 and ER β 2/cx was addressed using *in-silico* bioinformatics approach with 'Multialign'. Analysis revealed a high degree of similarity in the coding sequence (CDS) region targeted by the primers across different ER β gene variants. This similarity could hinder specific primer binding to the intended sequences in the genes. Since these unexpected bands were not predicted through initial alignment techniques, the possibility of novel ER β gene splice variants cannot be ruled out. However, further investigations are necessary to confirm this.

Figure 3.8 Gradient PCR gel image on experimental cDNA sample for ER α , ER β 1 & ER β 2/cx gene primers. Image 'A' representing single 99bp band product for ER α while gel image 'B' and 'C' showing multiple bands for ER β 1 and ER β 2/cx gene primers respectively.

d) ER β _iso Primer Optimization for qPCR

This study compared the performance of ER β primer for qPCR analysis. Gradient PCR was employed to evaluate primer specificity at two annealing temperatures (57°C and 61°C). The results shown in figure 3.9 revealed significant differences between the originally chosen primers and a newly designed primer pair named "ER β _iso." The ER β _iso primer set exhibited superior target specificity, making them ideal for subsequent qPCR studies investigating ER β gene expression

Figure 3.9: A PCR gel image comparing primers for ER(s) used with single band product for newly designed ER β isoform primer.

3.3.8 Validation of PCR Efficiency and Primer Specificity

a) Importance of PCR Efficiency:

In relative gene expression studies using qPCR, it's crucial to ensure comparable PCR efficiencies between the primers targeting the endogenous control (EC) gene and the genes of interest (GOIs). This ensures accurate quantification of relative mRNA expression levels.

Validation Experiment:

An experiment involving primer dilution was performed to validate the PCR efficiency of the primers used in a study.

Calculating PCR Efficiency:

The PCR efficiency (E) was calculated using the slope (m) obtained from the linear equation of the standard curve generated during the validation experiment.

The formula used is: $E = 10^{(-1/m)} - 1$ (Equation 2)

The percentage efficiency (%E) is then calculated as: $\%E = (2 - E) \times 100$
.....(Equation 3)

Factors Affecting PCR Efficiency:

There are various factors that can lead to misleadingly low (< 100%) PCR efficiency calculations. These factors include: pipetting errors; inaccurate

dilutions; primer dimer formation; high primer-to-template ratio; impurities in RNA samples (e.g., from ethanol or phenol carryover during isolation); Inconsistent Cq values across serial dilutions; Hairpin loop structures in the target sequence.

Table 3.13: Details of PCR efficiency and R² value for ER β _iso primer.

Gene	Forward and Reverse primer (5'-3')	Product (bp)	R ²	E (%)	Reference
ER β _iso	FWD 5'-TGG GCT TAC TGA CCA ACC TG -3' REV 5'-CCT GAT CAT GGA GGG TCA AA-3'	140	0.99	90 %	This study

3.3.9 Relative gene expression for ER α and ER β in MCF-7 over time in culture

This section investigates how the expression levels of ER α and ER β genes change over time in MCF-7 cells grown in culture was performed (as described in experiment section 3.2.3.8). The goal is to understand the baseline expression patterns before further experiments involving E2 treatment.

The text correctly identifies the most common method for relative gene expression analysis: the $\Delta\Delta Cq$ method (Livak & Schmittgen, 2001; Schmittgen & Livak, 2008). This method relies on two key assumptions: Doubling of PCR product with each cycle & stable expression of the reference gene (endogenous control) across all samples. The $\Delta\Delta Cq$ method allows for comparisons between samples but requires careful consideration of these assumptions. The experiment used samples with a fixed cell density of 2.5×10^5 cells/mL collected at four time points: 6H, 12H, 24H,

and 48H in culture. qPCR was performed in duplicate (n=2) for the endogenous control gene and the target genes (ER α and ER β). Relative gene expression was calculated using the $\Delta\Delta Cq$ method based on average Cq values obtained from the three biological replicates (n=3) at each time point. The 6H time point was chosen as the calibrator for comparison with 12H, 24H, and 48H expression levels. The rationale for excluding the zero-time point is sound. Harvesting cells can introduce stress, potentially leading to inaccurate expression estimates (Chaudhary, 2008; Huang et al., 2010).

Fig 3.10 Two graphs showing relative gene expression as mean fold change with bar representing SD for (A) ER α and (B) ER β using a fixed cell number for different time points of 12H, 24H and 48H to study any change in gene expression with time in culture compared with 6H as arbitrary or control sample.

Chapter 4

E2 Treatment

Relative Gene Expression

ER α & ER β in MCF-7

4.0 Effect of 17 β -Estradiol on Relative ER Gene Expression in MCF-7 Cells

4.1 Introduction

Studies show that oestrogen plays a significant role in the development of some cancers (hormonal carcinogenesis) as observed in cell cultures. Higher lifetime exposure to estradiol (E2), the main form of oestrogen, can speed up the growth of both the lining (epithelium) and supportive tissue (stroma) in the breast. This rapid growth increases the likelihood of mutations accumulating in these cells, potentially leading to breast cancer. Factors such as starting menstruation at a young age (early menarche), having a first child later in life (late first full-term pregnancy), and going through menopause later are all associated with a higher lifetime exposure to oestrogen and therefore a potentially increased risk of breast cancer (Russo et al., 2002; Clemons & Goss, 2001).

Oestradiol (E2), the main form of oestrogen, is produced through a process called synthesis. This process happens mainly in the ovaries before menopause and in other tissues throughout the body (peripheral tissues) after menopause. In postmenopausal women, E2 is formed by converting a substance called androgen (an oestrogen precursor) into E2 through a process called aromatization. Additionally, E2 can be taken up from circulation in the form of oestrogen sulfate and then converted to usable E2 through a process called desulfation (Elissen & Hankinson, 2008; Zhu, 1998).

Interestingly, the concentration of oestrogen metabolites can vary significantly between the bloodstream and breast tissue. For example, postmenopausal

women can have E2 levels in their breast tissue that are 10 to 50 times higher compared to the levels found in their blood (Sasano et al., 2009). Blood oestrogen levels may not accurately represent the actual amount of oestrogen and its breakdown products present within breast tissue. This is because breast tissue can produce its own oestrogen locally through a process called local metabolism. Because of this ability, breast tissue acts like an "intracrine organ." This local oestrogen production might be linked to the development and progression of breast cancer. In other words, the hormonal environment surrounding breast tissue itself may play a significant role in breast cancer formation (Yaghjian & Colditz, 2011).

There is ongoing debate about the main way breast cancer tissue produces estradiol (E2). One pathway, the aromatase pathway, involves converting a precursor hormone to E2. This pathway gains support because a key enzyme (aromatase, encoded by the CYP19A gene) is more highly expressed in the supportive tissue (stroma) surrounding tumors, which can also produce E2 (Santen et al., 1997). Another pathway involves converting a different oestrogen molecule (estrone sulfate) into usable E2. Interestingly, a study found higher levels of several sex hormones, including E2, in tumor tissue itself compared to blood serum levels (Mady et al., 2000). This suggests that breast tumors can produce their own E2, potentially contributing to their growth. Some researchers propose that during the early stages of breast cancer development, oestrogen produced locally by supportive tissue cells (stromal fibroblasts) fuels the growth of the epithelial cells lining the breast ducts (epithelial expansion). This process likely involves a

signaling mechanism called paracrine signaling, where the stromal cells release oestrogen that interacts with oestrogen receptors on the epithelial cells. In later stages of breast cancer, the epithelial cells themselves may take over oestrogen production, creating a self-sustaining loop (autocrine signaling) that could further promote tumor growth (Shekhar et al., 2003).

Oestradiol (E2) appears to play a complex role in tumor development. Studies suggest that E2 can influence the production of signaling molecules called cytokines by immune cells within the tumor. Additionally, E2 may attract immune cells like macrophages and lymphocytes to the tumor site. Interestingly, these same immune cells can produce cytokines that, in turn, seem to stimulate E2 production. However, the exact details of this interaction between E2 and cytokines remain unclear (Reed & Purohit, 1997; Roy et al., 2007). There is strong evidence that the hormonal environment surrounding breast tumors plays a critical role in the development and progression of cancer. It appears that breast tumors may arise due to a breakdown in the normal communication between the epithelial cells (lining) and the stromal cells (supportive tissue) within the breast. This disruption likely involves complex interactions between hormone regulation, hormone production, and the influence of other factors secreted by the surrounding stromal cells. MCF-7 cells are a valuable tool for studying oestrogen signaling and its effects in breast cancer research, particularly for investigating how oestrogen impacts gene expression in the laboratory (in vitro). These cells have been widely used to explore both short-term and long-term effects of oestrogen (Katzenellenbogen, 1987).

The MCF-7 cell line is a well-established tool for studying hormone-responsive breast cancer. These immortalized epithelial cells were originally derived 45 years ago at the Michigan Institute of Cancer Foundation in the US from a patient with metastatic breast cancer. The cells were isolated from pleural effusion, which is fluid buildup around the lungs. The name "MCF-7" comes from the institute where they were developed (Levenson & Jordan, 1997). The researchers were able to keep these initially loosely organized cells (free-floating passages) alive and growing for 71 weeks. They achieved this by regularly transferring them (sub-cultivation) to a specific nutrient broth called Eagle's minimal essential media. This broth was enriched with additional ingredients to support the cells' growth, including essential amino acids, insulin, antibiotics (penicillin and streptomycin), and fetal calf serum (Soule et al., 1973).

In early studies, researchers compared the newly developed MCF-7 cells to a throat cancer cell line. They found that the MCF-7 cells grown between passages 71 and 87 expressed a significant amount of oestrogen receptor (ER). The KD value, which reflects the binding affinity of oestrogen to the ER, was 2.5 nM for oestradiol (E2) in these MCF-7 cells (Brooks et al., 1973). This suggests that MCF-7 cells possess a strong ability to bind to oestrogen. Compared to sub-lines derived from MCF-7 cells that are resistant to the anti-oestrogen drug tamoxifen, the original MCF-7 cell line expresses lower levels of oestrogen receptor (ER). This is also true for progesterone receptor (PR) expression in these cells (Baguley & Leung, 2011).

Scientists can create MCF-7 sublines with varying levels of oestrogen receptor (ER) expression. They achieve this by treating the original MCF-7 cells (wild type) with several methods: exposure to anti-oestrogen drugs, long-term or short-term treatment with estradiol (E2), and changes in the nutrient medium the cells are grown in. These different treatments cause the MCF-7 cells to diverge genetically (genomic level) and in their gene expression patterns (RNA level) compared to the original MCF-7 cell line (Nugoli et al., 2003). This allows researchers to study the effects of different conditions on ER expression and breast cancer development.

MCF-7 cells respond differently to oestrogen (E2) depending on their past exposure. When MCF-7 cells are deprived of oestrogen for a long time (LTED) and then re-exposed to E2, they are more likely to undergo apoptosis (programmed cell death). Similarly, long-term treatment with anti-oestrogen drugs also makes MCF-7 cells more susceptible to E2-induced apoptosis. Interestingly, exposing MCF-7 cells to E2 for a long time (LTEE) has the opposite effect, leading to significant changes in the expression of many genes throughout the genome (Spink et al., 2009). This suggests that a cell's history with oestrogen can influence its future response to the hormone. Researchers can remove oestrogen from the culture medium for MCF-7 cells by using a special type of serum that has been treated with charcoal to absorb oestrogens. This process of creating long-term oestrogen-deprived MCF-7 cells leads to several changes in the cells. First, the cells become hypersensitive to oestrogen, meaning they respond more strongly to even small amounts of the hormone. Second, the overall pattern of gene expression in the cells is altered. Finally, there is an up-regulation of specific

signaling pathways, including those involving oestrogen receptor alpha ($ER\alpha$), the Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinase (MAPK) pathway, and the mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR) pathway. These pathways play a role in cell growth and survival (Santen et al., 2005). This suggests that long-term oestrogen deprivation can cause MCF-7 cells to adapt in a way that makes them more sensitive to oestrogen and potentially more aggressive.

Studies have shown that E2 can induce apoptosis (programmed cell death) in MCF-7 cells that have been deprived of oestrogen for a long time (LTED). This process involves several steps:

Activation of the Fas death receptor pathway: E2 triggers the assembly of a protein complex on the cell surface that includes Fas receptors and Fas ligand (FasL).

Mitochondrial changes: E2 leads to the release of cytochrome c (cyt c) from the mitochondria, a critical event in apoptosis initiation.

Regulation of Bcl-2 family proteins: E2 likely alters the activity of proteins like Bcl-2, which are involved in controlling cell survival or death.

Down-regulation of NF- κ B: E2 also appears to decrease the activity of an anti-apoptotic factor called nuclear factor kappa-B (NF- κ B).

These findings suggest that E2 can act as a double-edged sword for LTED MCF-7 cells, promoting both growth under some conditions and cell death under others (references: Song et al., 2001; Lewis et al., 2005a; Song et al., 2005; Lewis et al., 2005b; Lewis et al., 2008).

E2 has been shown to induce apoptosis (programmed cell death) not only in laboratory experiments with MCF-7 cells (in vitro) but also in live mice (in-vivo). However, the exact mechanisms by which E2 causes cell death in these animal models are still not fully understood. Additionally, E2 can induce apoptosis in cancer cells that have become resistant to anti-hormone drugs used to treat breast cancer (Yao et al., 2000; Osipo et al., 2003; Zhang et al., 2009). This suggests that E2 may have potential therapeutic applications, even for tumors that no longer respond to conventional hormone-blocking therapies.

These findings on E2 inducing apoptosis in cell studies are mirrored by clinical trial results. A study led by Ellis et al. investigated the use of E2 as a treatment for metastatic breast cancer (Ellis et al., 2009). Interestingly, they found that a daily dose of 6 mg of E2 was able to halt tumor growth and even shrink tumors in about 25% of women whose cancer had become resistant to both standard and anti-hormonal therapies. This suggests that E2 may have a role in treating some cases of advanced breast cancer, even when other hormone-based treatments have failed.

In contrast to the cell death observed with short-term oestrogen deprivation, long-term oestrogen exposure (LTEE) appears to promote cancer development. LTEE may activate genes and trigger mutations that lead to persistent changes in gene expression within MCF-7 cells. This can enhance the tumorigenic potential of these cells. Studies using serum-free DF5 and DC5 media have shown that MCF-7 cells adapt to LTEE and respond differently to physiological levels of oestrogen. This

adaptation involves significant alterations in gene expression throughout the genome. These findings are supported by both laboratory experiments (in vitro) and studies in mice with weakened immune systems (SCID models). In these mice, chronic E2 exposure of MCF-7 cells resulted in increased growth independent of attachment (anchorage-independent growth) and enhanced invasion into surrounding tissues (Zou & Matsumura, 2003; Spink et al, 2009). This suggests that long-term exposure to oestrogen may contribute to the development of more aggressive breast cancers.

While oestrogen receptor (ER) levels play a role in how MCF-7 cells respond to oestrogen (E2), it's not the whole story. These cells also have other growth factor receptors on their cell surface, such as EGFR and HER2, which are separate from the ER pathway. Interestingly, E2-responsive MCF-7 cells can release their own growth factors that act on the insulin-like growth factor type 1 receptor (IGF-IR) on the same cell in an autocrine manner (Hamelers et al., 2003). This suggests that MCF-7 cells can activate their own growth through multiple pathways, not just through the classic ER pathway. There's also evidence that microRNAs (miRNAs) play a role in regulating IGF-2 signaling within MCF-7 cells (Martin et al., 2012). Understanding these additional signaling pathways is important for a more complete picture of how MCF-7 cells grow and respond to hormonal cues.

Studies have shown that insulin can influence the amount of oestrogen receptor (ER) present in MCF-7 breast cancer cells. This change in ER levels can explain why these cells become less responsive to tamoxifen, an anti-oestrogen drug, and

to oestrogen itself (Butler et al., 1981). This suggests a potential link between insulin signaling and oestrogen signaling in breast cancer development and response to treatment.

The way MCF-7 cells are grown in the lab can influence their characteristics. When these cells are cultured in a medium containing calf serum and a small amount of oestrogen, they tend to maintain their original phenotype, which is positive for oestrogen receptor (ER). However, if oestrogen is completely removed from the medium, the cells will favor the growth of variants that rely on other signaling pathways for survival and proliferation. These alternative pathways involve growth factor receptors such as EGFR and HER2 (Baguley et al., 2011). This highlights the importance of considering the growth environment when studying MCF-7 cells and interpreting experimental results.

Studies have shown that including human breast fibroblast cells along with MCF-7 cells can increase MCF-7 tumor growth. This suggests that fibroblasts in the tumor microenvironment may play a significant role in breast cancer progression, and their influence can be even stronger than the effects of growth factors produced by the cancer cells themselves (Horgan et al., 1987). This highlights the importance of considering cell-to-cell communication within tumors when studying breast cancer biology.

In this chapter MCF-7 cells obtained from the ATCC LGC standard collection at passage 146 were cultured in a specific nutrient medium called DMEM:F12 that lacked phenol red. We also included 10% fetal bovine serum in the medium but

did not add any additional oestrogen. We made this choice because some studies have shown that phenol red, a common component of cell culture media, can have weak oestrogen-like effects (Berthois et al., 1985). By eliminating phenol red from the medium, we aimed to ensure that any observed effects on the MCF-7 cells were not due to this potential confounding factor.

When studying the effects of oestrogen (E2) on fibroblast and trophoblast cells, researchers often use culture media containing serum. This is because the amount of E2 naturally present in fetal bovine serum (FBS), a common component of cell culture media, is very low. This low level of E2 in FBS is unlikely to significantly alter the overall concentration of E2 in the culture medium. Therefore, using media with serum allows researchers to investigate the effects of additional E2 they add to the system while minimizing the influence of any background oestrogen from the serum itself (Henson et al., 1996; Detti et al., 2007).

This chapter aims to determine how higher E2 level treatment affects the relative gene expression of ER α and ER β gene in MCF-7 cells. It will be achieved with the following a two-step approach:

Optimization of an Alamar Blue cell viability assay: This initial step will be crucial to establish a non-toxic E2 concentration range for effective experimentation with MCF-7 cells.

To assess the effects of E2 on MCF-7 cell proliferation and cytotoxicity (cell death), the Alamar Blue (AB) assay has been decided. This assay offers several advantages:

Simplicity and Rapidity: AB is a user-friendly and time-saving method.

Efficiency and Reliability: It provides reliable and consistent measurements of cell viability.

Sensitivity: AB can detect changes in cell viability even with a small number of cells (as few as 80). This sensitivity rivals radioactive methods but avoids associated environmental and waste disposal concerns.

Safety and Cost-Effectiveness: AB is non-toxic to cells and eliminates the need for cell death to obtain measurements, unlike the MTT assay. This allows for further investigation of the same cells and reduces costs, especially with primary cultures.

Colorimetric/Florescence Readout: AB utilizes a colorimetric assay format, making it amenable to automation and high-throughput screening in micro=titer plates (McBride et al., 2004).

Mechanism of AB:

AB, also known by its original name resazurin, is a non-fluorescent blue dye. When taken up by viable cells, mitochondrial enzymes reduce it to a pink, fluorescent form called resorufin. The amount of resorufin produced is proportional to the

metabolic activity of the cells, providing a measure of their viability. This assay can even detect reduction in the medium due to some chemical reactions, although intracellular reduction is preferred (Mistuhashi & De Fries, 1995).

Figure 4.1 Chemical reaction showing conversion of Resazurin to Resorufin within metabolically active cells resulting into generation of fluorescent product & fluorescence produced is proportional to the number of viable cells. (Figure is created using Chemdraw)

Validation of AB:

The suitability of AB for this study is supported by its successful application in cytotoxicity and proliferation studies across various cell types, including immortalized and cancer cell lines (Page et al., 1993; Nakayama et al., 1997), human lymphocytes (Ahmed et al., 1994), primary neuronal cultures (White et al., 1996), and fibroblasts (Voyti-Harbin et al., 1998).

Evaluation of E2 effects on ER α and ER β gene expression: Once the optimal E2 concentration range is established, it will be used in reverse transcription

quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR) developed assay (refer to chapter 3) to evaluate the effects of E2 on the relative gene expression of ER α and ER β in E2-stimulated MCF-7 cell samples.

By investigating these objectives, will aid-in gaining a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between E2, ERs, and their potential roles in breast cancer development.

4.2 Method

This section describes the methods used in the research to investigate the effects of higher estrogen (E2) on MCF-7 breast cancer cells.

4.2.1 Optimizing the Alamar Blue (AB) Assay for MCF-7 Cells

a) Cell Seeding and Density Variation:

MCF-7 cells were grown in a T-75 cm² flask and harvested when they reached 70% confluence. To test the effect of cell density on the AB assay, a series of dilutions were prepared from starting cell density of 2.5×10^6 cells/mL. Half-serial dilutions were performed for a total of seven dilutions. From each diluted cell suspension, 200 μ L aliquots were added to five replicate wells (n=5) in a flat-bottom 96-well plate. An additional well containing only media served as a control for background absorbance.

b) Incubation and AB Treatment:

The plate was incubated overnight at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ incubator. After 12 hours, the media in each well was replaced with fresh media, and 20 µL of AB dye was added to all wells, including the control. The plate was returned to the incubator for further incubation at designated time points: 3, 6, 12, 24, 30, 36, 48, and 72 hours.

c) Measurement of Cell Viability:

At each time point, the plate was read using a Bio-trick ELISA plate reader. Absorbance was measured at two wavelengths: 570 nm (primary absorbance) and 595 nm (excitation).

d) Data Analysis:

The collected data will be used to plot a graph of cell density versus the percentage of Alamar Blue reduction (ABR). This analysis will help determine the optimal cell density and incubation time for the AB assay when used with MCF-7 cells in subsequent experiments.

4.2.2 Preparation and Application of E2 Concentrations

a) E2 Stock Solution:

10 mM main stock solution of E2 was prepared by dissolving 0.00272 g of E2 in 1 mL of DMSO. 1Mm working stock solution was made in culture media containing 10% DMSO caused precipitation, performing a 1/10 dilution of the 10 mM stock solution in DMSO.

b) E2 Treatment level:

From working solutions of 1Mm E2 solution various concentrations of E2 (1 μ M, 100 nM, and 1 nM) were prepared fresh in culture media with less than \leq 1% DMSO. For each final E2 concentration, a corresponding vehicle control containing the DMSO (0.1%, 0.01%, and 0.0001%) was also prepared for use as vehicle control.

c) Cell Exposure and Viability Assay:

MCF-7 cells were harvested from a T-75 cm² flask and seeded in 96-well plates at a density of 1.5×10^5 cells per 200 μ L in five replicates (n=5) per treatment group. An additional well containing only media served as a control. The plates were incubated overnight at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ incubator. The following day, the media in each well was replaced with fresh media containing the designated E2 concentration or vehicle control (Fig. 4.2). The plates were incubated again for two different time points: 6 hours and 18 hours. After each incubation period, 20 μ L of Alamar Blue (AB) dye was added to each well. Following a further 24-hour incubation with AB, the plates were read using an ELISA plate reader at wavelengths of 570 nm (absorbance) and 595 nm (excitation). The data will be used to calculate the percentage of Alamar Blue reduction (ABR) and assess the effect of higher E2 concentrations on MCF-7 cell viability compared to controls.

Figure 4.2 Flow diagram of experimental design to study effect of E2 exposure over time on MCF-7.

4.2.3 Investigating E2-Stimulated ER Gene Expression using RT-qPCR

a) Experimental Design:

MCF-7 cells were seeded in 6-well plates at a density of 2.5×10^5 cells/mL and allowed to incubate for 48H. The experiment was performed in three biological replicates, designated as R1, R2, and R3.

b) E2 Stimulation and RNA Extraction:

Cells were stimulated with a range of E2 concentrations as 1 nM, 100 nM & 1 μ M) for two time points: 6H and 18H. For each E2 concentration, a corresponding vehicle control containing the same percentage of DMSO was included. After stimulation, total RNA was extracted from the cells using the Ribozol method (described in Section 3.2.3.2).

c) RNA Quality Control and cDNA Synthesis:

The extracted RNA was quantified using a NanoDrop instrument and its integrity was assessed using gel electrophoresis (as performed in Section 3.2.3.2). To eliminate DNA contamination, which can interfere with downstream applications, the RNA samples were treated with DNase enzyme twice (refer to Section 3.2.3.2 for details). Following confirmation of DNA-free RNA, cDNA synthesis was performed (refer to Section 3.2.3.2 for details). cDNA integrity was also evaluated.

d) RT-qPCR Analysis of ER Genes:

The synthesized cDNA samples were diluted 1/100th and used for quantitative real-time PCR (RT-qPCR) in duplicates (n=2) for each run (R1, R2, and R3). The housekeeping gene 18S rRNA was used as an endogenous control for normalization. Specific primers designed for ER α and ER β *_iso* genes (as described in Table 3.6 & Table 3.8 of Chapter 3) were employed for amplification. The mean C_q (cycle threshold) values obtained from the three replicates were used to calculate the relative gene expression levels using the $\Delta\Delta C_q$ method.

4.3 Result

4.3.1 Optimising AB assay on MCF-7

MCF-7 cells were optimised for AB assay and cell range 78,125 cells /mL was found optimal with % alamar blue reduction (ABR) above 50 (table 3.1) and intermediate range of the plateau in the graph shown below (Figure 3.3).

Figure 4.3 Above graph is showing % reduction of AB on the y-axis for different cell number at various time points on the x-axis for MCF-7 while optimisation experiment laid to choose optimal cell density with higher % reduction AB. The colorimetric measurement was taken by ELISA plate readout at absorbance 570 nm and 595nm).

Table 4.1 Listed % Reduction alamar blue for cell/mL at 24H time point and status with achieving plateau on the graph (Fig 4.3).

Worked out Cells per well	% Alamar blue dye reduction \pm SD at 24H	Plateau
500,000	56.19 \pm 1.3	Reached
250,000	54.38 \pm 2.7	Reached
125,000	59.77 \pm 3.5	Reached
62,500	71.42 \pm 3.8	Near
31,200	71.13 \pm 3.0	Near
15,000	68.60 \pm 3.4	Intermediate
7800	53.56 \pm 2.2	Intermediate
3900	42.15 \pm 0.9	Intermediate

Effect of E2 in DMSO on MCF-7 Cell Viability

To assess the potential cytotoxicity of E2 working stock solution with 1% DMSO v/v, MCF-7 cells were exposed to treatment E2 concentration as 1nM, 100 nM & 1µM along with respective vehicle control 0.1% - 0.0001%) in culture media. Alamar Blue assay was used as per section 4.2.2 (c) to measure cell viability after exposure. Figure 4.4 below represent the cell viability for E2 treatment with respective vehicle control.

Figure 4.4 Cell viability for MCF-7 cells treated with [E2] : Above graph (a) & (b) is showing % ABR ELISA plate read out (absorbance 570nm/595nm) after 24H incubation with AB in plate undergone treatments with E2 for two time point of 6H and 18 H respectively. In each graph data showing control, E2 treatment range 1nM, 100nM, 1µM and their vehicle control respectively.

4.3.2 E2 Stimulation and RNA Isolation for RT-qPCR Analysis

MCF-7 cells were seeded in six-well plates at a density of 2.5×10^5 cells/mL, as established in Chapter 3. The cells were then stimulated with a range of higher E2 concentrations (1 nM - 1 μ M) prepared in culture media containing a corresponding vehicle control of DMSO (0.1% to 0.0001%). A control group with no E2 treatment was also included. This experiment was performed in three biological replicates, designated as R1, R2, and R3. Cells were stimulated for two time points: 6 hours and 18 hours. After stimulation, total RNA was extracted from the cells using the Ribozol method described in Section 3.2.3.2. The extracted RNA was quantified using a NanoDrop instrument and its integrity was assessed using a 2% agarose gel electrophoresis, as performed in Section 3.2.3.2.

4.3.2.1 RNA Quality Assessment

The table summarizes the RNA quality measurements obtained using a nanodrop instrument.

While the RNA samples exhibited good yield with a prominent absorbance peak at 260 nm, the A260/A280 ratios suggest potential contamination from phenol or ethanol used during the RNA extraction process (refer to Section 3.2.3.2 for details).

Table 4.2 (a) & (b) representation measurement from Nano-drop of Total RNA from E2 stimulated sample at points as 6H and 18H. This was achieved for three biological repeats (n=3).

(a)

Sample ID Cells culture for 6H	RNA quantification values		RNA concentration ng/ μ L
	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₈₀	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₃₀	
Control	1.76	0.42	774.9
E2 1 μ M	1.67	0.57	682.2
E2 100 nM	1.8	0.43	815.3
E2 1 nM	1.84	0.65	602.8
0.1% DMSO	1.65	0.53	578.9
0.01% DMSO	1.74	0.43	702.1
0.0001% DMSO	1.7	0.38	758.1

(b)

Sample ID Cells in culture for 18H	RNA quantification values		RNA concentration ng/ μ L
	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₈₀	A ₂₆₀ /A ₂₃₀	
Control	1.65	0.43	169.8
E2 1 μ M	1.74	0.56	948.6
E2 100 nM	1.82	0.67	889.5
E2 1 nM	1.76	0.54	334.8
0.1% DMSO	1.85	0.43	198.4
0.01% DMSO	1.58	0.54	398.2
0.0001% DMSO	1.62	0.63	746.5

4.3.2.2 RNA Integrity Check

The integrity of the extracted RNA was further evaluated using gel electrophoresis with a 2% agarose gel, following the MIQE guidelines. This analysis assesses the presence of intact ribosomal RNA (rRNA) bands (28S and 18S) and helps ensure the absence of significant degradation.

Figure 4.5 Above gel picture is of RNA samples from E2 treatment experiment using MCF-7 cell line for testing the RNA integrity. Gel image is showing two bands upper being 28S rRNA band and lower being 18S rRNA adjacent to 5kilo base pair (Kbp) and 2Kbp on the 1Kb resolved DNA ladder. A to E wells represent samples as 0.1% DMSO (Vehicle control to 1 μ M E2), 0.01% DMSO (Vehicle control VC_100 nM E2), 0.0001% DMSO (Vehicle control VC_1 μ M E2), 1 μ M E2 and 100 nM E2 at 6H respectively while wells from F to I represent samples as 0.1% DMSO, 0.01% DMSO, 1 mM E2 & 100nM E2 at 18 respectively. This image is representative of gels prepared for three technical repeats (n=3).

4.3.2.3 Confirmation of DNA Absence after DNase I Treatment

To ensure the absence of contaminating DNA, which can interfere with downstream applications like cDNA synthesis, all RNA samples were treated with DNase enzyme twice. Subsequently, PCR amplification using primers specific for

the 18S rRNA gene was performed on the DNase-treated RNA samples. The absence of a PCR product for 18S rRNA confirms that there was no detectable DNA contamination in the RNA samples, proceeding them for cDNA synthesis with confidence.

Figure 4.6 Above gel image is a representation of PCR using 18S rRNA primer (Table 3.5) on E2 stimulated RNA samples from technical repeats undergone DNase I treatment. Negative control (water) well showed no band as amplified 110 bp 18S rRNA band in positive control having the cDNA BeWo cell line when compared to 100bp size on 1Kbp DNA ladder. No band amplification detected in samples from A to I.

4.3.2.4 Verification of cDNA Integrity using 18S rRNA Primers

Following cDNA synthesis (as described in Section 2.4.5) of the DNase-treated RNA samples (refer to previous section for DNase treatment confirmation), the integrity of the cDNA was evaluated using PCR amplification with primers specific for the 18S rRNA gene. Amplification of the 18S rRNA target in the cDNA samples indicates successful cDNA synthesis and the presence of amplifiable cDNA

templates. This step helps ensure the quality of the cDNA before proceeding with further analyses like RT-qPCR.

Figure 4.7 PCR gel image showing consistency in band size 110 bp 18S rRNA product against 1Kbp DNA ladder for cDNA synthesised E2 stimulated samples shown in well A to H while no band for control and NTC samples 6H & 18H was seen. This image is a representative of gels prepared for three technical repeats (n=3).

4.3.2.5 RT-qPCR Analysis of ER α and ER β Gene Expression

a. Experimental Design and Controls:

Quantitative real-time PCR (RT-qPCR) was performed to evaluate the relative expression levels of estrogen receptor genes (ER α and ER β _iso) in E2-stimulated MCF-7 cells. As revised (Section 3.2.3.6), TOP1 was chosen as the endogenous control gene for normalisation due to its stable expression in the stimulated samples. The experiment E2 treatment was conducted in three biological replicates designated as R1, R2, and R3 (refer to Section 3.2.3.1 for details). cDNA

samples from each replicate were run in triplicates (n=3) for each target gene (ER α and ER β _iso) and the endogenous control (TOP1) to obtain Cq (cycle threshold) values.

b. Data Analysis using the $\Delta\Delta Cq$ Method:

The ΔCq method was used to calculate the relative gene expression levels. ΔCq was calculated for each sample by subtracting the Cq value of the endogenous control (TOP1) from the Cq value of the target gene (ER α or ER β _iso). The average ΔCq and standard deviation ($\Delta Cq \pm SD$) were determined for each treatment group across the replicates (R1, R2, and R3). $\Delta\Delta Cq$ was then calculated for each replicate by subtracting the average ΔCq of the untreated control group from the ΔCq value of each treated sample, refer to annexure II A-D.

Finally, the fold change in gene expression was determined using the formula $2^{-\Delta\Delta Cq}$. The mean fold change and standard deviation (mean fold change \pm SD) were calculated for each target gene across the samples for three biological replicates. Non-parametric Mann-Whitney's U-test were used for statistical analysis on the data using minitab software (trial version) and results are shared in table 4.3 & table 4.4.

a. ER α Gene Expression at 6H

b. ER α Gene Expression at 18H

Figure 4.8 Above graph is representation of $2^{-\Delta\Delta Cq}$ or mean fold value for ER α target gene normalized with TOP1 gene using three biological repeats of E2 treatment experiment runs a. 6H & b. 18H time point. Data analysis achieved using non-parametric statistical tool Mann-Whitney's U-test (table 4.3, below) significance in data was explored. For significant difference p value symbol * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.005$, *** $p < 0.0005$ is defined.

Table 4.3 Mann-Whitney's U-test data (refer to Supplementary table 1) for ER α target gene normalised against TOP1 endogenous control.

ER ALPHA Mann-Whitney: Control 6H, E2 Treatment 6H							
Sample	N	Median	Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence	W-Value	P-Value
Control 6H	12	1.04032	0.211825	(-0.0286897, 0.505688)	95.72%	153.00	0.145
E2 Treatment 6H	9	0.78328					
ER ALPHA Mann-Whitney: Control 18H, E2 Treatment 18H							
Sample	N	Median	Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence	W-Value	P-Value
Control 18H	12	0.924957	0.403258	(0.140038, 0.682240)	95.72%	175.00	0.003
E2 Treatment 18H	9	0.588136					

ER β Gene expression at 6H

ERβ Gene expression at 18H

Figure 4.9 Above graph is representation of $2^{-\Delta\Delta Cq}$ or mean fold value for $ER\beta$ target gene normalized with $TOP1$ gene using three biological repeats of E2 treatment experiment runs a. 6H & b. 18H time point. Data analysis achieved using non-parametric statistical tool Mann-Whitney's U-test (table 4.4, below) significance in data was explored. For significant difference p value symbol * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.005$, *** $p < 0.0005$ is defined.

Table 4.4 Mann-Whitney's U-test data (refer to Supplementary table 1) for $ER\beta$ target gene normalised against $TOP1$ endogenous control.

ER BETA Mann-Whitney: Control 6H, E2 Treatment 6H							
Sample	N	Median	Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence	W-Value	P-Value
Control 6H	12	1.16005	0.157932	(-0.293570, 0.740151)	95.72%	143.00	0.456
E2 Treatment 6H	9	0.88797					
ER BETA Mann-Whitney: Control 18H, E2 Treatment 18H							
Sample	N	Median	Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence	W-Value	P-Value
Control 18H	12	0.816460	0.237673	(0.0201395, 0.566105)	95.72%	164.00	0.025
E2 Treatment 18H	9	0.613418					

Chapter 5

E2 Treatment

Relative Gene Expression

ACKR(s) in MCF-7

5.0 Oestrogen Regulation of Atypical Chemokine Receptor Expression in MCF-7 Breast Cancer Cells

5.1 Introduction

The presence of a chemokine network is essential for cancer-induced inflammation, which plays a critical role throughout cancer development and progression. Malignant and stromal cells within a tumor's microenvironment produce chemokines and their receptors. These signaling molecules not only control the movement and infiltration of immune cells (leukocytes) into the initial tumor but also influence processes like blood vessel formation (angiogenesis), cancer cell growth, and the spread of cancer cells to other organs (metastasis) (Allavena et al., 2011). CCL12, discovered as the first chemokine in tumor cell secretions, highlights its significance in cancer (Bottazzi et al., 1983). From pre-cancerous stages to full-blown tumors, chemokines play a key role. They influence tumor growth, invasion, and metastasis by promoting the formation of blood vessels (angiogenesis), a crucial factor for tumor development. This underlines the importance of chemokines and their receptor networks as potential targets for controlling tumor growth, especially during early stages (Strieter et al., 2004). Chemokines are signaling molecules best known for directing the movement of immune cells (leukocytes). They achieve this by influencing the molecules on cell surfaces (adhesion molecules) and the surrounding matrix (extracellular matrix), allowing cells to detach and migrate (Le et al., 2004). Chemokine receptors, a type of protein that spans the cell membrane seven times, play a critical role in regulating immune responses. There are about 50 known chemokines that can

bind to 18 different chemokine receptors in humans (Kiefer & Siekmann, 2011). A specific group of chemokine receptors acts like scavengers, clearing inflammatory chemokines and reducing inflammation. These were previously called atypical chemokine receptors and included Duffy antigen receptors for chemokines (DARC), Decoy receptor 6 (D6), and others. A newer naming system has been adopted: DARC is now ACKR1, D6 is ACKR2, and so on (Feng et al., 2009; Nibbs & Graham, 2013). Another receptor, ACKR6 (Nir1), is still being studied for its similarities to the ACKR family. It can bind to CCL18, a chemokine released by tumor-associated macrophages (TAMs), and is believed to play a role in breast cancer metastasis. While the exact mechanism is unclear, this interaction seems to be important in cancer spread by promoting a cellular change called epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) through a specific signaling pathway (Zhang et al., 2017). Certain ACKRs, like ACKR1 and ACKR2, act as "silent decoy receptors." These receptors capture and break down chemokines, essentially neutralizing their effects (Galzi et al., 2010). ACKRs like ACKR1 and ACKR2 are similar to other cell receptors but lack the ability to trigger cellular responses. This is because they have a specific change in their protein structure (**DRYLAIV** motif to **DKYLEIV** amino acid sequence D6 or decoy receptor) within a loop located inside the cell membrane. Due to this change, they cannot connect with a molecule called G-protein, which is essential for triggering signals inside the cell. Despite lacking signaling ability, these ACKRs excel at capturing a wide variety of chemokines. Once bound, they engulf the chemokines in compartments within the cell (endocytic vesicles) where enzymes (lysosomal activity) break down the

chemokines. Finally, the ACKRs themselves are recycled back to the cell surface. Through this process, these ACKRs effectively regulate the concentration and availability of chemokines in the local environment of inflamed tissues (Feng et al., 2009). Scientists have investigated the role of several ACKR proteins (ACKR1, ACKR2, ACKR3, and ACKR4) in cancer. Among these, ACKR1 and ACKR2 act as defence mechanisms against cancer metastasis (the spread of cancer cells) throughout the body. Specifically, ACKR1 might be involved in preventing cancer cells from entering the bloodstream, while ACKR2 might play a role in blocking their spread to lymph nodes (Shen et al., 2006).

In contrast to the chemokine receptor CXCR4, which fuels breast cancer cell growth by activating a specific pathway (p38 MAPK) with the help of a molecule called beta-arrestin (Sun et al., 2002), ACKR2 (also known as decoy receptor 6 or D6) acts as a brake on cancer spread to lymph nodes. Interestingly, lower levels of ACKR2 are associated with more advanced stages of breast cancer, suggesting its potential as a tumour suppressor. However, the exact signalling pathway involved in ACKR2's anti-cancer effects remains under investigation (Wu FY et al., 2008). ACKR1 stands out as a unique chemokine receptor. It can capture inflammatory signalling molecules (ligands) from a wider range than any other receptor, binding to over 20 chemokines from both the CC and CXC families (Lague et al., 2013). Interestingly, ACKR1 is found on the lining of blood vessels in specific areas of lymph nodes (Graham et al., 2012). Some pre-clinical studies suggest that ACKR1 might play a protective role in breast cancer. Its overexpression has been observed in some cases, and lower levels might be an

early indicator of the disease (Wang et al., 2006; Zeng et al., 2011; Zang et al., 2014). However, more research is needed to fully understand its function in cancer. D6, also known as ACKR2, is a receptor found in various tissues like the placenta, lymphatic vessel linings (endothelial cells), and immune cells. It acts like a magnet, attracting a wide range of inflammatory chemokines (CCL2, 3L1, 4, 5, 7, 8, 11-14, and 22) with a weaker affinity for CCL17 (Hajrasovilha et al., 2013). Once ACKR2 binds to a chemokine, it engulfs it into the cell. After the chemokine is broken down within the cell, ACKR2 itself gets recycled back to the cell surface, possibly with the help of a molecule called beta-arrestin (Borroni et al, 2013). Interestingly, higher levels of ACKR2 are associated with lower risks of lymph node metastasis in breast cancer patients, suggesting a protective role. This receptor is also found in breast cancer cells themselves, but it's unclear if healthy breast cells (epithelial cells) have ACKR2 as well (Wu et al.,2008; Chew et al, 2013). As breast cancer progresses, studies have shown a link between a decrease in ACKR2, ACKR1, and ACKR4 levels and a worse prognosis (Zeng et al., 2011; Zeng et al., 2014). ACKR4, also known as CCRC1 or CCX-CKR, acts like a janitor for specific chemokines involved in maintaining balance (homeostatic chemokines) like CCL19, CCL21, and CCL25. It can also weakly bind to CXCL13 (Comerford et al.,2007). Similar to ACKR2, it engulfs these chemokines with the help of a molecule called beta-arrestin, breaks them down inside the cell, and becomes temporarily inactive (desensitized) (Catusse et al., 2010). While it's unclear if ACKR4 triggers any cellular signals (Watts et al., 2013), studies suggest a complex role. In lab experiments, high levels of ACKR4 in aggressive breast

cancer cells (MDA-MB-231) slowed their growth. However, in animal models, these cells still formed tumors. Interestingly, lower levels of ACKR4 in breast cancer patients seem to be associated with a poorer outcome (Langenes et al., 2013). Studies have shown that when ACKR4 (also known as CCX-CKR) is missing, the levels of chemokines CCL19 and CCL21 increase in lymph nodes (Comerford et al, 2013). In mice without ACKR4, this leads to problems with immune cell (dendritic cell) movement to the lymph nodes, ultimately weakening the immune response (Comerford et al., 2010).

Figure 5.1 Diagram showing D6/ACKR2 as chemokine scavenger (acts like a sponge) by internalising ligand in an endocytic vesicle that undergoes degradation and further decoy receptor is recirculated to plasma membrane. ACKR2 is highly promiscuous receptor which can bind to several CC chemokines (CCL2, CCL3, CCL4, CCL5, CCL7, CCL8, CCL11, CCL13, CCL14, CCL17 & CCL22) (Figure is adapted from Sarmad P et al., 2016).

CXCR7 was previously thought to be a signaling receptor, activating pathways like MAPKs or Akt through a molecule called beta-arrestin. However, recent research suggests it might be better classified as an ACKR. This is because studies have shown that while CXCR7 can bind to its ligand CXCL12, it doesn't trigger typical intracellular signals itself. Interestingly, CXCR7 can interact with another receptor, CXCR4, by forming a combined structure called a heterodimer, potentially influencing CXCR4's function (Hartmann et al., 2008; Levoe et al., 2009).

Despite its lack of traditional signaling, CXCR7 expression in breast cancer cells seems to be important for their growth and survival (Miao et al., 2007). In contrast, ACKR3 (previously known as CXCR7) appears to promote cancer cell growth in MCF-7 cells by activating a specific pathway (Erk1/2) and preventing cell death (apoptosis) (Gao et al., 2015). Chemokine receptors are a type of protein embedded in cell membranes called G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs). When chemokines bind to these receptors, they trigger a series of cellular responses within seconds to minutes. These responses involve the movement of calcium ions inside the cell, activation of multiple pathways like MAPK, PLC, PI3K, RAS, and NF- κ B, and ultimately influence gene expression (reviewed by Comerford et al., 2011). Interestingly, oestrogen (E2), a female sex hormone, can also signal through these rapid, non-genomic pathways. Specific regions of the endoplasmic reticulum, a network of membranes within the cell, seem to be involved in this process. These ER sites collaborate with various molecules like MAPK, PI3K, and others to control gene expression within a short timeframe (reviewed by Bjornstorm & Sjoberg et al, 2005).

Recent research suggests a new twist: oestrogen can also bind to a specific G protein-coupled receptor on the cell surface, called the membrane E2 receptor. This receptor has a unique feature – it gets taken up inside the cell upon activation by estrogen, following a pathway independent of clathrin and caveolin, which are usually involved in internalization (Benten et al., 2001). Furthermore, studies in the goat uterus suggest that inactive oestrogen receptors (naER) associated with GPCRs might be internalized upon hormone binding. This process seems to involve tyrosine kinases (Karthikeyan & Thampan, 1996; Anuradha et al, 1994).

During mammary gland development, both before and after birth, macrophages play a crucial role in shaping the branching structure. These immune cells are attracted by high levels of inflammatory CC-chemokines. Interestingly, a receptor called ACKR2 acts like a scavenger, removing these very chemokines. The expression of ACKR2 itself changes throughout mammary gland development. Because of this, researchers believe ACKR2 plays a key role in regulating the branching process specifically during the postnatal stage (Wilson et al., 2017).

Sex hormones, like oestrogen and progesterone, can directly or indirectly influence the levels of various chemokines throughout the menstrual cycle (Dominguez et al., 2003; Zhang et al., 2000; DeLoia et al., 2000). This close coordination between the immune system and hormonal changes is essential for the lining of the uterus (endometrium) to become receptive for a successful pregnancy. These interactions play a role in processes like blood vessel formation (angiogenesis), the invasion of the uterus by the fertilized egg (trophoblast invasion), and the formation of the placenta (placentation) (Park et al., 2011).

Estrogen, particularly E2 (estradiol), is a major factor contributing to breast cancer. It can influence cancer cells through oestrogen receptors located either inside the cytoplasm (cell fluid) or on the cell membrane. These receptors can trigger signaling pathways, either requiring oestrogen (ligand-dependent) or not (ligand-independent), to control the activity of genes involved in cancer development (Sreeja & Thanpan, 2003). When oestrogen binds to the membrane-associated oestrogen receptor, it activates a specific pathway called MAPK/ERK, which is mainly triggered by the activation of G proteins (Razandi et al., 1999).

Since oestrogen (E2) is a major factor in breast cancer development, researchers have investigated how hormones influence a gene called ACKR3. Studies have shown that ACKR3 expression may affect how ER-positive breast cancer cells (such as the MCF-7 cell line) respond to hormonal therapy (Ribas et al., 2014). This suggests a potential role for ACKR3 in endocrine resistance, a condition where cancer cells no longer respond to hormone-based treatments.

Novel Research on Oestrogen and ACKR Expression in Breast Cancer

This research project investigates a new area of breast cancer biology. It aims to understand how oestrogen (E2) influences the expression of specific molecules called ACKRs (atypical chemokine receptors) in hormone-dependent MCF-7 breast cancer cells.

ACKRs are known to play a critical role in regulating tumor development and spread. Since they can act as scavengers for inflammatory molecules, they are considered potential targets for anti-inflammatory and immune therapies. Studies

suggest that ACKRs (particularly ACKR1 and ACKR2) might influence breast cancer cell invasion (Chew et al., 2013).

Oestrogen levels are often elevated in breast tumors due to production by surrounding stromal cells. Therefore, this research will explore how physiological levels of E2 affect the expression of ACKR2, specifically, in MCF-7 cells.

Hypothesis: Higher E2 levels will modulate the expression of ACKR2 in MCF-7 cells (in vitro study). **Aim:** To determine the effect of E2 on ACKR gene expression in MCF-7 cells. **Objectives:**

1. Characterize ACKR expression (ACKR1, ACKR2 & ACKR3, ACKR4) in MCF-7 cells.
2. Use RT-qPCR to measure the relative gene expression of ACKRs in MCF-7 cells.

5.2 Methods

5.2.1 E2 Stimulation of MCF-7 Cells

MCF-7 cells were prepared and stimulated with higher concentrations of E2 as described in section 4.2.2. This generated E2-stimulated samples for subsequent analysis of ACKRs gene expression.

5.2.2 Characterization of ACKR Expression by Gradient PCR

To determine the optimal amplification conditions for each ACKR gene (ACKR1, ACKR2, ACKR3, ACKR4), gPCR was performed. Specific primers were used to target each ACKR genes. Primers for ACKR2 were obtained from a published study by Wu et al. (2008). Primers for ACKR1, ACKR3 and ACKR4 were designed for this study refer to table 5.3 (using similar approach used in section 3.2.3.7 b).

5.2.3 Design of ACKR Primers for qPCR

a. *In-silico* Analysis of ACKR Genes:

Public databases such as the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) were used to identify potential isoforms of ACKR genes (ACKR1, ACKR3, ACKR4, and ACKR6). The coding sequences (CDS) of these isoforms were retrieved and aligned using an online multiple sequence alignment tool like "Multialign" to assess sequence similarity.

Table 5.1 Details of ACKR(s) nucleotide variants and protein isoform sourced from NCBI.

ACKR Gene Homo sapiens	Nucleotide sequence ID	Protein sequence ID	CDS amino acid	Tissue type	Reference
Atypical chemokine receptor 1 (Duffy blood group)	NM_001122951.2	NP_001116423.1	338 a.a	Bone marrow	(Chaudhuri et al., 1993)
	NM_002036.3	NP_002027.2	336 a.a	Placenta	(Wakamatsu et al., 2007; Isogai et al., 2007)
Atypical chemokine receptor 2	NM_001296.4	NP_001287.2	384 a.a	Placenta	(Strausberg et al., 2002)
Atypical chemokine receptor 3	NM_020311.2	NP_064707.1	362 a.a	Testes	(Martin et al., 2006)
Atypical chemokine receptor 4	NM_016557.3	NP_057641.1	350 a.a	Heart	(Khoja H et al., 2000)
	NM_178445.2	NP_848540.1			
PITPNM family member 3 (PITPNM3)	NM_031220.3	NP_112497.2 membrane-associated phosphatidylinositol transfer protein 3 isoform 1	974 a.a	Brain, hippocampus	(Strausberg et al., 2002)
	NM_001165966.1	NP_001159438.1 membrane-associated phosphatidylinositol transfer protein 3 isoform 2	938 a.a	Pooled human melanocyte, fetal heart, and pregnant uterus	

b. Primer Design Strategy:

Based on the *in-silico* analysis: Primers for ACKR1, ACKR3, ACKR4 were designed from mRNA exon-exon spanning region, refer to table 5.2. This approach helps ensure amplification of specific transcripts and minimizes amplification of genomic DNA. The primer design process followed a similar strategy as described in section 3.2.3.7 (b) for ER β primers.

Table 5.2 Primer details for ACKR(s) type to bring in use for future experimental plan.

ACKR type	Primer sequence	Location on CDS	Product size
ACKR 1	Forward 5'-AGA CTA TGG TGC CAA CCT-3' Reverse 5'- AAG ACG GGC ACC ACA ATG CTG AA -3'	FWD 123-140 REV 349-335	227 bp
ACKR2	Forward 5'- CCT GCT CCT TGC TAC CAT AGT ATG G -3' Reverse 5'-CAC CAA GAC ACA ACC AAT ACG GGA G-3'	FWD 483-508 REV 714-690	232 bp
ACKR3	Forward 5'- AAA AGC GTC CTG CTC TAC AC- 3' Reverse 5'- AGA CTG GGA TGG TGA GGA CAA -3'	FWD 118-138 REV 298-278	200 bp
ACKR 4	Forward 5'-TGG ATG GCT GCC ATC TTG-3' Reverse 5'-CTT CAT GAG TGT CCT TGC TGT G-3'	FWD Primer 484-501 REV Primer 687-666	203 bp

c. ACKR Primers:

Primer sequences for ACKR2 were obtained from the published qPCR study by Wu et al. (2008) (listed in references). This including rest of the in house ACKR gene primers are included in the table 5.3.

Table 5.3 Details of primers for ACKRs

Gene	Primers	NCBI Seq. no.	Product size	Reference
ACKR1	<p>FWD 5'-AGA CTA TGG TGC CAA CCT-3'</p> <p>REV 5'-AAG ACG GGC ACC ACA ATG CTG AA-3'</p>	<p>NM_001122951.2</p> <p>NM_002036.3</p>	227 bp	This study
ACKR2	<p>FWD 5'- CCT GCT CCT TGC TAC CAT AGT ATG G -3'</p> <p>REV 5'-CAC CAA GAC ACA ACC AAT ACG GGA G-3'</p>	NM_001296.4	232 bp	Wu et.al.,2008
ACKR3	<p>FWD 5'- AAA AGC GTC CTG CTC TAC AC-3'</p> <p>REV 5'- AGA CTG GGA TGG TGA GGA CAA -3'</p>	NM_020311.2	199 bp	This study
ACKR4	<p>FWD 5'-TGG ATG GCT GCC ATC TTG-3'</p> <p>REV 5'-CTT CAT GAG TGT CCT TGC TGT G-3'</p>	<p>NM_0.16557.3</p> <p>NM_178445.2</p>	203 bp	This study

5.2.4 Gradient PCR for ACKR Primer Optimization

a. Primer Details:

The ACKR primer sequences used for this experiment are listed in Table 5.3. These primers were designed to characterize the expression of ACKR genes (ACKR1, ACKR2, ACKR3 and ACKR4) in MCF-7 cells.

b. Sample and PCR Conditions:

Un-treated E2 sample from MCF-7 cell were used as the cDNA template for gPCR. The PCR reaction conditions were optimized as described in section 3.2.3.5. This optimization step aimed to confirm mRNA expression & the annealing temperature that results in the amplification of a single band of the expected size for target ACKR genes.

c. Gel Electrophoresis Analysis:

Following gradient PCR, the amplified products were separated on a 1.2% agarose gel using electrophoresis. This procedure followed the protocol outlined in section 3.2.3.5. The gel was then visualized using a UV trans-illuminator to identify the presence and size of the PCR products.

Selection annealing temperature for qPCR:

The annealing temperature that yielded a single, clear band of the expected size for each ACKR gene was chosen for subsequent qPCR experiments aimed at measuring relative gene expression of ACKR gene in E2 treatment samples.

5.2.5 qPCR ACKR Relative Gene Expression

a. Selection of Genes for qPCR:

Based on the results from gPCR (section 5.2.4), primers for ACKR2, ACKR3 and ACKR4 were chosen for further analysis using quantitative PCR (qPCR). These primers produced visible bands of the expected size, indicating successful amplification of the target genes in MCF-7 cells.

b. qPCR Reagents and Master Mix:

The qScript™ One-Step SYBR® Green qRT-PCR Kit with ROX (VRW Life Science, UK) was used for this experiment. The kit included reagents such as One-Step Master Mix with ROX (2X) and nuclease-free water.

c. Master Mix Preparation and Sample Loading:

The qPCR master mix was prepared in batches for three biological replicates of E2-stimulated samples, refer to the table 5.4.

Table 5.4 Reagents measure per reaction in Syber green qPCR mix

Reagents	Amount (µL) per reaction
One-Step-Master Mix ROX (2x)	12.5 (1X)
Primer Fwd (50 nM)	0.25
Primer Rev (50 nM)	0.25
Nuclease free water	11
cDNA template /water control	1
Total Volume	25

Each replicate included negative controls: water control and a no-reverse transcriptase (NTC) control. The master mix was designed for amplification of ACKR2, ACKR3, and ACKR4. The qPCR was performed in 96-well plates. Each sample was run in duplicate (n=2) for better accuracy. Briefly, 24 µL of qPCR master mix was added to each well, followed by 1 µL of cDNA sample or negative

control (water or NTC). The plate was then centrifuged at 500 x g for 3 minutes using a microplate centrifuge to eliminate any air bubbles trapped in the wells.

d. Cycling Conditions and Detection:

The qPCR plate was loaded into the StepOnePlus system (Applied Biosystems) and the program was run according to the manufacturer's instructions. The program included cycles of reverse transcription, denaturation, annealing, and extension to achieve amplification of the target genes (as per section 3.2.3.6 b).

e. Data Analysis:

The comparative $\Delta\Delta Cq$ method was used to analyze the relative gene expression of ACKR2 and ACKR3 in E2-stimulated samples. TOP1 was chosen as the endogenous control gene based on its stable expression observed in the RNA optimization experiment (refer to section 3.2.3.6 c). No treatment sample was used as the calibrator for comparison with E2-treatment with respective vehicle control samples.

f. Calculation of Fold Change:

The following steps were followed to calculate the fold change in gene expression for each replicate:

Obtained the mean Cq values for the endogenous control (18S rRNA) and target genes (ACKR2, ACKR3, ACKR4) from the three experimental runs (n=3).

Calculated ΔCq for each sample: $\Delta Cq = (\text{mean Cq of target gene}) - (\text{mean Cq of TOP1})$.

Determined the average ΔCq and standard deviation (SD) for each biological replicate (R1, R2, R3).

Calculated $\Delta\Delta Cq$ for replicates: $\Delta\Delta Cq = (\text{average } \Delta Cq \text{ for treated sample}) - (\text{average } \Delta Cq \text{ for untreated sample})$.

Calculated the fold change for each replicate using the formula: $2^{-\Delta\Delta Cq}$.

Reported the mean fold change and standard deviation (SD) across all replicates.

5.3 Result

5.3.1 Gradient PCR Optimization of ACKR Primers

gPCR was performed to optimize the annealing temperature for primers targeting ACKR genes (ACKR1, ACKR2, ACKR3 and ACKR4) in MCF-7 cells (Table 5.3). This step aimed to ensure specific and efficient amplification during subsequent qPCR experiments.

Figure 5.2: Gradient PCR gel image for gene primers for ACKR2, ACKR3 & ACKR4 and absence of ACKR 1 and ACKR6 mRNA expression on gel leading 1 μ L of cDNA (0.2 μ g) sample.

a. mRNA expression from qPCR

No treatment sample from MCF-7 was used for gradient PCR. The results showed:

Clear bands corresponding to the expected amplicon sizes were observed for ACKR2 (232 bp), ACKR3 (199 bp), and ACKR4 (200 bp) on the agarose gel (visualized against a 50 bp DNA ladder). This indicates mRNA expression of these genes in the untreated MCF-7 cells. No bands were detected for ACKR1 primers suggesting undetectable mRNA expression.

b. Optimal Annealing Temperature:

An annealing temperature of 61°C yielded the best results for amplification of ACKR2, ACKR3, and ACKR4. This temperature will be used for subsequent qPCR experiments.

5.3.3 Relative Gene Expression of ACKR2, ACKR3 & ACKR4 using $\Delta\Delta Cq$ Method

The comparative $\Delta\Delta Cq$ method was used to analyze the relative gene expression of ACKR2, ACKR3 and ACKR4 using E2 treatment sample. This analysis involved three biological replicates (R1, R2, and R3) run in duplicate (n=2). Mean Cq values were calculated for each gene (ACKR2, ACKR3, ACKR4 and the endogenous control, TOP1) across all replicates. The $\Delta\Delta Cq$ method was then employed to determine the fold change in gene expression in E2 treatment samples, refer to annexure III A-F. The results are presented in figure 5.3, 5.4 & 5.5. These graphs likely depict the fold change in expression of ACKR2 and ACKR3 relative to the untreated control following E2 stimulation. Statistical analysis was done using non-parametric Mann-Whitney's U-test (Table 5.5, 5.6 & 5.7) to find significance within

the relative gene expression of ACKR genes at 6H & 18H time-point exposure to higher concentration of E2.

a. ACKR2 Gene Expression at 6H

b. ACKR2 Gene Expression at 18H

Figure 5.3 Above graph is representation of $2^{-\Delta\Delta Cq}$ or mean fold value for ACKR2 target gene normalized with TOP1 gene using three biological repeats of E2 treatment experiment runs a. 6H & b. 18H time point. Data analysis achieved using non-parametric statistical tool Mann-Whitney's U-test (refer to table 5.5) significance in data was explored. For significant difference p value symbol * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.005$, *** $p < 0.0005$ is defined.

Table 5.5 Mann-Whitney's U-test data for ACKR2 (refer to Supplementary table 2) target gene normalised against TOP1 endogenous control.

ACKR2 Mann-Whitney: Control 6H, E2 Treatment 6H							
Sample	N	Median	Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence	W-Value	P-Value
Control 6H	12	1.23128	0.131102	(-0.370776, 0.769851)	95.72%	136.00	0.804
E2 Treatment 6H	9	0.90322					
ACKR2 Mann-Whitney: Control 18H, E2 Treatment 18H							
Sample	N	Median	Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence	W-Value	P-Value
Control 18H	12	0.917534	0.314647	(0.126236, 0.527902)	95.72%	171.00	0.006
E2 Treatment 18H	9	0.577239					

a. ACKR3 Gene Expression at 6H

b. ACKR3 Gene Expression at 18H

Figure 5.4 Above graph is representation of $2^{-\Delta\Delta Cq}$ or mean fold value for ACKR3 target gene normalized with TOP1 gene using three biological repeats of E2 treatment experiment runs a. 6H & b. 18H time point. Data analysis achieved using non-parametric statistical tool Mann-Whitney's U-test (table 5.6, below) significance in data was explored. For significant difference p value symbol * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.005$, *** $p < 0.0005$ is defined.

Table 5.6 Mann-Whitney's U-test data for ACKR3 (refer to Supplementary table 2) target gene normalised against TOP1 endogenous control.

ACKR3 Mann-Whitney: Control 6H, E2 Treatment 6H							
Sample	N	Median	Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence	W-Value	P-Value
Control 6H	12	1.04032	0.211825	(-0.0286897, 0.505688)	95.72%	153.00	0.145
E2 Treatment 6H	9	0.78328					
ACKR3 Mann-Whitney: Control 18H, E2 Treatment 18H							
Sample	N	Median	Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence	W-Value	P-Value
Control 18H	12	1.08025	0.559590	(0.355884, 1.13156)	95.77%	124.00	0.001
E2 Treatment 18H	9	0.53342					

a. ACKR4 Gene Expression at 6H

b. ACKR4 Gene Expression at 18H

Figure 5.5 Above graph is representation of $2^{-\Delta\Delta Cq}$ or mean fold value for ACKR4 target gene normalized with TOP1 gene using three biological repeats of E2 treatment experiment runs a. 6H & b. 18H time point. Data analysis achieved using non-parametric statistical tool Mann-Whitney's U-test (table 5.7, below) significance in data was explored. For significant difference p value symbol * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.005$, *** $p < 0.0005$ is defined.

Table 5.7 Mann-Whitney's U-test data for ACKR4 (refer to Supplementary table 2) target gene normalised against TOP1 endogenous control.

ACKR4 Mann-Whitney: Control 6H, E2 Treatment 6H							
Sample	N	Median	Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence	W-Value	P-Value
Control 6H	12	0.901825	0.0879857	(-0.108645, 0.489312)	95.72%	139.00	0.644
E2 Treatment 6H	9	0.965578					
ACKR4 Mann-Whitney: Control 18H, E2 Treatment 18H							
Sample	N	Median	Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence	W-Value	P-Value
Control 18H	12	1.05070	0.290245	(0.0064575, 0.622638)	95.72%	161.00	0.043
E2 Treatment 18H	9	0.70434					

Chapter 6

Discussion

6.0 Discussion

In chapter 1, literature review covers a broad range of topics related to estrogen, including its forms, production, functions in various systems, and signaling pathways and effectively communicate the understanding of the complex relationship between estrogen, inflammation, and ACKRs in breast cancer.

In chapter 2, aim of research project is explained as it will investigate the effects of high oestradiol (E2) levels on gene expression in MCF-7 breast cancer cells. Specifically, it focuses on how E2 might influence the expression of two types of genes:

1. **Oestrogen receptors (ERs):** These are well-established players in breast cancer development, and the study wants to see if E2 levels affect their expression.
2. **Atypical chemokine receptors (ACKRs):** These are less explored in breast cancer, and the research aims to see if E2 modulates their gene expression and potentially their role in the disease.

MCF-7 cells and real-time qPCR has been chosen to measure relative gene expression changes under varying E2 concentrations. As an objective it is deemed to determine a reliable reference gene for accurate data analysis.

In chapter 3, the RT-qPCR assay method has been developed by integrating methods used for RNA isolation, cDNA synthesis, primer optimization, and real-time PCR (qPCR) analysis. MCF-7 breast cancer cells were used and maintained in DMEM:F12 media with 10% FBS but in the experimental design FBS was not

included. RNA was extracted from samples and assessed using a Nanodrop for purity (A260/A280 ratio) and integrity (28S/18S band intensity on agarose gel). DNase I treatment was performed to remove DNA contamination before cDNA synthesis. cDNA was synthesized from the purified RNA. Gradient PCR was used to optimize the annealing temperature for primers targeting housekeeping genes (HKGs) and target genes (ER α , ER β). TOP1 was revised as the most stable reference gene for normalization based on low standard deviation (SD) in ΔCq values in stimulated samples over 18S rRNA. qPCR was performed on cDNA samples using optimized primers for ER α , ER β _iso (a newly designed primer set for ER β gene), and TOP1. PCR efficiency was checked for all primers, although ER β _iso showed lower efficiency due to potentially low abundance. The $\Delta\Delta Cq$ method was used to analyze the relative gene expression of ER α and ER β _iso at different time points (6H, 12H, 24H, and 48H) in MCF-7 cells. TOP1 was selected as endogenous control for qPCR analysis of the target genes. ER α and ER β expression did not change significantly with culturing time in MCF-7 cells. The newly designed ER β _iso primer set was considered ideal for future studies.

In chapter 4, the research work explores the effects of E2 on MCF-7 cell proliferation and ER gene expression. Previous studies have shown E2 can stimulate MCF-7 cell proliferation at various concentrations and culturing conditions (using charcoal-stripped FBS, different media, etc.). This study investigates the effects of E2 on MCF-7 cells grown consistently in 10% FBS using DMEM:F12 media. The study finds that $\leq 1\%$ DMSO use in E2 working stock

solution is ideal for experimental use to study effect of E2 and higher concentration of DMSO causes viability decline in MCF-7 cells at 6H & 18H exposure time-points. DMEM:F12 media (without FBS) was used in this experimental design of studying the effect of higher E2 levels in MFC-7.ER α and ER β gene expression showed a significant down-regulation of gene with higher E2 concentration compared to control/vehicle control (\leq 1% DMSO v/v) at 18H time point.

In chapter 5, the research work describes the findings of a study investigating the effects of E2 on the expression of ACKR genes in in-vitro MCF-7 breast cancer cells. Primers for ACKR1 and ACKR6 did not amplify any product, suggesting minimal or undetectable expression of these genes in MCF-7 cells. Primers for ACKR2, ACKR3, and ACKR4 successfully amplified products, indicating their expression in MCF-7 cells. The study investigated whether E2 levels can modulate the expression of ACKR genes in MCF-7 cells. Down-regulation of ACKR2, ACKR3, and ACKR4 gene expression showed a significant down-regulation of gene with higher E2 concentration compared to control/vehicle control (\leq 1% DMSO v/v) at 18H time point. No significant change in expression at 6h for these genes. Overall, more qPCR replicates are needed to confirm the fold change data due to variation in initial RNA yield. Culturing MCF-7 cells in 2D with 10% FBS may not fully mimic the complex tumor microenvironment. Studying cells in a 3D model with stromal factors and immune mediators might provide a clearer picture of hormone effects on cancer cell behavior. Overall, the discussion effectively presents the main findings on E2's effects on ACKR2, ACKR3, and ACKR4 expression in MCF-7 cells at transcriptional (mRNA) level.

7.0 References

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Supplementary Figure 1. Amplification & Melting curves from qPCR for each HKGs using cell densities & time point samples:

a) 18S rRNA; b) HPRT1; c) TBP & d) TOP1

(a) 18S rRNA

(b)HPRT1

(c)TBP

(d) TOP1

Supplementary Figure 2. In-silico 'Multialign' analysis result for the published ERβ1 and ERβ2/cx primers against the coding domain sequence of ESR2 variants ERβ1 & ERβ2/cx gene.

Fwd. primer (which is common for ERβ1 & ERβ2/cx published primer) in red box aligns completely from location 1780bp-1799bp while rev. primer for ERβ2/cx shown in green boxes does shows low consensus and do not align fully.

Supplementary Figure 3. In-silico 'Multialign' analysis result for the new ER β iso primer set FWD/Rev in red box aligned to the coding domain sequence of all known ESR2 gene variants.

Supplementary Table 1. Statistical Analysis ER α & ER β relative gene expression data

ER ALPHA 6H

Mann-Whitney: Control 6H, E2 Treatment 6H

Method

η_1 : median of Control 6H

η_2 : median of E2 Treatment 6H

Difference: $\eta_1 - \eta_2$

Descriptive Statistics

	Sample	N	Median
Control 6H	12		1.04032
E2 Treatment 6H	9		0.78328

Estimation for Difference

Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence
0.211825	(-0.0286897, 0.505688)	95.72%

Test

Null hypothesis $H_0 : \eta_1 - \eta_2 = 0$

Alternative hypothesis $H_1 : \eta_1 - \eta_2 \neq 0$

W-Value	P-Value
153.00	0.145

ERALPHA 18 H

Mann-Whitney: Control 18H, E2 Treatment 18H

Method

η_1 : median of Control 18H

η_2 : median of E2 Treatment 18H

Difference: $\eta_1 - \eta_2$

Descriptive Statistics

	Sample	N	Median
Control 18H	12		0.924957
E2 Treatment 18H	9		0.588136

Estimation for Difference

Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence
0.403258	(0.140038, 0.682240)	95.72%

Test

Null hypothesis $H_0 : \eta_1 - \eta_2 = 0$

Alternative hypothesis $H_1 : \eta_1 - \eta_2 \neq 0$

Method	W-Value	P-Value
Not adjusted for ties	175.00	0.003
Adjusted for ties	175.00	0.003

ER BETA 6H

Mann-Whitney: Control 6H, E2 Treatment 6H

Method

η_1 : median of Control 6H
 η_2 : median of E2 Treatment 6H
Difference: $\eta_1 - \eta_2$

Descriptive Statistics

Sample	N	Median
Control 6H	12	1.16005
E2 Treatment 6H	9	0.88797

Estimation for Difference

Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence
0.157932	(-0.293570, 0.740151)	95.72%

Test

Null hypothesis $H_0 : \eta_1 - \eta_2 = 0$
Alternative hypothesis $H_1 : \eta_1 - \eta_2 \neq 0$

W-Value	P-Value
143.00	0.456

ER BETA 18H

Mann-Whitney: Control 18H, E2 Treatment 18H

Method

η_1 : median of Control 18H
 η_2 : median of E2 Treatment 18H
Difference: $\eta_1 - \eta_2$

Descriptive Statistics

Sample	N	Median
Control 18H	12	0.816460
E2 Treatment 18H	9	0.613418

Estimation for Difference

Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence
0.237673	(0.0201395, 0.566105)	95.72%

Test

Null hypothesis $H_0 : \eta_1 - \eta_2 = 0$
Alternative hypothesis $H_1 : \eta_1 - \eta_2 \neq 0$

W-Value	P-Value
164.00	0.025

Supplementary Table 2. Statistical Analysis ACKR2, ACKR3 & ACKR4 relative gene expression data

ACKR2 6H

Mann-Whitney: Control 6H, E2 Treatment 6H

Method

η_1 : median of Control 6H
 η_2 : median of E2 Treatment 6H
 Difference: $\eta_1 - \eta_2$

Descriptive Statistics

	Sample	N	Median
Control 6H	12		1.23128
E2 Treatment 6H	9		0.90322

Estimation for Difference

Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence
0.131102	(-0.370776, 0.769851)	95.72%

Test

Null hypothesis $H_0: \eta_1 - \eta_2 = 0$
 Alternative hypothesis $H_1: \eta_1 - \eta_2 \neq 0$

W-Value	P-Value
136.00	0.804

ACKR2 18H

Mann-Whitney: Control 18H, E2 Treatment 18H

Method

η_1 : median of Control 18H
 η_2 : median of E2 Treatment 18H
 Difference: $\eta_1 - \eta_2$

Descriptive Statistics

	Sample	N	Median
Control 18H	12		0.917534
E2 Treatment 18H	9		0.577239

Estimation for Difference

Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence
0.314647	(0.126236, 0.527902)	95.72%

Test

Null hypothesis $H_0: \eta_1 - \eta_2 = 0$
 Alternative hypothesis $H_1: \eta_1 - \eta_2 \neq 0$

Method	W-Value	P-Value
Not adjusted for ties	171.00	0.006
Adjusted for ties	171.00	0.006

ACKR3 6H

Mann-Whitney: Control 6H, E2 Treatment 6H

Method

η_1 : median of Control 6H

η_2 : median of E2 Treatment 6H

Difference: $\eta_1 - \eta_2$

Descriptive Statistics

	Sample	N	Median
Control 6H	12		1.04032
E2 Treatment 6H	9		0.78328

Estimation for Difference

Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence
0.211825	(-0.0286897, 0.505688)	95.72%

Test

Null hypothesis $H_0: \eta_1 - \eta_2 = 0$

Alternative hypothesis $H_1: \eta_1 - \eta_2 \neq 0$

W-Value	P-Value
153.00	0.145

ACKR3 18H

Mann-Whitney: Control 18H, E2 Treatment 18H

Method

η_1 : median of Control 18H

η_2 : median of E2 Treatment 18H

Difference: $\eta_1 - \eta_2$

Descriptive Statistics

	Sample	N	Median
Control 18H	9		1.08025
E2 Treatment 18H	9		0.53342

Estimation for Difference

Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence
0.559590	(0.355884, 1.13156)	95.77%

Test

Null hypothesis $H_0: \eta_1 - \eta_2 = 0$

Alternative hypothesis $H_1: \eta_1 - \eta_2 \neq 0$

Method	W-Value	P-Value
Not adjusted for ties	124.00	0.001
Adjusted for ties	124.00	0.001

ACKR4 6H

Mann-Whitney: Control 6H, E2 Treatment 6H

Method

η_1 : median of Control 6H

η_2 : median of E2 Treatment 6H

Difference: $\eta_1 - \eta_2$

Descriptive Statistics

	Sample	N	Median
Control 6H	12		0.901825
E2 Treatment 6H	9		0.965578

Estimation for Difference

Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence
0.0879857	(-0.108645, 0.489312)	95.72%

Test

Null hypothesis $H_0: \eta_1 - \eta_2 = 0$

Alternative hypothesis $H_1: \eta_1 - \eta_2 \neq 0$

Method	W-Value	P-Value
Not adjusted for ties	139.00	0.644
Adjusted for ties	139.00	0.644

ACKR4 18H

Mann-Whitney: Control 18H, E2 Treatment 18H

Method

η_1 : median of Control 18H

η_2 : median of E2 Treatment 18H

Difference: $\eta_1 - \eta_2$

Descriptive Statistics

	Sample	N	Median
Control 18H	12		1.05070
E2 Treatment 18H	9		0.70434

Estimation for Difference

Difference	CI for Difference	Achieved Confidence
0.290245	(0.0064575, 0.622638)	95.72%

Test

Null hypothesis $H_0: \eta_1 - \eta_2 = 0$

Alternative hypothesis $H_1: \eta_1 - \eta_2 \neq 0$

Method	W-Value	P-Value
Not adjusted for ties	161.00	0.043
Adjusted for ties	161.00	0.043

ANNEXURE I

A. Ranking HKGs				
SD with Cq value for HKG's densities & time point samples				Cell
Sample Name	18s rRNA (1/100 dil)	TOP1	TBP	HPRT1
6H_W2 Run1	19.96109	29.62349	UD	29.1009
6H_W3 Run1	15.67095	23.81849	UD	21.96371
6H_W4 Run1	15.39073	22.66896	UD	21.24699
6H_W5 Run1	13.92428	22.18005	UD	20.55471
6H_W6 Run1	14.03055	21.75524	UD	20.06527
12H_W2 Run1	19.4112	32.44238	UD	28.32984
12H_W3 Run1	17.80241	26.49061	UD	25.88636
12H_W4 Run1	15.91857	24.03404	UD	23.03298
12H_W5 Run1	15.84926	24.58398	UD	23.44681
12H_W6 Run1	15.4729	22.83451	UD	21.96827
24H_W2 Run1	17.15293	24.6333	26.75323	24.48293
24H_W3 Run1	17.40767	24.99375	26.42691	23.94684
24H_W4 Run1	16.42505	25.36269	26.74911	23.39797
24H_W5 Run1	16.37089	25.04657	26.69651	23.97154
24H_W6 Run1	17.3746	25.96855	27.51078	25.43451
48H_W2 Run1	15.6894	25.16801	35.52612	23.99316
48H_W3 Run1	18.65231	26.87194	29.39544	27.80818
48H_W4 Run1	17.36697	26.02358	28.33878	25.66814
48H_W5 Run1	16.44596	25.85267	27.67722	25.22572
48H_W6 Run1	15.9477	24.2271	26.03422	23.34343
6H_W2 Run 2	20.31034	27.10324	26.97391	29.14951
6H_W3 Run 2	18.20205	27.28152	27.44909	26.25719
6H_W4 Run 2	16.07259	23.68042	24.46336	23.82949
6H_W5 Run 2	17.02644	23.18483	23.84605	24.56414
6H_W6 Run 2	15.45771	22.20309	22.39142	21.11205
12H_W2 Run 2	18.8211	29.41198	26.40886	27.3396
12H_W3 Run 2	19.90455	26.66226	23.82812	22.3554
12H_W4 Run 2	13.83677	24.85633	21.64308	20.18582
12H_W5 Run 2	14.30953	25.29556	21.1938	20.18775
12H_W6 Run 2	13.60364	22.42288	20.55704	17.53985
24H_W2 Run 2	13.61759	27.52695	24.22036	21.22059
24H_W3 Run 2	13.2529	24.82203	23.74909	19.96776
24H_W4 Run 2	12.74498	23.49918	22.73272	18.90335
24H_W5 Run 2	13.37082	22.00348	22.14525	19.16727
24H_W6 Run 2	12.96251	21.68462	22.24778	17.7351
48H_W2 Run 2	22.88317	28.07327	23.92674	32.38262
48H_W3 Run 2	13.04564	23.88698	18.93112	19.73023
48H_W4 Run 2	12.96202	22.00082	19.4514	19.36044
48H_W5 Run 2	13.51286	22.05808	19.03526	18.66145
48H_W6 Run 2	12.80707	20.03041	18.53081	18.76706
6H_W2 Run 3	20.3473	24.79634	31.32788	25.39708

6H_W3 Run 3	18.42889	24.72173	28.84652	26.18982
6H_W4 Run 3	18.08243	23.33308	26.05987	22.94249
6H_W5 Run 3	15.16782	23.3588	27.40777	21.95745
6H_W6 Run 3	15.2789	22.57687	21.42226	20.34159
12H_W2 Run 3	19.52519	23.69151	27.56857	26.8036
12H_W3 Run 3	16.47041	22.11773	22.74546	24.28783
12H_W4 Run 3	16.45006	21.6114	20.55093	22.31586
12H_W5 Run 3	14.7557	21.59923	20.26756	20.9795
12H_W6 Run 3	14.42918	20.76421	20.14113	20.53424
24H_W2 Run 3	16.74474	25.20358	22.95719	23.75245
24H_W3 Run 3	17.77236	21.37768	21.84694	22.58857
24H_W4 Run 3	15.43301	22.0953	20.1475	21.6132
24H_W5 Run 3	16.01784	21.48433	20.98936	21.83946
24H_W6 Run 3	14.34517	21.16296	19.09208	20.56685
48H_W2 Run 3	16.26438	23.07967	21.69001	24.11501
48H_W3 Run 3	14.12392	21.39582	20.32755	19.53867
48H_W4 Run 3	14.89766	21.05183	19.33726	20.10454
48H_W5 Run 3	12.88297	20.92312	18.74007	19.63579
48H_W6 Run 3	13.74665	20.92996	18.94442	19.17006
MEAN	16.03557	23.99238	23.70488	22.76598
SDEV	2.29	2.49	3.78	3.15

UD | Undertermined

B. Selection Endogenous Control : TOP1 vs 18S rRNA		
SD ΔCq value for GOI (ERα, ERβ, ACKR2, ACKR3 & ACKR4)		
Sample	18S rRNA (diluted sample) Endogenous Control	TOP1 Control Endogenous
Control	0.744720247	0.319920292
E2 treatment	1.246108747	0.355610818
E2 treatment	0.660374323	0.303617084
E2 treatment	0.419905388	0.227188665
Vehicle Control	1.323677109	0.443335909
Vehicle Control	0.62109493	0.51832386
Vehicle Control	0.659244751	0.634927345
Control	0.24633862	0.449174476
E2 treatment	0.462583494	0.340389235
E2 treatment	0.346700877	0.308143744
E2 treatment	1.561157499	0.477988249
Vehicle Control	0.922640349	0.443335909
Vehicle Control	0.936601536	0.51832386
Vehicle Control	0.41743773	0.634927345
Control	1.625259945	1.202617006
E2 treatment	1.124970562	0.275618561
E2 treatment	0.727867062	0.439390983
E2 treatment	0.849555387	0.694847605
Vehicle Control	1.380429462	0.541645908
Vehicle Control	0.691734377	0.542486947
Vehicle Control	1.104536395	1.067269274
Control	0.166943191	0.491043066
E2 treatment	0.544559991	0.259177547
E2 treatment	0.205946127	0.401341074
E2 treatment	0.75210762	0.7699456
Vehicle Control	1.010467449	0.64844036
Vehicle Control	0.950505943	0.79090475
Vehicle Control	0.577438512	0.651976434
Control	0.452991893	1.203747214

E2 treatment	0.521150376	0.895831639
E2 treatment	0.711405254	0.927570835
E2 treatment	0.760875878	1.017422533
Vehicle Control	0.706645374	0.785921334
Vehicle Control	0.747208986	0.701706672
Vehicle Control	0.598859532	0.672019422
Control	0.719473579	1.033184258
E2 treatment	1.379469038	0.645398448
E2 treatment	1.076507859	0.469454307
E2 treatment	2.280247453	0.241514843
Vehicle Control	1.64761478	0.428441197
Vehicle Control	1.587113949	1.393788953
Vehicle Control	0.808496778	0.386410457
Control	0.744720247	0.319920292
E2 treatment	1.246108747	0.355610818
E2 treatment	0.660374323	0.303617084
E2 treatment	0.419905388	0.227188665
Vehicle Control	1.323677109	0.443335909
Vehicle Control	0.62109493	0.51832386
Vehicle Control	0.659244751	0.634927345
Control	0.304110077	0.607637265
E2 treatment	0.791564556	0.217550401
E2 treatment	0.664708913	0.244824009
E2 treatment	1.816420776	0.604580957
Vehicle Control	0.895839037	0.692617642
Vehicle Control	1.568406648	1.378159042
Vehicle Control	0.334768362	0.956227258
Control	0.827574078	0.15724578
E2 treatment	1.077627093	0.247142186
E2 treatment	0.514185006	0.323046987
E2 treatment	0.647794179	0.326338986
Vehicle Control	1.188315782	0.578116535
Vehicle Control	0.483102139	0.556852511
Vehicle Control	0.886320272	0.880537169
Control	0.700998376	0.397509315
E2 treatment	0.347511779	0.630704216
E2 treatment	0.088061741	0.569507412
E2 treatment	0.892592053	0.825892674
Vehicle Control	0.857397092	0.909910302
Vehicle Control	0.439869886	0.610615045
Vehicle Control	0.359719517	0.888136999
SDEV	0.3	0.2

ANNEXURE II

A. ER α relative gene expression 6H

	Replicate sample	Ct Gene of interest (ER α)	Ct Endogenous Control (TOP1)	Average Δ Ct	$\Delta\Delta$ Ct for replicates ($\Delta\Delta$ Ct = Δ Ct for Treated - Average Δ Ct for Control)	2 ^{^-$\Delta\Delta$Ct} Replicates	Mean Fold change	SDEV
CALIBRATOR SAMPLE (CONTROL_6H)	replicate 1	19.3419	21.05494		-0.12822	1.092946	1.015845	0.211196
	replicate 2	18.81543	20.03612		0.364141	0.776931		
	replicate 3	19.11681	20.93755	-1.58482	-0.23592	1.177657		
1nM_E2	replicate 1	19.67148	21.42191		-0.1656	1.121635	0.868439	0.223404
	replicate 2	18.88564	19.95399		0.516464	0.699083		
	replicate 3	19.18624	20.42109	-1.35121	0.349972	0.784599		
100nM_E2	replicate 1	19.47114	21.15685		-0.10089	1.072437	0.858283	0.188216
	replicate 2	19.29924	20.53167		0.3524	0.78328		
	replicate 3	19.11346	20.22261	-1.34243	0.475674	0.719131		
1 μ M_E2	replicate 1	19.5706	21.09233		0.063093	0.95721	0.813673	0.130577
	replicate 2	18.85661	19.93082		0.510611	0.701925		
	replicate 3	19.48007	20.70992	-1.27527	0.354971	0.781885		
VC_1nM	replicate 1	19.89397	21.84649		-0.36769	1.290288	0.982594	0.296837
	replicate 2	19.42269	20.94792		0.059589	0.959537		
	replicate 3	18.86681	19.93284	-1.5146	0.518787	0.697958		
VC_100nM	replicate 1	19.5118	21.67985		-0.58322	1.498193	1.072851	0.389801
	replicate 2	19.25346	20.82041		0.017878	0.987685		
	replicate 3	18.77801	19.91408	-1.62369	0.448755	0.732675		
VC_1 μ M	replicate 1	19.43886	21.67985		-0.65617	1.575891	1.247068	0.469772
	replicate 2	18.6933	20.82041		-0.54228	1.456276		
	replicate 3	18.82533	19.91408	-1.81895	0.496069	0.709036		

VC - Vehicle control

B. ER α relative gene expression 18H

	Replicate sample	Ct Gene of interest (ER α)	Ct Endogenous Control (TOP1)	Average ΔC_t	$\Delta\Delta C_t$ for replicates ($\Delta\Delta C_t = \Delta C_t$ for Treated - Average ΔC_t for Control)	$2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ for Replicates	Mean Fold change	SDEV
CALIBRATOR SAMPLE (CONTROL_18H)	replicate 1	19.98655	21.35127	-1.8224	0.457644	0.728174	1.032377	0.314794
	replicate 2	20.17684	22.01665		-0.01745	1.012167		
	replicate 3	22.21223	24.47479		-0.4402	1.356789		
1nM_E2	replicate 1	20.78995	22.41105	-1.2349	0.20126	0.86979	0.678405	0.167705
	replicate 2	19.09063	20.1958		0.71719	0.608281		
	replicate 3	19.23732	20.21581		0.843877	0.557145		
100nM_E2	replicate 1	19.50916	20.56667	-0.8791	0.764851	0.588514	0.527683	0.105036
	replicate 2	19.58152	20.63811		0.765778	0.588136		
	replicate 3	19.16817	19.69149		1.299035	0.406398		
1 μ M_E2	replicate 1	19.75905	21.0498	-0.7388	0.531613	0.691781	0.490403	0.174398
	replicate 2	19.05617	19.51902		1.359513	0.389714		
	replicate 3	19.05617	19.51902		1.359513	0.389714		
VC_1nM	replicate 1	19.89397	21.84649	-1.5146	-0.13015	1.094411	0.833428	0.251775
	replicate 2	19.42269	20.94792		0.297127	0.813871		
	replicate 3	18.86681	19.93284		0.756325	0.592002		
VC_100nM	replicate 1	19.5118	21.67985	-1.6237	-0.34569	1.270754	0.909983	0.330626
	replicate 2	19.25346	20.82041		0.255416	0.837746		
	replicate 3	18.77801	19.91408		0.686293	0.621448		
VC_1 μ M	replicate 1	19.43886	21.67985	-1.819	-0.41863	1.336658	1.057752	0.398456
	replicate 2	18.6933	20.82041		-0.30475	1.235201		
	replicate 3	18.82533	19.91408		0.733607	0.601398		

VC Vehicle control

ANNEXURE II

C. ERβ relative gene expression 6H

	Replicate sample	Ct Gene of interest (ERβ)	Ct Endogenous Control (TOP1)	ΔC_t (C _t GOI - C _t EC Gene)	Average ΔC_t	$\Delta\Delta C_t$ for replicates ($\Delta\Delta C_t = \Delta C_t$ for Treated - Average ΔC_t for Control)	$2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ Replicates	Mean Fold change	SDEV
CALIBRATOR SAMPLE (CONTROL_6H)	replicate 1	30.88929	21.0549	9.83434	9.719	0.1153	0.923188	1.0722	0.5
	replicate 2	30.34307	20.0361	10.3069		0.58791	0.665307		
	replicate 3	29.95338	20.9376	9.01583		-0.70321	1.628124		
1nM_E2	replicate 1	30.69368	21.4219	9.27177	9.5185	-0.44727	1.363455	1.1629	0.22
	replicate 2	29.76998	19.954	9.81598		0.09694	0.935013		
	replicate 3	29.88898	20.4211	9.46789		-0.25115	1.190159		
100nM_E2	replicate 1	30.17334	21.1569	9.01649	9.4269	-0.70255	1.627384	1.2619	0.37
	replicate 2	29.90557	20.5317	9.37391		-0.34514	1.270271		
	replicate 3	30.11306	20.2226	9.89045		0.17141	0.887973		
1μM_E2	replicate 1	29.71369	21.0923	8.62136	9.4166	-1.09768	2.14011	1.3388	0.7
	replicate 2	29.8373	19.9308	9.90648		0.18744	0.878166		
	replicate 3	30.43187	20.7099	9.72194		0.0029	0.99799		
VC_1nM	replicate 1	30.79067	21.8465	8.94419	9.4602	-0.77485	1.711018	1.2525	0.45
	replicate 2	30.36003	20.9479	9.41211		-0.30694	1.237078		
	replicate 3	29.95712	19.9328	10.0243		0.30523	0.809313		
VC_100nM	replicate 1	30.50181	21.6798	8.82196	9.4301	-0.89708	1.862292	1.2832	0.51
	replicate 2	30.42438	20.8204	9.60397		-0.11507	1.083031		
	replicate 3	29.77837	19.9141	9.86429		0.14525	0.904222		
VC_1μM	replicate 1	30.0919	21.6798	8.41205	9.3163	-1.307	2.474257	1.5521	0.95
	replicate 2	29.86361	20.8204	9.0432		-0.67584	1.597525		
	replicate 3	30.40761	19.9141	10.4935		0.77449	0.584596		

VC - Vehicle control

ANNEXURE II

D. ER β relative gene expression 18H

	Replicate sample	Ct Gene of interest (ER β)	Ct Endogenous Control (TOP1)	ΔC_t (C_t GOI - C_t EC Gene)	Average ΔC_t	$\Delta\Delta C_t$ for replicates ($\Delta\Delta C_t = \Delta C_t$ for Treated - Average ΔC_t for Control)	$2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ Replicates	Mean Fold change	SDEV
CALIBRATOR SAMPLE (CONTROL_18H)	replicate 1	30.2297	21.3513	8.878452	8.512852	0.3656	0.7761	1.0412	0.38
	replicate 2	30.722	22.0167	8.705385		0.1925	0.8751		
	replicate 3	32.4295	24.4748	7.954718		-0.5581	1.4724		
1nM_E2	replicate 1	31.1206	22.411	8.709518	8.992913	0.1967	0.8726	0.7248	0.13
	replicate 2	29.2471	20.1958	9.051311		0.5385	0.6885		
	replicate 3	29.4337	20.2158	9.217909		0.7051	0.6134		
100nM_E2	replicate 1	29.607	20.5667	9.040287	9.409533	0.5274	0.6938	0.5508	0.15
	replicate 2	29.9897	20.6381	9.351631		0.8388	0.5591		
	replicate 3	29.5282	19.6915	9.836679		1.3238	0.3995		
1 μ M_E2	replicate 1	29.9493	21.0498	8.8995	9.785139	0.3866	0.7649	0.4582	0.27
	replicate 2	29.6795	19.519	10.16052		1.6477	0.3192		
	replicate 3	29.8144	19.519	10.2954		1.7825	0.2907		
VC_1nM	replicate 1	29.711	21.8465	7.864517	8.606161	-0.6483	1.5674	1.0066	0.49
	replicate 2	29.8358	20.9479	8.887831		0.375	0.7711		
	replicate 3	28.999	19.9328	9.066135		0.5533	0.6815		
VC_100nM	replicate 1	31.7309	21.6798	10.05107	9.139768	1.5382	0.3443	0.7072	0.32
	replicate 2	29.5563	20.8204	8.735865		0.223	0.8568		
	replicate 3	28.5464	19.9141	8.63237		0.1195	0.9205		
VC_1 μ M	replicate 1	29.9547	21.6798	8.274832	8.94995	-0.238	1.1794	0.7906	0.36
	replicate 2	29.8194	20.8204	8.999004		0.4862	0.7139		
	replicate 3	29.4901	19.9141	9.576014		1.0632	0.4786		

VC - Vehicle control

ANNEXURE III

A. ACKR2 relative gene expression 6H

	Replicate sample	Ct Gene of interest (ACKR 2)	Ct Endogenous Control (TOP1)	ΔC_t (C _t GOI - C _t EC Gene)	Average ΔC_t	$\Delta\Delta C_t$ for replicates ($\Delta\Delta C_t = \Delta C_t$ for Treated - Average ΔC_t for Control)	$2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ Replicates	Mean Fold change	SDEV
CALIBRATOR SAMPLE (CONTROL_6H)	replicate 1	27.9109	21.0549	6.856		1.0802	0.47297		
	replicate 2	26.0294	20.0361	5.9933		0.2175	0.86008		
	replicate 3	25.4157	20.9376	4.4781	5.7758	-1.2977	2.45829	1.2638	1.05
1nM_E2	replicate 1	28.1383	21.4219	6.7164		0.9406	0.52103		
	replicate 2	25.8766	19.954	5.9226		0.1469	0.90322		
	replicate 3	25.3495	20.4211	4.9284	5.8558	-0.8474	1.7992	1.0745	0.66
100nM_E2	replicate 1	27.9257	21.1569	6.7688		0.993	0.50242		
	replicate 2	26.2612	20.5317	5.7295		-0.0463	1.03261		
	replicate 3	25.141	20.2226	4.9184	5.8056	-0.8574	1.81179	1.1156	0.66
1uM_E2	replicate 1	27.9702	21.0923	6.8779		1.1021	0.46584		
	replicate 2	25.8821	19.9308	5.9513		0.1755	0.88545		
	replicate 3	25.5556	20.7099	4.8457	5.8916	-0.9301	1.90544	1.0856	0.74
VC_1nM	replicate 1	28.3903	21.8465	6.5438		0.768	0.58724		
	replicate 2	26.4287	20.9479	5.4808		-0.295	1.22688		
	replicate 3	24.9423	19.9328	5.0095	5.678	-0.7663	1.70088	1.1717	0.56
VC_100nM	replicate 1	28.0511	21.6798	6.3712		0.5955	0.66184		
	replicate 2	26.2909	20.8204	5.4705		-0.3053	1.23569		
	replicate 3	24.9029	19.9141	4.9889	5.6102	-0.7869	1.72541	1.2076	0.53
VC_1uM	replicate 1	27.8367	21.6798	6.1568		0.3811	0.76788		
	replicate 2	25.7751	20.8204	4.9547		-0.8211	1.76671		
	replicate 3	24.9493	19.9141	5.0352	5.3823	-0.7406	1.67086	1.4018	0.55

VC

Vehicle Control

ANNEXURE III

B. ACKR2 relative gene expression 18H

	Replicate sample	Ct Gene of interest (ACKR2)	Ct Endogenous Control (TOP1)	ΔC_t (Ct GOI - Ct EC Gene)	Average ΔC_t	$\Delta\Delta C_t$ for replicates ($\Delta\Delta C_t = \Delta C_t$ for Treated - Average ΔC_t for Control)	$2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ Replicates	Mean Fold change	SDEV
CALIBRATOR SAMPLE (CONTROL_18H)	replicate 1	25.9037	21.3513	4.55246	3.72086	0.8316	0.56191	1.0805	0.47
	replicate 2	25.1871	22.0167	3.17042		-0.55045	1.46454		
	replicate 3	27.9145	24.4748	3.43971		-0.28115	1.21517		
1nM_E2	replicate 1	27.575	22.411	5.16391	4.67642	1.44305	0.36779	0.5532	0.26
	replicate 2	25.1166	20.1958	4.92083		1.19997	0.43528		
	replicate 3	24.1603	20.2158	3.94451		0.22365	0.8564		
100nM_E2	replicate 1	25.9934	20.5667	5.42673	4.98028	1.70587	0.30654	0.4328	0.14
	replicate 2	25.6614	20.6381	5.02333		1.30247	0.40543		
	replicate 3	24.1823	19.6915	4.49079		0.76993	0.58645		
1uM_E2	replicate 1	26.4097	21.0498	5.35987	5.63871	1.63901	0.32108	0.2672	0.05
	replicate 2	25.2933	19.519	5.77427		2.05341	0.24091		
	replicate 3	25.301	19.519	5.782		2.06113	0.23963		
VC_1nM	replicate 1	25.9037	21.3513	4.55246	3.72086	0.8316	0.56191	1.0805	0.47
	replicate 2	25.1871	22.0167	3.17042		-0.55045	1.46454		
	replicate 3	27.9145	24.4748	3.43971		-0.28115	1.21517		
VC_100nM	replicate 1	25.9037	21.3513	4.55246	3.72086	0.8316	0.56191	1.0805	0.47
	replicate 2	25.1871	22.0167	3.17042		-0.55045	1.46454		
	replicate 3	27.9145	24.4748	3.43971		-0.28115	1.21517		
VC_1µM	replicate 1	25.9037	21.3513	4.55246	3.72086	0.8316	0.56191	1.0805	0.47
	replicate 2	25.1871	22.0167	3.17042		-0.55045	1.46454		
	replicate 3	27.9145	24.4748	3.43971		-0.28115	1.21517		
VC									
								Vehicle Control	

ANNEXURE III

C. ACKR3 relative gene expression 6H

	Replicate sample	Ct Gene of interest (ACKR3)	Ct Endogenous Control (TOP1)	ΔC_t (C _t GOI - C _t EC Gene)	Average ΔC_t	$\Delta \Delta C_t$ for replicates ($\Delta \Delta C_t = \Delta C_t$ for Treated - Average ΔC_t for Control)	$2^{-\Delta \Delta C_t}$ Replicates	Mean Fold change	SDEV
CALIBRATOR SAMPLE (CONTROL_6H)	replicate 1	19.3419	21.05494	-1.713		-0.128222	1.0929		
	replicate 2	18.81543	20.03612	-1.2207		0.364141	0.7769		
	replicate 3	19.11681	20.93755	-1.8207	-1.5848	-0.23592	1.1777	1.0158	0.211
1nM_E2	replicate 1	19.67148	21.42191	-1.7504		-0.165604	1.1216		
	replicate 2	18.88564	19.95399	-1.0684		0.516464	0.6991		
	replicate 3	19.18624	20.42109	-1.2349	-1.3512	0.349972	0.7846	0.8684	0.223
100nM_E2	replicate 1	19.47114	21.15685	-1.6857		-0.100893	1.0724		
	replicate 2	19.29924	20.53167	-1.2324		0.3524	0.7833		
	replicate 3	19.11346	20.22261	-1.1091	-1.3424	0.475674	0.7191	0.8583	0.188
1uM_E2	replicate 1	19.5706	21.09233	-1.5217		0.063093	0.9572		
	replicate 2	18.85661	19.93082	-1.0742		0.510611	0.7019		
	replicate 3	19.48007	20.70992	-1.2299	-1.2753	0.354971	0.7819	0.8137	0.131
VC_1nM	replicate 1	19.89397	21.84649	-1.9525		-0.367693	1.2903		
	replicate 2	19.42269	20.94792	-1.5252		0.059589	0.9595		
	replicate 3	18.86681	19.93284	-1.066	-1.5146	0.518787	0.698	0.9826	0.297
VC_100nM	replicate 1	19.5118	21.67985	-2.168		-0.583223	1.4982		
	replicate 2	19.25346	20.82041	-1.5669		0.017878	0.9877		
	replicate 3	18.77801	19.91408	-1.1361	-1.6237	0.448755	0.7327	1.0729	0.39
VC_1uM	replicate 1	19.43886	21.67985	-2.241		-0.656168	1.5759		
	replicate 2	18.6933	20.82041	-2.1271		-0.542284	1.4563		
	replicate 3	18.82533	19.91408	-1.0888	-1.819	0.496069	0.709	1.2471	0.47

VC

Vehicle Control

ANNEXURE III

D. ACKR3 relative gene expression 18H

	Replicate sample	Ct Gene of interest (ACKR 3)	Ct Endogenous Control (TOP1)	ΔC_t (C _t GOI - C _t EC Gene)	Average ΔC_t	$\Delta\Delta C_t$ for replicates ($\Delta\Delta C_t = \Delta C_t$ for Treated - Average ΔC_t for Control)	$2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ Replicates	Mean Fold change	SDEV
CALIBRATOR SAMPLE (CONTROL_18H)	replicate 1	22.9417	21.351	1.59042	1.06758	0.522843	0.696	1.0628	0.47
	replicate 2	23.228	22.017	1.21137		0.143794	0.9051		
	replicate 3	24.8757	24.475	0.40094		-0.66664	1.5874		
1nM_E2	replicate 1	24.0322	22.411	1.62114	1.7243	0.553563	0.6813	0.639	0.09
	replicate 2	22.17	20.196	1.97424		0.906659	0.5334		
	replicate 3	21.7933	20.216	1.57751		0.509936	0.7023		
100nM_E2	replicate 1	22.5758	20.567	2.00917	1.83102	0.941598	0.5207	0.5949	0.1
	replicate 2	22.19	20.638	1.55185		0.484276	0.7149		
	replicate 3	21.6235	19.691	1.93204		0.864461	0.5493		
1uM_E2	replicate 1	23.0337	21.05	1.98392	2.47449	0.916339	0.5299	0.3982	0.15
	replicate 2	21.8086	19.519	2.28963		1.222054	0.4287		
	replicate 3	22.6689	19.519	3.14992		2.082339	0.2361		
VC_1nM	replicate 1	21.7477	21.846	-0.0988	0.66488	-1.16633	2.2444	1.4314	0.72
	replicate 2	21.7888	20.948	0.84085		-0.22672	1.1702		
	replicate 3	21.1854	19.933	1.25253		0.184956	0.8797		
VC_100nM	replicate 1	24.548	21.68	2.86811	1.33902	1.800538	0.2871	1.067	0.77
	replicate 2	21.7766	20.82	0.95622		-0.11136	1.0802		
	replicate 3	20.1068	19.914	0.19273		-0.87484	1.8338		
VC_1µM	replicate 1	22.413	21.68	0.7332	1.6605	-0.33438	1.2608	0.7618	0.47
	replicate 2	22.4255	20.82	1.60505		0.537474	0.689		
	replicate 3	22.5573	19.914	2.64324		1.575663	0.3355		

VC

Vehicle Control

ANNEXURE III

E. ACKR4 relative gene expression 6H

	Replicate sample	Ct Gene of interest (ACKR4)	Ct Endogenous Control (TOP1)	ΔC_t (C_t GOI - C_t EC Gene)	Average ΔC_t	$\Delta\Delta C_t$ for replicate s ($\Delta\Delta C_t = \Delta C_t$ for Treated - Average ΔC_t for Control)	$2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ Replicates	Mean Fold change	SDEV
CALIBRATOR SAMPLE (CONTROL_6H)	replicate 1	26.6447	21.0549	5.58972	5.408595	0.18112	0.882015	1.00388	0.11
	replicate 2	25.3431	20.0361	5.307		-0.1016	1.072959		
	replicate 3	26.2666	20.9376	5.32907		-0.0795	1.056674		
1nM_E2	replicate 1	26.8391	21.4219	5.41721	5.607084	0.00861	0.994047	0.87978	0.14
	replicate 2	25.4715	19.954	5.51752		0.10893	0.927278		
	replicate 3	26.3076	20.4211	5.88652		0.47792	0.71801		
100nM_E2	replicate 1	26.579	21.1569	5.42213	5.565278	0.01354	0.990661	0.91154	0.19
	replicate 2	25.8702	20.5317	5.33854		-0.0701	1.049759		
	replicate 3	26.1578	20.2226	5.93517		0.52657	0.694203		
1uM_E2	replicate 1	26.3012	21.0923	5.20891	5.508038	-0.1997	1.148446	0.94912	0.21
	replicate 2	25.39	19.9308	5.45913		0.05054	0.965578		
	replicate 3	26.566	20.7099	5.85607		0.44747	0.733326		
VC_1nM	replicate 1	27.4697	21.8465	5.62323	5.92369	0.21463	0.861767	0.73482	0.26
	replicate 2	26.5056	20.9479	5.55768		0.14908	0.901825		
	replicate 3	26.523	19.9328	6.59017		1.18157	0.440871		
VC_100nM	replicate 1	26.3767	21.6798	4.69687	5.056656	-0.7117	1.637759	1.33579	0.45
	replicate 2	25.5954	20.8204	4.77503		-0.6336	1.551398		
	replicate 3	25.6121	19.9141	5.69807		0.28947	0.818201		
VC_1uM	replicate 1	26.3002	21.6798	4.62032	4.997165	-0.7883	1.727012	1.48218	0.73
	replicate 2	25.1882	20.8204	4.36777		-1.0408	2.057411		
	replicate 3	25.9175	19.9141	6.00341		0.59482	0.662129		

VC

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ANNEXURE III

F. ACKR4 relative gene expression 18H

	Replicate sample	Ct Gene of interest (ACKR4)	Ct Endogenous Control (TOP1)	ΔC_t (Ct GOI - Ct EC Gene)	Average ΔC_t	$\Delta \Delta C_t$ for replicates ($\Delta \Delta C_t = \Delta C_t$ for Treated - Average ΔC_t for Control)	$2^{\Delta \Delta C_t}$ Replicates	Mean Fold change	SDEV
CALIBRATOR SAMPLE (CONTROL_18H)	replicate 1	25.8971	21.3513	4.54582	4.4711	0.07475	0.9495	1.0261	0.29
	replicate 2	26.0582	22.0167	4.0415		-0.4296	1.3468		
	replicate 3	29.3007	24.4748	4.8259		0.35483	0.782		
1nM_E2	replicate 1	26.5514	22.411	4.14039	4.713	-0.3307	1.2576	0.8984	0.36
	replicate 2	24.8054	20.1958	4.60961		0.13853	0.9084		
	replicate 3	25.6048	20.2158	5.38902		0.91794	0.5293		
100nM_E2	replicate 1	24.9527	20.5667	4.38601	4.9625	-0.0851	1.0607	0.7489	0.29
	replicate 2	25.6148	20.6381	4.97672		0.50565	0.7043		
	replicate 3	25.2162	19.6915	5.52475		1.05368	0.4817		
1uM_E2	replicate 1	25.3411	21.0498	4.2913	5.2358	-0.1798	1.1327	0.6613	0.41
	replicate 2	25.1131	19.519	5.59412		1.12305	0.4591		
	replicate 3	25.3411	19.519	5.82208		1.35101	0.392		
VC_1nM	replicate 1	24.6806	21.8465	2.83409	3.865	-1.637	3.1102	1.7519	1.18
	replicate 2	25.1526	20.9479	4.20464		-0.2664	1.2028		
	replicate 3	24.489	19.9328	4.55619		0.08511	0.9427		
VC_100nM	replicate 1	26.3961	21.6798	4.71621	4.1589	0.24513	0.8437	1.3193	0.57
	replicate 2	24.3266	20.8204	3.5062		-0.9649	1.9519		
	replicate 3	24.1683	19.9141	4.25422		-0.2169	1.1622		
VC_1μM	replicate 1	24.87	21.6798	3.19013	4.0478	-1.2809	2.43	1.5123	0.87
	replicate 2	24.8102	20.8204	3.98974		-0.4813	1.396		
	replicate 3	24.8776	19.9141	4.96356		0.49248	0.7108		

VC

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